

BACHELOR OF ARTS IN MULTIMEDIA STUDIES
Capstone/Special Project

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

BACHELOR OF ARTS IN MULTIMEDIA STUDIES

DEPANTE, AIRIEL LICCA

**#MOOTOO: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON MAMAMOO AS PURVEYOR OF
FEMINISM IDEALS**

Thesis Adviser:

RODA L. TAJON

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

18 September 2024

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Student's signature:

Thesis adviser signature:

University Permission Page

#MOOTOO: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON MAMAMOO AS PURVEYOR OF FEMINISM IDEALS

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

Ariel Licca Depante September 18, 2024

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **AIRIEL LICCA DEPANTE** with the title: “**#MOOTOO: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON MAMAMOO AS PURVEYOR OF FEMINISM IDEALS**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

RODA L. TAJON
Adviser

September 18, 2024

(Date)

DR. EMELY M. AMOZOLA
Program Chair

(Date)

DR. DIEGO S. MARANAN
Dean
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

18 September 2024
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Airiel Licca Depante is an aspiring multimedia artist from Quezon City, Philippines. She graduated from Colegio de San Lorenzo under the Humanities and Social Sciences strand.

Aside from a full-time student she is also a full-time nerd and fangirl, obsessing over the likes of video games (Assassin's Creed, Hades, Stardew Valley, Minecraft, etc.), movies (Fight Club, Heathers, The Handmaiden, Everything Everywhere All at Once, Dragon Ball Super: Super Hero, etc.) and music (MAMAMOO, Purple Kiss, Onewe, Oneus, Billie Eilish, etc.). Her love and support for MAMAMOO have contributed to her desire to create a study on media and Feminism.

In addition to being a full-time student and a full-time nerd and fangirl, Airiel also focuses on the technological aspects of multimedia, wherein she takes the time to study video editing production as this is the initial forte that she truly wants to focus on.

With that in mind, she primarily focuses on scrutinizing details of production and storyline-wise in videos, hence why she wanted to analyze further MAMAMOO and their presentation of storytelling in their music videos and lyrics. At the same time, Airiel believes the topic of Feminism is a silent advocate for the issue. Hence, she

combined and analyzed MAMAMOO's presentation and representation and their advocacy for Feminism.

Acknowledgment

First and foremost, I would like to thank the people I call my family, from my biological family to my friends, who I can call my other home: the Brodettes, MMM cuties, ring people, and several others who have been curious of this research while I was conceptualizing it, thank you. I truly appreciate every single one of you, especially those who even wanted to help me transcribe my work. You know who you are, thank you.

Second, I would like to thank Ms. Roda Lawrence Tajon; without her continued support, this research would not have been finished. Her continued hands-on approach to ensuring I can reach out to her any day and time is truly appreciated. I would also like to thank my critic, Ms. Ruth Rodriguez, for giving her advice and constructive feedback, which has helped my research tremendously. Thank you, Ma'am Roda and Ma'am Ruth, for everything.

Third, I would also like to thank my fur-nieces, Julianne and Fivvy. Even if sometimes they annoy me with their constant zoomies and cry for food, I still love them to death and appreciate their presence in making this research less lonely.

Last but not least, I would like to thank MAMAMOO. These four women have given me the needed inspiration and boost with their empowerment and constant indirect reassurances through their guest appearances, songs, music videos, and

even informal live videos such as BStage, Instagram, and YouTube. Without them, this research would never have been possible, and without them giving me the strength, I would have never finished this research. A wishful dream of mine is for them to be able to read this research to see the impact they have made on people like me and the respondents. Thank you for everything, MAMAMOO, saranghanuuu, and I will never let go!

A group photo opportunity with Solar, the leader of MAMAMOO.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	vi
Table of Contents	viii
ABSTRACT	x
I. INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Study	1
Objectives/Statement of the Problem	4
Theoretical Framework	5
Significance of the Study	7
II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	8
The Grueling History of K-Pop Girl Groups in Society	8
The Use of Songs and Aesthetics as Means...	10
The Relationship of K-Pop Girl Groups on Feminism	12
MAMAMOO and Feminism	13
III. METHODOLOGY	16
IV. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA	18
Content Analysis	18
Fans' perception of Feminism while listening to MAMAMOO	21
Definition of Feminism and Feminist Ideals	25
Influences and Reception to Fandom	27
V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	33
Summary and Conclusion	33
Recommendations	35

BIBLIOGRAPHY	37
APPENDICES	42

Abstract

Feminism has been a polarizing topic for many years and decades, challenging the norms of how women should follow in accord breaking the barrier for people who are marginalized due to their gender and sexuality. At the same time, music artists have been creating subtle messages for listeners and audiences to catch onto their hidden advocacies that can help either empower said listeners and audiences or be taken aback by their music or performances. This is no different with K-pop idols, where some write their songs and insert themes that either divide audiences or unite them due to messages inserted, like environmental issues, feminism, and mental health. One of the well-known K-pop girl groups that have been outspoken in advocacy for feminism has been MAMAMOO. Based on the findings, MAMAMOO does have an influence on how feminism has been perceived by fans, creating a platform that can help avid and other casual listeners to identify female empowerment and be influenced by the girl group. However, it should be noted that not all feminist issues were tackled by MAMAMOO, leaving room for more before fully calling them a feminist girl group.

Keywords: MAMAMOO, Feminism, Lyrics, Music Video, Music Video Aesthetics

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The latter half of the past century witnessed the emergence of the 'East' in global popular culture. With Works like Manga, Anime, Martial Art Films, and many more that created a global phenomenon that flourished and has taken by storm (Inwood, 2012).

With the rise of Korean Pop Music, the increase in double standards against women comes into play. South Korea is notorious for having a masculine and patriarchal mindset wherein women are not much given a chance to let themselves shine. Men are typically celebrated, whereas women are judged based on their appearance. This is mentioned by former K-pop singer, Way, that there are stricter rules when it comes to women idols than men (Chung, 2020). In an opinion piece by Khan (2021), mentions the accounts of former idol-turned-actress, Kim Jae-Hyung, wherein she and her group were forced to participate in weekly weight checks, displaying their weight on the wall to "motivate" them to compare with one another.

In a 2019 poll by Hanbok Research Company (Reuters, 2021), 58.6% of South Korean men who are among the 20s' and early 30s' opposes feminism in their country. Meanwhile 25.9% of the respondents strongly opposes feminism rating it of a scale of 0 to 12 on how much intensity does their opposition place (Park, 2021). This is rooted due to men's belief on feminism being the driving factor for their difficulty in society and economic aspects (Moon, 2022). Furthermore, since women

were giving more opportunities, this can be a way for men to lose their standing on society and see themselves as a victim of Feminism (Park, 2021).

Park Hee-a, a journalist, states:

The stronger feminism grows in society, the more girl groups will have to distance themselves from it to ease their male fans. There are both supporters and antis of feminism, but society is so polarized that just speaking about it can send the wrong message...Feminism tells women that they can and they should be vocal about their rights, but that's not the case for girl groups. If they do, then that's interpreted as a symbol of distancing themselves from men. They get trapped more and more in the idolized version of women (So-Yeon, 2022).

With the rise of the '#MeToo Movement' in Western Countries, it has taken a form of its own life in the East side of the world, more specifically in South Korea, wherein women have spoken out against the treatment of sexual harassment, abuse, threats, and many more ill intentions that East Asian women have faced in their everyday lives. (Haynes & Chen, 2018).

K-pop girl groups have also voiced their concerns about women's empowerment, creating a double-edged sword scenario wherein they are ridiculed by the public but empowering their fellow women. One of the prominent examples is f(x)'s Sulli, a non-conforming K-pop idol who broke barriers in the stereotype of the K-pop world. However, her actions for empowerment had a price for her mental

health due to the harassment and criticism she has received online, eventually being the cause of her tragically taking her own life (McCurry, 2019).

One of the most vocal groups is MAMAMOO. In 2014, four women entered Rainbowbridge World (RBW), a Korean entertainment industry, as individuals trying to get their talents known. These four women, collectively known as MAMAMOO, were vastly different yet compatible with one another. Their breakthrough has finally seen them advocate for women's rights and opinions that were usually frowned upon. Beauty standards, age discrimination, LGBTQ+ rights, and being as excellent as men are messages that MAMAMOO has generally incorporated into their lyrics. Songs such as 'Yes I Am,' 'HIP,' and 'Gogobebe' are some examples of their advocacy. Yeung (2017) mentions in a review that MAMAMOO's 'Yes I Am' "values confidence over conformity," believing in individuality while showing off an empowering scene for confident women. Feminism is their number one advocacy for themselves and their fans. In this research, the researcher would like to explore further if these messages have helped fans recognize feminism as a whole and if MAMAMOO lyrics have impacted their perspective or feeling of empowerment on feminism and have either positively or negatively impacted it.

The researcher primarily focuses on MAMAMOO due to personal impact MAMAMOO has made towards the researcher, wherein they felt belong or rather seen due to the theme and plot of their songs and music videos. Aside from that, various comments and opinions that were made online, wherein there was an impact that MAMAMOO has brought to their life through social media has piqued the researcher's interest and the possible contribution of seeing K-pop music in a

different light due to the different messages that listeners can perceive MAMAMOO's songs.

Objectives/Statement of the Problem:

This study aims to assess the influence and representation of MAMAMOO on feminist ideals to the fans, specifically on their works, such as songs and music video aesthetics.

In particular, the researcher aims to answer these questions:

- I. What feminist ideals do the works of MAMAMOO embody?
- II. How representative of the Feminist theory is in the works of MAMAMOO?
- III. How can K-pop Songs and Aesthetics be used as a platform for advocacy on feminism and the rights of women and people of diverse SOGIESC?
- IV. How can K-Pop Girl Groups capture and reflect the feminism discourse?

Theoretical Framework:

The study was primarily based on the principles of Liberal Feminism.

Feminism is the promotion of equality in the sexes in terms of economic, social, and political. Eastern Kentucky University (n.d.) mentions how feminism has evolved from inequality between sexes to the promotion of different genders and sexuality and how its construction can be seen in society, a modern take on the theory of feminism. Several theories have come about with the surge of feminism. Some include 'cultural feminism,' 'radical feminism,' 'postmodern feminism,' and 'contemporary feminism,' which all have a different way of critiquing societal norms

usually seen in a patriarchal setting. Feminism is also not a way of oppressing the opposite gender. Instead, it is a way of contesting daily limits and barriers women tend to experience (Ebert, 1991). One of the famous feminist theories that the researcher would like to use further as a principle is liberal feminism. In relation to popular culture, Hollows & Moseley (2006, p. 4-5), refers to the gender inequality that has occurred in the media industry due to the “patriarchal mass culture” or a male-dominated society. Thus, feminism opens the way to challenge what the societal norm was and created an intervention to provide platforms and presentations on how women should be treated and challenge patriarchal meanings.

Liberal feminism is defined as creating an environment wherein equal rights can be distributed in terms of laws, authorities, and institutions for both men and women. Taken from the philosophy of Liberalism, it primarily seeks to enhance an individual’s freedom further while also changing laws and policies that oppose and discriminate rights for all. Rights such as freedom of speech and choice for women are some of the factors that liberal feminism primarily focuses on. Meanwhile, this theory focuses on achieving individual elements that can primarily benefit oneself, such as self-realization, modern agency, and rationality (V, 2018). Oxley (2011) summarizes the intent of liberal feminism, stating that “the message of liberal feminism remains the same: women, as rational human beings, are deserving of the same social and political rights as men and gender justice is best achieved by modifying existing social institutions and political systems.” In terms of popular culture with liberal feminism, it can be seen with several media forms such as movies like *Legally Blonde*, and songs like *Power* by Little Mix. This creates a form of movement that empowers women to be as equal as men. Through this theory, liberal

feminism can be used as a lens to assess further MAMAMOO's lyrics and music video aesthetics while also understanding the fans' perspective on MAMAMOO's songs and videos and how it can be interpreted as a form of feminism that advocates for Liberalism.

Significance of the Study

The research findings aim to provide information beneficial to those regarding the chosen topic, especially to the fans of MAMAMOO, the fans of K-Pop in general, Feminism Advocates, Multimedia Scholars, and Future Researchers. Primarily contributing to those who want further analysis of pop culture through the lens of feminist theory, using songs and lyrics to understand how multimedia and pop culture can be a way to advocate their ideals for society.

The findings of this research hope to bring some significance to the categories of beneficiaries to fully integrate and understand how each meaning of the lyrics and music video aesthetic from their song has an impactful outlook on feminism and women's rights. This, in turn, will give a form of understanding of the role of K-pop not only in pop culture but also in promoting various theories and advocacies in society. Each beneficiary has a different perspective or outcome of how the research will be seen. This, in turn, will give an outlook on how each different multimedia aesthetic can be a form of feminism within the media that MAMAMOO wants to portray.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Numerous studies have come to fruition regarding the topic of K-Pop. From the statistical amount of global income K-Pop Idols have brought into their home country to how each intricate detail of a K-Pop concept can show off meaning to their audiences, there is bound to be a topic related to K-Pop itself and the different K-Pop Idols. This review explores the influence of K-pop idols, feminism, and the relationship between MAMAMOO and Feminism, specifically examining their lyrics and visual aesthetics on how it has become a purveyor in the form of feminism for fans and listeners alike.

The Grueling History of K-Pop Girl Groups in Society.

Korean Pop Culture has been a staple since the 1990s with the rise of different forms of media. So, with the rise of Seo Taiji and Boys, the Korean Entertainment Industry knew that they had hit the jackpot with the public. Therefore, different companies and industries have tried to find the next big thing for music. Different men and women took part in auditions and training to fulfill their dreams of becoming a pop idol. So, it is not surprising that Jonas (2021, p. 2) mentions how these companies and entertainment industries most likely use women as a tool for profit—also mentioning how men were given more value than K-Pop women. Women are given much more or less opportunities than men. In some cases, they were seen less appealing than how men would be perceived by the public (Primer, 2023). However, this is not simply due to no reason but instead to a long history of patriarchal culture wedged within South Korea, enforcing standards that must be

reached higher for women than men (Lin & Rudolf, 2017). The activities of girl groups become formulaic due to the social expiration date imposed on them. Jones (2021, p. 4) also mentions that members of large girl groups are simply pretty and given shallow concepts that can be easily replaced by younger idols once deemed too old for the public. However, even with the preceding research stating the negative status of women in K-pop, there is a history of the use of women in terms of girl crush.

Sun et al. (2022) describe girl crush as:

An overarching K-pop concept with dynamic meanings that can refer to different aspects of a girl group: bold and challenging music lyrics strong and fierce performances characterized by sartorial descriptors, such as "masculinized" clothes, haircuts, and attitudes or music videos representing edgy and bold women... At its core, it conveys a relatability that inspires audiences to embrace a confident and empowering female attitude, rejecting the stereotypical female images and traditional gender norms to pursue independence.

Although girl crush may seem a positive trait and empowering, Sun et al. continues to emphasize that the girl crush of today is more of a cash grab, presenting itself as a "faux feminist marketing strategy" who tries to defy the South Korean world of patriarchy but essentially falls under the greedy world. At the same time, women outside of K-pop, women are still treated awfully due to the patriarchal world of South Korea.

Whether through cutesy or sexy forms of content, women are more of a state of money source to gain income for the entertainment industries. Even with the rampant "girl crush" or "feminism" in some girl groups, this can still be seen as a way to capitalize on this type of market strategy. Although Jonas (2021) has briefly mentioned MAMAMOO in their study, the girl group has not been further delved into, brushing through as an example in terms of girl crush and girl groups in South Korea

The Use of Songs and Aesthetics as Means of Spreading Advocacy on Feminism

With music, there are several ways to incorporate subtle messages and meanings throughout the song. Instances wherein lyrics have been bold in proclaiming advocacy for feminism or subtle words that might be an easy-to-understand type of message but something that needs to be further evaluated.

However, when it comes to Feminism, Rodnitzsky (1975) stresses that many feminist singers need to create different music from men. An example of this is when Ellen Shumsky once left an "all-woman environment" to attend a recent folk festival and was left shocked by the direct and subtle sexism of singers through lyrics and situations.

It is a tell-tale sign of how many messages can be seen in songs that can be offensive or off-putting for some women. Other related research in music and

feminism, such as Dworksy (2019) analyzing Janelle Monae's music and music videos, concludes that Monae's stance on feminism has dramatically influenced her songs and videos, showcasing her opinion on women's rights and how each woman can be empowered through her medium. Another research related to music feminism by Adhitya & Lahari (2019) tackles Lana Del Rey's Ultraviolence album, which primarily focuses on male domination and how women respond to the said patriarchal world.

In terms of K-Pop, Li (2022) focuses on (G)-IDLE's Tomboy concluding that:

The findings are three-fold: first, the MV of Tomboy has shown a postfeminist sensibility by exhibiting an entanglement of feminist and antifeminist signs; second, by focusing on women's collective empowerment and sisterhood, Tomboy signals the intertextuality between feminism and queerness, highlighting the power achieved through sisterhood that is also validated by the fans; third, while Tomboy has carried out empowering messages for women, the fact that it is situated in a highly commercialized K-pop industry has also brought about the drawbacks of celebrity feminism.

Drawing a specific problem that the K-Pop Industry leads to a faux feminist ideal that was previously mentioned above.

Previous studies tell us that there are different studies based on analyzing lyrics and videos as a form of subtle message for advocacy on feminism. However, aside from Li's research, no further research has been found to analyze lyrics for

K-pop girl groups regarding the theory of feminism. Primarily focusing on (G)-IDLE's Tomboy to be the primary analysis of the girl group's advocacy.

The Relationship of K-Pop Girl Groups on feminism.

As mentioned above, feminism has been a polarizing topic in K-pop, especially in South Korea. Instances of backlash and division of opinions have occurred for female Idols who want to showcase their advocacy for their belief. A study by Septiani & Prihatini (2022) shows how Red Velvet (another K-pop girl group) was also subjected to discrimination and backlash. An example of cases like Red Velvet member, Joy, wearing a shirt with a graphic stating 'We All Must Be Feminists.' Certain negative comments were seen due to Joy wearing the said shirt. Another is Red Velvet member, Irene, who admitted to reading a famous Feminist book entitled 'Kim Ji-Young: Born 1982'. This caused an uproar against the Red Velvet member, such as having her merchandise burned by their harsh naysayers. Questioning their values and beliefs due to the supporting, advocating, or mentioning of feminism (Septiani & Prihatini, 2022). However, boy groups were also given some backlash for advocating feminism through their songs and subtle actions. Like Irene from Red Velvet, Kim Namjoon, famously known as R.M. from BTS, was praised by people in South Korea, although some would criticize him. Even so, Namjoon was given laxer treatment compared to Irene (yckim124, 2018; Herman, 2018).

The studies mentioned above tell us that feminism is a polarizing topic in the South Korean community due to the heavy backlash that idols would receive if subtle actions and messages were inspected closely by the public. Red Velvet was one of

the most significant examples of the research and how their subtle actions led to numerous consequences in the eyes of the people in South Korea. However, MAMAMOO has not been further researched and established if their actions are truly for feminism.

MAMAMOO and Feminism

Upon the rise of stardom, MAMAMOO has become generally known for their outlandish songs and unique appearance and skillset not commonly seen in the K-Pop Industry. MAMAMOO is a group formed back in 2014 where they debuted in a small company called Rainbowbridge World (RBW). Due to their company being generally unknown compared to larger companies like JYP Entertainment, SM Entertainment, and YG Entertainment, RBW was not given much focus, putting more pressure on MAMAMOO to be more successful for their company to thrive.

Kim Yongsun, or Solar, was among the select few to be accepted by Rainbowbridge World even if she was twenty-three years old, an age wherein it was considered too old to audition and how the group was given more pressure since they were deemed 'unpretty' or 'too short' (Jonas, 2021 p. 7-8). However, even with that experience, MAMAMOO continues to spread feminist awareness in other aspects, such as Solar taking the role of an ambassador for Women's Reproductive Health (Solarsido, 2020). At the same time, Solar has also advocated for diversity stating in an interview that "I also hope that we can all enjoy the diversity around the world. Foreign countries are really open minded but I think Korea is still quite conservative. I wish that things can be a little bit more open in this area" (Lee, 2024).

The leader of MAMAMOO has also composed and written a song about showing and being loud and proud of oneself, incorporating kiki or a nonconforming gender ballroom choreography with dancers from the LGBTQ+ community also using the style of voguing which is described as a jazz dance created by the African-American gay community (Koudelová, 2022).

Moon Byulyi, or Moonbyul, was given the role of rapper and has shown an androgynous side and advocacy for feminism, also writing a sapphic erotica song, a massive feat for the general Korean public (Lucas, 2021). In an interview, Moonbyul mentions how she would like to challenge a one-view of gender in songs, stating, "So far, I have been trying to release songs that do not sound either feminine or masculine, because I believe I am quite androgynous," she said. "I want to become a person who can challenge the binary view of gender through music." (Sun-hwa, 2022).

Similarly, Jung Wheein, simply known as Wheein, was one of the few who had written a sapphic love song, embracing love equally for all (MAMAMOO, 2019). Lastly, Ahn Hyejin, famously known as Hwasa, was formerly ridiculed due to her dark skin and thick thighs, a stark difference from the usual Korean Beauty Standards that focus primarily on light-skinned and thin girls (Hwa Sa, 2018). Due to this, she has written and sang songs primarily focusing on loving yourself while showing off your own individuality such as 'I Love My Body' and 'I'm A B'. Her performances also has put her into the spotlight when conservatives filed a police case against her for showing off her provocative side in a university concert (Sun-hwa, 2023). As seen in

the different articles and circumstances, MAMAMOO is no stranger to advocating for feminism due to their past experiences.

In the end, the articles above tell us that there are numerous instances where MAMAMOO showcases feminism due to their experiences using their platform to provide necessary empowerment for those who are undermined.

III. METHODOLOGY

For this study, the researcher used a qualitative method, using Reception Analysis that combines both Focus Group Discussions with twelve (12) respondents conducted last March to April 2024 and Content Analysis. Guided by the use of a feminist framework that sought to recognize the context of gender inequality and the influence of feminism in popular culture.

Most of the respondents that were interviewed were active MAMAMOO fans who have bought merchandise such as albums, photo cards, t-shirts, and posters and have gone to the MAMAMOO concert in the Philippines last February 12, 2023, and the Whee In concert last April 13, 2024. Aside from materialistic ways to support the girl group, the respondents also stream their songs, with one respondent listening to them almost daily. Another respondent uses Korean voting applications such as Mubeat, TheKKing, and IDOLChamp to vote for MAMAMOO in awards and music shows for their new songs or fan activities. Six of the respondents are part of the MAMAMOO Philippines or the MAMAMOO PH Fanbase, with varying positions in the organization, such as overall head, graphics head, technical specialist, secretary, and volunteer of the fanbase group.

These respondents were communicated through Telegram, a messaging application, to further set a time and date for the interview proper. Respondents will also be asked for consent to conduct an oral interview on Google Meet, regarding further information on their feminist perspective, presenting their certification of

Completion for a course on Research on Ethics based on the Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans (TCPS 2: CORE 2022).

The researcher chose both methods as form of further analyzation of their perspective as a fan of MAMAMOO and how each input can lead to a causal or a detrimental outlook on feminism wherein video-based focus group interviews are a form of interview where respondents are asked to discuss and explain their answers pertaining to MAMAMOO and feminism. When transcribing the interviews, the researcher used the free website goodtape.io to easily transcribe what has been spoken in the interview proper. At the same time, a thorough manual cleaning and editing on the transcription has been made to make sure the transcription properly reflects on the interview.

For the overall research, a contextual or thematic analysis would be the primary method to understand further the context and the different aesthetics of MAMAMOO, their perspective on feminism, and how it impacts the fans' insights on the topic. As the MAMAMOO songs that were mentioned by the respondents in their interview, these were ultimately what the researcher has chosen to analyze: Yes I Am and WANNA BE MYSELF. Meanwhile, for the music videos, it would be Um Oh Ah Yeh, while both lyrics and music videos were chosen for HIP. Finally, reception analysis will also be used to see if the interview data validates or invalidates the researcher's content analysis of the four songs that were chosen. The reception analysis will also be used to combine the content analysis that was mentioned by the researcher above to be an additional factor for thorough validation or invalidation of the findings.

IV. RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The study presents information gathered from twelve (12) respondents conducted last March until April 2024. The analysis primarily focuses on the content of MAMAMOO's lyrics and music video, and if it aligns with the respondent's corresponding answers.

Content Analysis

HIP

Majority of the respondents bring up HIP as their number one song and music video when talking about MAMAMOO and feminism. Based on the lyrics, HIP tackles more on being yourself and not caring about others, with lyrics such as *"There's only one you in the world. But what's wrong? Why spit on your own face", "Beep, beep, people keep talking my fashion (Oh). I don't care, it's just an action.",* and *"Greasy hair I don't care. Stained shirt panty sticking out. Greasy hair If I do it, it's hip".* Most of the lyrics primarily focuses on self-love and preservation, while also tackling on making sure that listeners can focus on themselves and do what they love rather than letting society judge on who you are. Meanwhile for its music video, HIP uses the concept of alternate universes wherein members are not part of MAMAMOO but have their own career paths with the members, a company CEO (Moonbyul) and another is the President of South Korea (Hwasa). These characters represent how women can dominate in any career path they choose. Specifically, with Moonbyul and Hwasa's chosen career paths which is usually recognized as a male-dominated environment, especially for South Korea. On the other hand, one of the other

members' alternate career path or character is a rockstar (Solar) and their band members were drag queens. Presenting a platform for drag queens and creating an inclusive environment to let anyone and everyone be on their videos.

Yes I Am

With the second song majority of the respondents mentions Yes I Am as an empowering anthem for them. With lyrics such as *"Don't be self-conscious, you're Vogue. Hello, "Bonjour", "Ni hao", "Annyeong". Each country has its own charm", "If I were to describe myself, describe myself. I am very chic. If I were to describe myself, describe myself. Introduce myself", "I'm a confident woman (Ah-hey). So to speak, a sentimental woman (My baby). If you're confident, you can follow me (You can)", "Yes I am, my cheeks are chubby. My face is more round than V-line. I like it. It's my own, some special thing.", and "Instead of double eyelids. I like my mono eyelids. When I smile, my Indian dimples and wrinkles on my nose. I compliment them."* Similarly to HIP, Yes I Am's lyrics emphasizes on self-confidence and love, allowing everyone, especially their listeners to be themselves, and creating a safe environment and expressing who they are. At the same time, especially lyrics that tells that audience *"If you think you can do it, you can follow me"*, allowing the audience to jump on the song and let themselves be free on accepting their own flaws.

WANNA BE MYSELF

The third song that was mentioned by almost all of the respondents was WANNA BE MYSELF wherein similarly to Yes I Am and HIP uses self-love and empowerment as their theme. Lyrics like *"I'm beyond measure. I'm in my world. I wanna achieve as much as I want", "I WANNA BE MYSELF! There is no set standard in the world. Like this and like that. Don't compare", and "I respect myself. If I like it, that's it OK OK. I'm original."* Frequently mentioning everyone is unique to one another and advice the listeners that it is okay to be different, letting yourself be who you are and making sure that you can do anything if you respect yourself.

With the three songs mentioned above, all their lyrics follow the theme of self-empowerment, self-love, acceptance, and forging their own path.

Similarly, Hollows & Moseley's (2006, p. 4-5) chapter, indicates how media has been a way to present feminist's points such as women being treated fairly, and challenge on what the patriarchal norms have been set. With the HIP music video this corresponds with the summary of Liberal Feminism by Oxley (2011) wherein the main point is letting any rational human beings be themselves and having their own social and political rights while also maintaining justice for all genders.

Um Oh Ah Yeh

Lastly, rather than the lyrics, some respondents said that Um Oh Ah Yeh is an empowering music video for them. With the synopsis of the video being Yul (played by Moonbyul) chased around by Solar who is head over heels for the boy while Ricky (played by Hwasa) is a guy who chases Solar whilst she is chasing Yul.

Meanwhile, Koko (played by Wheein) is a boy who simply wants to eat his food. The main climax of the music video reveals Yul as a girl and Solar was chasing a woman all along, shocking her. The music video presents a quirky and unorthodox side of the K-pop industry where majority of the idols presents themselves as a serious or a cute group. Yet with MAMAMOO they focused on making their characters unique and letting themselves be in a humorous video where they can all laugh along that Solar was duped and shocked by Yul's actual gender. Although the lyrics of the song offers the same plot, the music video emphasized more on the unconventional side of MAMAMOO.

Finally, for the music video, Jones (2021, p. 2-4) states that girl groups are typically seen as tools and have been given shallow concepts due to their pretty faces and their young bodies. However, once age catches up to the idols, they are merely replaced by a newer and a younger female idol. Yet, MAMAMOO's Um Oh Ah Yeh contrasts Jones' study, creating a unique yet uncommon music video not typically seen in the industry. Allowing themselves to be made fun of, while providing characters that can be seen as a distinct take on the normal male and female love story in a music video.

Fans' perception of Feminism while being listening to MAMAMOO

When it comes to the perception of Feminism while being a fan of MAMAMOO, majority of the respondents saw the girl group as a way that has represented Feminism well. Some also provided instances wherein MAMAMOO has helped them see feminism in a different light due to their songs, while also taking into

account for others who have already known feminism and do not see MAMAMOO as a way to understand feminism more than they already know.

Aleah, a respondent, states how MAMAMOO has helped them understand feminism better:

For me, yes. MAMAMOO helped me see feminism, helped me see feminism that it is more than just women empowerment. It's also more on normalizing what society did as not stereotype for women. It's more on, ayan nga, so, normalizing kung ano yung hindi normally naikita ng mga tao na ginagawa ng mga babae. So, just live confident. And, wag magpa-affect ka sa mga discouragement na sinasabi ng mga ibang tao sa'yo.

Ren, the respondent who previously stated that they are not a feminist, said that:

I don't really consider myself [...] as a feminist. But, what I mean by that is [...] I don't want to be under isang label kasi ako is [...] I want to be impartial. So, parang gusto ko is lahat meron perspective. Pero hindi ko naman din dinidenay yung nagiging role ng Mamamoo. It comes with feminism. And I think that, Yes. Kasi yung may mga tao, sabi natin, minority, [...] hirap sila to relay. For example, kasi yung sabi nga ngayon [...], yung mga complicated or yung mga mabibigat na issues is hindi naman lahat kasi nakakaintindi. So, through their songs, through their works, through their art, is na mapakita or narirelay ng Mamamoo.

Jason, the male respondent or fan, expressed his perspective of Mamamoo's representation of Feminism by saying that:

I think it's just siyempre ako guy ako. I identify myself as one. And for me, it gives freedom, I guess. In terms of [...] Kasi if you remember yung definition ko ng feminism, it's parang they have to do whatever it takes to achieve yung equality nga, diba? And I think one of the most important things that the feminism movement has made success is yung reaching out sa mga, not necessarily the marginalized, pero yung mga lalaki din. For me, it's [...] Siyempre ang guys kasi may sarili din silang respective society struggles. And for me, it really helps. Very inspiring yung mamamoo in a sense na nakikita mo sila. They can be so much more. And kaya ako nakikita ko, I can be so much more.

However, Yasmin believes that MAMAMOO's representation for Feminism has not fully helped them understand Feminism more than they already know, stating:

Hindi talaga kasi nga ewan ko nung [...] ang thinking ko kasi walang truly feminist na performer in general na kailangan kumita para kasi siyang yun sa pride alam mo yung mga company na bigla nagbebenta ng rainbow theme pero ang question ko palagi saan napupunta yung kinikita niyo para kasing for me put your money where your mouth is pag di ko nakikita na ang advocacy ba niya anong ginagawa niya outside the performance or as an artist [...] Have helped me see, siguro hindi naman I see it differently but it's more of it

adds something to you kasi parang they're known to have overcome the traditional standard of what it means to be an idol group.

They further added that although they have already known Feminism way before MAMAMOO and that they do not fully see them in the title for a 'feminist' girl group but rather applauds MAMAMOO's attempt for empowering other people through various means such as Hwasa's stance on the Beauty Standards:

I'm not saying that MAMAMOO didn't comply in a way kasi they did they keep losing weight mga ganon that's [...] typical of the industry pero I like what Hwasa said before she debuted with a group sabi niya kung hindi nagfifit yung image niya or yung standard eh hindi siya pasok, gagawa siya ng sarili niya, Na-empower talaga ako ni Hwasa personally [...] kasi yung sinabi niya sa lahat di nga lang siya sa feminism eh basta it empowers you in a way na "if you don't fit the mold make a separate mold", parang ganoon ay siguro as a non-binary kung hindi ako nagfifit sa ganito eto yung gagawin ko ganoon.

Although Yasmin did applaud MAMAMOO's efforts, their line of work in the industry still questions if the idol group is truly genuine for their work. However, they commend issues that MAMAMOO has brought to light, especially for beauty standards.

Similarly, in a study by Jonas (2021, p. 7-8), the theme of beauty standards has been an issue in the K-pop industry, and MAMAMOO has been an unfortunate

example of companies using beauty standards as a way to navigate through members and pick out the best looking girl to market as a selling point for the public.

Finally, although Francine did not fully understand Feminism through MAMAMOO but rather they encouraged them to see example of issues such as Body Standards, Conservatism, gaining a more insight and perspective on what is happening in the world:

Not so much inspired, but... It's more of an example of the rejection that you had of the backlash on her clothes. [...] I think there was one where the netizens were bashing because her underwear was showing or something like that. She included that in the lyrics of the hip. But she did not change. In the next airport events [...] If they face a backlash like that, it will be a bit conservative. They will fix it so that there will be no backlash again. But Hwasa is Hwasa. She sometimes over-do it to show that in a way mocking. And I'm happy because [...] it didn't really change. My perspective is that [...] I know that I can be like that even before MAMAMOO. But then it's just more of an encouragement for me. What Hwasa is doing. Don't be afraid.

Definition of Feminism and Feminist Ideals

The research participants, while united in their love for MAMAMOO, hold diverse beliefs about feminism and gender equality. Most of them view feminism as a tool for equality, a means to create equal rights and opportunities for all genders. They also perceive a gap between chances and openings for all. However, one

respondent, named Ren, offers a different perspective, believing that gender should be about equity rather than equality, and thus, not identifying as a feminist. This diversity of beliefs within the fanbase is a proof of the inclusive nature of the MAMAMOO community.

I know feminism, but do I consider myself as a feminist? I don't think so. But it depends on how I view feminism. But for me, I'm not—I don't consider myself really as a feminist [...] Feminism is fighting for equal rights for women. It says it's equal, but for me, it's more than equal. And equity is much more needed than equality. So, that's why I don't consider myself as a feminist.

Julia also states that Feminism should be a movement and a topic that should be outspoken freely. Thus, they do not label themselves as Feminists either because they prefer to support the topic clandestinely.

Hindi po yung, parang outspoken, talaga. I would prefer to donate parang, instead na makapaglaban. Ganun.

Meanwhile, others, such as Hanna, based their experience on their definition of feminism while considering themselves feminists.

Pero nung nag-move ako – dahil I would say my third job...It's for a newspaper. Marami kaming resources noon. It was owned by [...] isang education [...] sa US [...] My social consciousness [...] nag-open up at that time [...] Katulad ng sinabi ni Ren kanina, it's about equality [...] But equality

in a sense na [...] better treatment for women [...] without jeopardizing whatever it is that's the right of [...] anybody else [...] Feminism is also just about choosing for yourself.

Similarly, Aleah shares the same sentiments but was previously put off by feminism due to some negative attributes that she spoke briefly of.

It's more on women empowerment. Especially for me, because I work in a male-dominated field. I want to show that whatever they do, the hard work, the good work, I can do it too. Since pinag-aralan ko din 'yun, pinag-aralan din nila 'yun. I can also do what they do [...] There are some I hear that [...] Feminist are just entitled people [...] But I also researched further that it's not like that, what feminists want to reach.

Influences and Reception to Fandom

Within the fandom or the *MooMoo* community, MAMAMOO continues to be their role model wherein majority of the respondents cites MAMAMOO as their main influence in understanding feminism and applying it especially to themselves in their daily lives and even giving back to the community.

Julia, who is a part of the MAMAMOO PH fanbase, has stated that they have used MAMAMOO as a platform or topic of podcast that discusses various topics such as Feminism:

Ganon kasi kami yung segment na Chis-Moo-sa, which is yung parang podcast namin. So, the whole, nagtutok lang kami of a kind of topic, basta related sa mamamoo. parang ano rin po, personal rin po, ganon. Parang, halimbawa, may release ang mamamoo, tapos meron kaming side topics na related sa, yun nga, sa feminism, etc.

When talking about MAMAMOO's impact on their perspective on feminism Aleah discloses that:

Because sila din naman ang naging reasons why I got positive [...] towards feminism. It is more on women empowerment and giving equal rights to women.

While MAMAMOO has also provided the needed boost for some of the fans' self-confidence with a respondent named Merrick saying:

And then I guess [...] na-influence din ako ng mamamoo. Kasi before I wasn't really wearing parang mga crop tops and all. So parang slowly nung na-discover ko yung mamamoo and then parang na-influence din ako. Based from [...] paano sila manamit. Like some clothes na I thought na hindi [...] parang I guess hindi okay or hindi norm or parang maja-jujudge ko. Pero over time parang na-influence ako na to wear it. Parang okay wala akong paki.

Similar to Merrick, Anna also gained self-confidence after listening to MAMAMOO:

As well as yung confidence ko to interact with people [...] with a different gender. Kasi ako talaga, from the very start, [...] one of the boys. Pero introverted ako [...] Parang sa dun sa flow nila sa stage na yun, kasi yung camera nila dun iba't iba rin, parang pag di ka kasi fan at tinignan mo siya parang ang gulo [...] so bilang fan nasa iyo na yun kung pano interpret yung stage nila. So ayun nainspire ako to be more confident as a person na introvert dati. Medyo nag open na ako to step up to lead something, ako na nagiinitiate ng gawa, [...] kesa maghihintay ng gawa.

For the songs and music videos that were analyzed above, almost all of the respondents have a similar thinking where they believe that MAMAMOO uses their platform to empower their fans and allow other genders to be mentioned and presented on who they are. For HIP's music video this gave some respondents a form of discussion and questioning with a respondent, named Aster, stating:

Ah, kasi sa isang music video [...] HIP, si Hwasa, single mother siya dun. Tapos, ine-enjoy niya lang yun. [...] It should not also be vilified din. Diba, hindi dapat i-discriminate yung mga ganong situation. Either she chose to be a single mother or not. Dapat ang gawin na lang ng mga tao is to support, diba?"

Another respondent, namely Jason, also continues that

Alam mo yun, yung makita mo si Hwasa na nakasuot ng pang President. And then, makapaisip ka. "Ha? Parang wala namang masyado." Yun pa lang eh. It

raises the discussion na gaano ba karaming presidente na babae. And gaano karaming babae yung presidente yung actually advocating for, you know, are actual feminists.

For WANNA BE MYSELF, Aleah, specifically picked this song as their main inspiration due to the song's theme for one's uniqueness, explicitly saying that:

For me, [...] yung lyrics sa song ng Wanna be Myself, [...] hindi ko lang sure kung ito yung sakto, pero may lyrics doon na if translated [...] ang ibig sabihin is, wala akong pake kahit anong sabihin mo. [...] Kung hindi mo naman alam sa nasabi mo, huwag ka nalang mangelam. Parang gano'n. [...] Basta ito, gagawin ko to. Ito gusto kong gawin. Wag mo kong pakilaman, ganun.

For Um Oh Ah Yeh's music video, the wacky and uncommon plot presents a form of representation for some respondents, wherein Julia has said that:

Tapos, yung Um Oh Ah Yeh, which is, parang may ang dami lang inirepresent na mga people. Alam mo yun, not necessarily glamorous. [...] Kasi, di ba, maraming-maraming music videos [...], puro pacute lang yung ginagawa ng mga groups. Pero, sila, they're open to throwing different types of people, [...] kahit yung supposedly embarrassing type ng mga tao.

Hanna also states a similar perspective saying that:

So, doon [...] pinakita nila na, [...], hindi sila takot na, yung aesthetics nila is sabihin na, ano ba yan, ganyan, na yung maridicule kasi, think, yun nga, parang, yung personal styles nila is very [...] very appropriate for all genders.

However, Yes I Am's lyrics cause a barrier to those who do not fully identify as a woman, making a limiting space for others who want to be uplifted by Yes I Am. Yasmin, a respondent, continues this by saying:

Because the lyrics are very limiting, because confident woman, because not all who identify as a woman is born a woman right? or you, how do you feel that day. Since I identify as non-binary, I have feelings that this day [...] I don't really feel like [...] on the spectrum I'm not the woman-woman, I'm not the woman-woman or man-man, I'm not the man so today I'm going to sing I feel like a confident woman.

Another respondent, Francine, states that MAMAMOO's lyrics depends on the perspective saying:

So, in terms of the songs, hindi masyado, unless you take it in a general way, na empower yourself. [...] Pero yung Yes I Am, it's more on really the females. Na parang, yes, I am, I'm a female, kaya ganito. Diba, yun yung song. That's what it's all about. [...] But if you, if you listen to it, it's very, very important. And if you look into it [...] it depends on, I think for me, it depends on the person. So, if they're gonna take it in a positive, encouragement way.

Overall, in a study by Li (2022) other girl groups like (G)-IDLE presents a validation by fans towards their idols' desire to break barriers and deviate from social norms from their Tomboy music video. Likewise, based on the findings above, MAMAMOO's advocacy and main theme focuses on self-love and deviating from the social norm, allowing everyone to be themselves. Although not all fans agree with one another, all of them praise MAMAMOO's efforts to empower.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section summarizes the data gathered and the study's objectives. It also tackles the conclusions drawn and the recommendations for the analysis based on the results.

Summary of Findings and Conclusion

The study aimed to determine MAMAMOO as a primary representative of feminism for audiences. It investigated the connection of MAMAMOO with feminism by interviewing twelve (12) respondents, all aged 20-30, who are at least one year fans of MAMAMOO that supports them through merchandise, streaming of their music and music videos, and going to important events like their concerts. Simultaneously, the study also used content analysis to analyze further the connection of MAMAMOO songs and music video aesthetics with feminism and linked the content analysis with thematic analysis that occurred from interviewing the respondents, and finally ends with reception analysis to further explore if there is a disparity or similarity with the respondent's answers from the four songs that were assessed.

Moreover, most of the respondents believed that MAMAMOO is a well-known purveyor of feminism, providing instances such as their lyrics for HIP, WANNA BE MYSELF, and Yes I Am, as the primary source of empowerment that everyone is created equal regardless of their gender. The main criticism of a respondent mentions that MAMAMOO focuses more on women and people identifying as

women rather than other genders that identify as a different type of gender. Regardless, all the respondents mention the representation they have given to other genders, such as drag queens, through their music video and performances, citing the importance of giving them a platform to be themselves and showcase the drag queens' unique individuality. Additionally, MAMAMOO focuses on speaking out against Body Standards, wherein several of the respondents felt they were more confident due to the members showing their unique style, creating a safe space for fans and audiences to be themselves

Furthermore, the researcher's content analysis of the four songs that were mentioned consistently by the respondents (HIP's lyrics and music video, WANNA BE MYSELF's lyrics, Yes I Am's lyrics, and Um Oh Ah Yeh's music video) presents an ongoing theme of self-empowerment, and letting yourself be different than what is fitted into the norm. These themes represent a liberal feminism style in their works creating a platform for equality for different genders while maintaining self-confidence for their right to be themselves.

Using Reception Analysis, we can see that MAMAMOO's influence over fans varies due to their personal experience. With Yasmin, they believe that MAMAMOO is not the overall perfect girl group for Feminism due to believing that no idols nor artists are truly feminist without the income they are gaining. At the same time due to their gender preference, they feel limited by MAMAMOO's Yes I Am, believing it only empowers women rather than every gender. Although, they do commend MAMAMOO's efforts, creating a negational interpretation of MAMAMOO. For others such as Hanna and Aleah, they believe that MAMAMOO's lyrics and music videos

are impactful, using their knowledge based on their experiences as a Feminist as a way to see MAMAMOO in an empowering way, creating a preferred reading that almost every respondents agree with as their message comes across towards them.

Therefore, MAMAMOO can be a purveyor of feminism crafting music and video aesthetics with the ongoing theme of self-love and self-empowerment, MAMAMOO focuses more on uplifting oneself. However, they have not fully touched on other critical issues that are seen when tackling liberal feminism, such as reproductive rights, sexual harassment, domestic violence, and situations that occur in K-pop, such as cyberbullying against women and the desire to change girl groups that are deemed too old for the public. At the same time, the study also presents the potential of K-pop lyrics and music videos as a form of advocacy, representing those who are essentially marginalized by the public. Meanwhile, K-pop girl groups can also use their platform to break some barriers fundamentally and fight for what they believe in to improve the industry that they are part of.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the researcher proposes the following recommendations:

1. Firstly, feminist advocates and multimedia scholars further adopt an open perspective toward K-pop concepts and aesthetics to research the underlying meanings of their songs and videos. Their songs and music videos can be a platform to encourage everyone to empower one another, creating a safe environment and inclusivity to be themselves and following

the values of other advocacies that they want to let their supporters and listeners know more about.

2. Secondly, further research is needed, not only for MAMAMOO but also for other girl groups and female idols. Analysis of feminism should not be limited to only MAMAMOO but also other groups and idols that are outspoken similarly to MAMAMOO. Furthermore, additional data should be gathered since MAMAMOO's concepts and aesthetics are ever-changing due to the girl group's desire to try and experiment with different themes they aspire to do.

3. Thirdly, MAMAMOO also tackles other topics, such as mental health, issues of the music industry, and fame, which future researchers should further analyze to see how these topics influence the girl group's fans.

4. Fourthly, further research is also needed to understand how the fandom community can be influenced by the artists they idolize. Some songs and music videos can be a form of persuasion and message to fans for the artist's advocacy.

5. Finally, aside from adopting an open perspective on K-pop concepts and aesthetics, multimedia scholars should also consider how fandoms as a community can be influenced by the media they consume through established idols and artists and how this can be a way to analyze more of the audiences' reaction and input on the artist's perspective.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Journal Articles and Books

Ebert, T. L. (1991). The “Difference” of Postmodern Feminism. *College English*, 53(8), 886. doi:10.2307/377692

Inwood, H. (2012). Popular Culture of East and Southeast Asia, 1900-present. In P. J. Seybolt (Ed.), *Cultural Sociology of the Middle East, Asia, and Africa* (Vol. 3, pp. 345-347). Sage Publications Ltd. <https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/popular-culture-of-east-and-south-east-asia-1900-present>

Hollows, J. & Moseley, R. (2006) *Feminism in Popular Culture*. Berg Publishers.

Jonas, L. (2021). Crafted for the Male Gaze: Discrimination in the K-Pop Industry. *Journal of International Women’s Studies*, 22(7), 3-18. <https://vc.bridgew.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2492&context=jiws>

Koudelová, I. (2022). *Ballroom Community, LGBTQ+ and History*. Masarykova Univerzita. https://is.muni.cz/th/j8y1h/Ballroom_Community__LGBTQ__and_History.pdf

Lin, X. & Rudolf, R. (2017). Does K-Pop Reinforce Gender Inequalities? Empirical Evidence from a New Data Set. *Asian Women*, 22(4), 27-54. <http://www.e-asianwomen.org/xml/12430/12430.pdf>

Primer, P. (2023). *How Gender Shapes Music: A Comparison Within K-Pop*. Fordham Research Commons. Retrieved from: https://research.library.fordham.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1106&context=international_senior

Oxley, J.C. (2011). Liberal Feminism. Just the Arguments: 100 of the Most Important Arguments in Western Philosophy. In Bruce, M. & Barbone, S. (Eds.), Blackwell Publishing Ltd., p. 258

Sanchez, M. (2023). The Sexualization of Asian Women In the Korean Pop Industry. UCR Honors Capstones 2022-2023. Retrieved from: <https://escholarship.org/content/qt7wf5s4jd/qt7wf5s4jd.pdf>

Septiani, S. & Prhatini, E. (2022). K-Pop Idol Promoting Feminism in South Korea: A Case from Red Velvet. Proceedings of the 7th North American International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management. Retrieved from: <https://ieomsociety.org/proceedings/2022orlando/431.pdf>

V, A. (2018). Sociology of Genders. In Wagh, A.C. (Ed). INFLIBNET Centre. <https://ebooks.inflibnet.ac.in/socp10/chapter/liberal-feminism-radical-feminism/>

Wallin, D. (2001). POSTMODERN FEMINISM AND EDUCATIONAL POLICY DEVELOPMENT. McGill Journal of Education / Revue Des Sciences De l'éducation De McGill, 36(001). Retrieved from <https://mje.mcgill.ca/article/view/8552>

Wood, J.T. (2012). "Feminist Standpoint Theory." SAGE Reference Online. Encyclopedia of Communication Theory. Ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, 2009. 397- 99.

News Articles and Websites

Amysbubble85. (2017). MAMAMOO – Yes I am (나로 말할 것 같으면). Color Coded Lyrics.

https://colorcodedlyrics.com/2017/06/22/mamamoo-yes-nalo-malhal-geos-gateumyeon/#google_vignette

Chen, A. & Haynes, S. (2018). How #MeToo Is Taking on a Life of Its Own in Asia. TIME. <https://time.com/longform/me-too-asia-china-south-korea/>

Chung, C. (2020). How female K-pop idols suffer gender inequality and are held to different standards: 'It's totally unfair'. South China Morning Post. https://www.scmp.com/lifestyle/entertainment/article/3051389/how-female-k-pop-idols-suffer-gender-inequality-and-are?campaign=3051389&module=perpetual_scroll_0&pgtype=article&fbclid=IwAR2GqxxwIxPOsiHCx_cvNwAliKqOCRZvhSVnAhmaqPKAO_r3rSgy4m9thE

Eastern Kentucky University (n.d.) Feminism: What is it? Retrieved from: <https://www.eku.edu/wgs/feminism-what-is-it/>

Herman, T. (2018). Female K-Pop Stars Face Criticism for Seemingly Feminist Behavior. Billboard. <https://www.billboard.com/music/music-news/female-k-pop-stars-face-criticism-feminist-behavior-8257777/>

Khan, A. (2021). K-Pop Needs Its #MeToo Moment [Opinion]. Trinitonian. <https://trinitonian.com/2021/10/14/k-pop-needs-its-metoo-moment/>

Lee S. (2024). Solar said, "Moon Byul, I listened to But I and said, 'I want to have it.' Take out my earphones." [Interview ②] (lunaestrellad0s, Trans). <https://m.entertain.naver.com/article/108/0003231970> [Translation: <https://twitter.com/lunaestrellad0s/status/1785122130373599510>].

Lucas, S. (2021). Netizens Can't Stop Praising MAMAMOO's Moonbyul For The Inclusive Lyrics In Her New Track "Shutdown". Koreaboo. <https://www.koreaboo.com/news/mamamoo-moonbyul-praise-inclusiveness-seori-shutdown/>

Moon, K.H.S. (2022). South Korea's misogyny problem. East Asia Forum.
<https://eastasiaforum.org/2022/12/09/south-koreas-misogyny-problem/>

Park, S.N. (2021). Why So Many Young Men in South Korea Hate Feminism.
Foreign Policy.
<https://foreignpolicy.com/2021/06/23/young-south-korean-men-hate-liberals-feminists/>

Silva. (2019). MAMAMOO – HIP. Color Coded Lyrics.
<https://colorcodedlyrics.com/2019/11/14/mamamoo-hip/>

Seraphina. (2020). MAMAMOO (마마무) – WANNA BE MYSELF. Color Coded
Lyrics.
<https://colorcodedlyrics.com/2020/09/12/mamamoo-mamamu-wanna-be-myself/>

So-Yeon, Y. (2022). [CRITICALLY SPEAKING: K-POP] Girl groups live in fear of
anti-feminist backlash. Korea JoongAng Daily.
<https://koreajoongangdaily.joins.com/2022/08/01/business/industry/Korea-Kpop-critic/20220801163240111.html>

Sun-hwa, D. (2022). INTERVIEW '6equence': MAMAMOO's Moonbyul unfolds 6
different stories in new album. TheKoreanTimes.
https://www.koreatimes.co.kr/www/art/2023/12/398_322490.html

Sun-hwa, D. (2023). MAMAMOO's Hwasa investigated for obscene performance.
TheKoreanTimes. https://www.koreatimes.co.kr/www/art/2023/12/398_358935.html

Villadelgado, R. (2023). Hallyu – The Korean Wave. Los Angeles Times High School
Insider. <https://highschool.latimes.com/hs-insider/hallyu-the-korean-wave/>

Yckim124 (2018). BTS' RM and Yoo Jae Suk revealed to have read the feminist
novel involved in Irene's controversy. Allkpop.

<https://www.allkpop.com/article/2018/03/bts-rm-and-yoo-jae-suk-also-revealed-to-have-read-the-feminist-novel-involved-in-irenes-controversy>

Yeung, K. (2017). Review: MAMAMOO's Yes I Am. BigTimeWrites. <https://bigtimewrites.wordpress.com/2017/08/30/review-mamamoos-yes-i-am/>

Videos

Hwa Sa. (2019). Experience on Beauty Standards [Speech]. 2019 MAMAMOO CONCERT 4season F/W. Jangchung Arena, Seoul, South Korea. Retrieved from: <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/ptRI9XSoesA>

MAMAMOO. (2019). [WHEE IN] 'soar' Making Prologue #2 [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3MZVnLZsb-A>

Solarsido. (2020). The most painful traditional practice for women ... it's the worst [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/PgkzCktomus>

Stone Cube Entertainment. (2015). 마마무 (MAMAMOO) - 음오아예 (Um Oh Ah Yeh) MV [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pFuJAIMQjHk>

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Translated MAMAMOO Lyrics

HIP

All I wanna be is cool	However I want pick it, kick it
However I want, pick it, kick it	Head, shoulders, knees, it's all HIP
Head, shoulders, knees, it's all HIP	
Do it do it like me do it	Bbi-bbi-bbi it becomes a controversy,
Copy me, kick it	my fashion
Clapping clapping everyone together	I don't care much, just action
HIP	Keep on click me click me, like you're
	possessed, zoom
I love you whatever you say	Close up close up close up
Respect you whatever you do	
It's always warm, that attention is tingly	It's HIP HIP HIP
Again glancing glancing glancing	Head, shoulders, knees, HIP
	HIP HIP HIP HIP HIP It's HIP HIP HIP
Now, everything is easy, veteran	Head, shoulders, knees, HIP
I cut up and eat success like Michelin	HIP HIP HIP It's HIP HIP
I walked faster than anyone else,	
off-season	(Attention) Wherever you go
It's been a while since I forgot, step	(Reflection) You can shine
back	There's only one you in the world
	But what are you doing, spitting on
All I wanna be is cool	your own face

Thank you to everyone who provokes
me

Losers who stopped there, right back
at you

Thanks to you, my mentality is strong
I'm gonna go make the next album

All you wanna be is trendy

Trolling gimmick hit

People that are like that together HIP

Bbi-bbi-bbi it becomes a controversy,
my fashion

I don't care much, just action

Keep on click me click me, like you're
possessed, zoom

Close up close up close up

It's HIP HIP HIP

Head, shoulders, knees, HIP

HIP HIP HIP HIP HIP It's HIP HIP HIP

Head, shoulders, knees, HIP

HIP HIP HIP It's HIP HIP

T-shirt with snot on it, mouth sticking
out

Greasy hair, it doesn't matter to me

T-shirt with snot on it, mouth sticking
out

Greasy hair, it's HIP if I do it

T-shirt with snot on it, panties sticking
out

Greasy hair, it doesn't matter to me

T-shirt with snot on it, panties sticking
out

Greasy hair, it's HIP if I do it

Bbi-bbi-bbi it becomes a controversy,
my fashion

I don't care much, just action

Keep on click me click me, like you're
possessed, zoom

Close up close up close up

It's HIP HIP HIP

Head, shoulders, knees, HIP

HIP HIP HIP HIP HIP It's HIP HIP HIP

Head, shoulders, knees, HIP

HIP HIP HIP It's HIP HIP

Yes I Am

If I were to describe myself
I'm a confident woman
To put it in words, a woman of feeling
(My baby)
If you think you can do it, you can
follow me (You can)
Follow me, follow me
Follow me-e ay ay
Makeup is light, 'cause I'm lazy
I won't show skin, no need to do that

It's strange, I'm a bit unique
I don't like ordinary things
I thank my parents for this side of me

Me me 4 with Sun
Stop thinking, my mind is high class
Don't be shy, you're Vogue
Hello bonjour nǐhǎo annyeong
Just like how each country has its own
charm
If I were to describe myself
Whenever I wear sleeveless shirts

It becomes summer, I love you
(Introduce my self)

If I were to describe myself
I'm a confident woman
To put it in words, a woman of feeling
(My baby)
If you think you can do it, you can
follow me (You can)
Follow me, follow me
Follow me-e ay ay

Yes I am, [WHEE/HWA] if I were to
describe myself
Yes I am, I'm very cheeky

I like comfort 'cause that's just me
I won't sugarcoat, I can't hide it
I'm cheeky, I don't care
You don't know me
I just do what I wanna do

My name is Moonstar

This is just my taste
So don't be too sensitive
My complex is nothing
Slacks, shirts, loafers
With a classic style
I express myself, my baby
You still try to take me down
Take off the blind
Drive, get in my car

Now, now, if I were to describe myself
I'm a confident woman
To put it in words, a woman of feeling
(My baby)
If you think you can do it, you can
follow me (You can)
Follow me, follow me
Follow me-e ay ay

Yes I am, [WHEE/HWA] if I were to
describe myself
Yes I am follow me-e ay ay
Yes I am, [WHEE/HWA] if I were to
describe myself
Yes I am, my cheeks are chubby

My face is more round than V-line
I like it
It's my own, some special thing
Instead of double eyelids
I like my mono eyelids
When I smile, my Indian dimples
and wrinkles on my nose
I compliment them

[SOL/HWA] If I were to describe myself
[SOL/HWA] If I were to describe myself
I'm very chic
If I were to describe myself
If I were to describe myself
Her, her, her (Introduce my self)
If I were to describe myself
I'm a confident woman
To put it in words, a woman of feeling
If you think you can do it, you can
follow me (You can)
Follow me, follow me
Follow me-e ay ay

Yes I am, [WHEE/HWA] if I were to
describe myself

Yes I am follow me follow follow follow
me

Yes I am, if I were to describe myself

Yes I am

I'm very cheek

WANNA BE MYSELF

They say they can't figure out at all

So that they can't figure it out

In my own world

I will achieve as much as I want

My role that I've dreamed of

Uncommon come on

Sometimes I do change

Whatever they say, I don't care

If you don't know then shh

Please don't jump to conclusions

There's no difference between you and

me

So what if I ruin it

As I want, do it again

Laugh in front, cry behind

Well, what to do?

Even if I express it, they will just see it

as they wish

Who am I?

Who who am I?

Every moment

WANNA BE MYSELF

There is no fixed standard in this world

Like this, like that

Don't compare

Not different, you and I are not
different

You and I

I respect myself, if I like it

Then that's all that matters

OK OK

I'm original

Not different, you and I are not
different

Every day I

WANNA BE MYSELF

The me that you're seeing, is that my
real self?

Yesterday and today

Just like how day and night are
different

Change, new feeling

I like it, do everything I want

Unending challenge

It does feel quite foreign sometimes

Regardless, I'm still the same

Oh, look at me

I have many colors

But nothing's different

About me

Every day

I WANNA BE MYSELF

There is no fixed standard in this world

Like this, like that

Don't compare

Not different, you and I are not
different

You and I

I respect myself

If I like it, then that's all that matters

OK OK

I'm original

Not different, you and I are not
different

Every day I

WANNA BE MYSELF

Wherever you are, living is the same

Doing this, doing that, doing whatever

I'm me, yes, me

When I'm me, when I'm just me

Wanna be right there

There is no fixed standard in this world

Oh, don't try to fit me

Not different, you and I are not
different

You and I

I respect myself (self)

If I like it, then that's all that matters

OK OK (that's all that matters)

I'm original (I'm original)

Not different, you and I are not
different

Every day I

WANNA BE MYSELF

Appendix C: Consent Form

#MooToo: An Exploratory Study on MAMAMOO as Purveyor of Feminism Ideals

Good day!

I am Airiel Licca Depante, a 4th Year Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies Student from the University of the Philippines Open University. As part of my course requirements in MMS 200 Special Project, I am investigating the influence of MAMAMOO's lyrics and music video aesthetics on the fans' impression, appreciation, and/or application of feminist beliefs.

There are no right or wrong answers regarding this questionnaire, and you may withdraw anytime.

Before proceeding to the interview proper, it is essential to read the following.

- This interview is purely voluntary.
- You can skip or leave out an answer to any of the questions if you feel uncomfortable to answer.
- Your answers are purely for research purposes and will remain confidential.
- You are allowing the researcher to record (through video and audio means) your answers for data analysis purposes.
- You are allowing the researcher to save and record your answers (if the interviewee prefers a text-based interview) for analysis purposes.
- You are allowing the researcher to screenshot and/or take a photograph for documentation purposes.

- You can halt the interview process and choose to leave at any time.
- After the interview, you can withdraw your answers if you do not want to participate in the research.

If you have any questions or concerns regarding the interview, please contact me at **aldepante@up.edu.ph** or **0926 782 3862**.

Attached is my Certificate of Completion for the [Course on Research: Ethics based on the Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans \(TCPS 2: CORE 2022\)](#).

Thank you so much for your participation.

"Fightiing!" - Solar

Appendix D: Certificate from the Panel on Research Ethics

**PANEL ON
RESEARCH ETHICS**
Navigating the ethics of human research

TCPS 2: CORE 2022

Certificate of Completion

This document certifies that

Airiel Depante

*successfully completed the Course on Research Ethics based on
the Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research
Involving Humans (TCPS 2: CORE 2022)*

Certificate # 0001249526

30 January, 2024

Appendix E: Interview Questionnaire

I. Demographics

1. Name (Optional)
2. Age
3. To which gender identity do you identify the most?
4. Highest level of educational attainment
5. Work Status
6. How long have you been a fan of MAMAMOO (in years)?

II. Interview Questions

7. Do you consider yourself a Feminist? Were you familiar with Feminism before listening to or following MAMAMOO? For you, what is Feminism? Which five (5) MAMAMOO songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?
8. What activities do you do to support MAMAMOO? (E.g., Merchandise, Streaming, etc.)
9. Do you believe that MAMAMOO in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? Can you cite cases and examples?
10. Do you believe that all spectrums of genders can relate to MAMAMOO? How so?
11. How do MAMAMOO's lyrics on various songs empower different genders? Such as, "If I were to describe myself, I'm a confident woman." (Yes I Am, 2018)
12. What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics MAMAMOO has presented are most important when empowering other genders?

13. What issues of feminism have been highlighted by MAMAMOO have helped you see feminism in a different light?
14. Do you see that, over time, MAMAMOO's song lyrics and music video aesthetics have significantly helped you understand feminism better?
15. What specific lyric or aesthetic (whether it be from a music video or their stage performance) of MAMAMOO inspire you and why?

Appendix F: Interview Transcriptions

Interview A: Yasmin Aguila

Researcher: So, good afternoon. Good afternoon. For formalities, I am Airiel Lcca Depante, a fourth-year BAMS student, Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies in UPOU or University of the Philippines Open University. As part of my course requirements in MMS 200 Special Project, I am investigating the influence of MAMAMOO's lyrics and music video aesthetics on the fans' impression, appreciation, or application of feminist beliefs. So, for formalities, there are no right or wrong answers regarding this questionnaire, and you may withdraw any time. So, of course, this is being recorded for research purposes only and will remain confidential between me and the research adviser. Can you state your name and your age?

Yasmin: I am Yasmin Aguila, 28 years old.

Researcher: Okay, so to which gender identity do you identify the most?

Yasmin: Non-binary.

Researcher: Non-binary. Highest level of educational attainment?

Yasmin: Undergraduate college.

Researcher: Okay, so what is your work status? Are you a full-time? Are you a...
Part-time?

Yasmin: Technical writer, full-time. Full-time.

Researcher: So, how long have you been a MAMAMOO fan? In years?

Yasmin: 2020, so... Four. Four years.

Researcher: Okay. So, do you consider yourself a feminist?

Yasmin: I think so.

Researcher: Were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following
MAMAMOO?

Yasmin: Yes.

Researcher: For you, what is feminism?

Yasmin: Hmm...Because humanism failed. That's why we need feminism. Like,
women are considered minorities. I mean, historically, in some places. Because they
don't really have equal say or like equal status in... In social life or culturally. That's
why I think feminism is for women having opportunity or having an equal voice in

maybe politically, socially, or culturally. So, that's feminism for me. Having an equal say or equal view. That's it. Yeah.

Researcher: In your opinion, which five MAMAMOO songs are about empowerment?

Yasmin: Hmm... For me, empowerment is... It's an ad, eh. Wanna be myself. Yes, I am. Um...

Researcher: You can look at Spotify if you want. For specific...

Yasmin: Do you need MAMAMOO or can I include...

Researcher: MAMAMOO.

Yasmin: Okay. Okay. Mm...Wanna be myself... Piano Man. I consider Piano Man... Okay. ...a feminist song. Hip is a feminist song.

Researcher: Okay. Piano Man. I'm gonna look at that.

Yasmin: No, because... Okay. Um... Who else? What else... For me... Mm-hmm. One last. Ano nga yun? Is that AHH OOP?

Researcher: Oh, AHH OOP? Okay.

Yasmin: Yeah. The rap song by Byul that says...Men are all the same.

Researcher: Let's search it.

Yasmin: Researcher is searching.

Researcher: Ma'am might be listening...Listen to me, boys. Gotta respect a girl.

Yasmin: Oh, right? Because that's Esna. Esna is a western girl. Even Piano Man was with Esna, she wrote it.

Researcher: Ah, okay. Okay. And come to me like a man is frustrating. Please tell... Stop telling obvious things.

Yasmin: That's it. It's AHH OOP. That's five, right?

Researcher: Yeah, five. So, AHH OOP. Hip. Wanna be myself. Yes, I am. Piano Man. Okay. So... What activities do you do to support MAMAMOO? Like, example...Merchandise? Buying? Streaming? What?

Yasmin: I started there. I bought an album. Then, I went to their concert. I listened to their songs, their releases.

Researcher: Do you believe that MAMAMOO in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders?

Yasmin: Various genders? Possibly.

Researcher: Can you cite cases and examples for possibly?

Yasmin: For example, non-binary. What drew me in is Moonbyul because she's not a typical rapper. she's not a typical female rapper with a brighter tone. She has a deep, cool voice. In terms of style, she also said that just because I'm female, she doesn't want the aesthetic to be socially considered as feminine. Androgynous siya. So that's what I want specifically, what drew me in. Because I became a fan during the eclipse era. I think, yes, because Solar is in charge of... Actually, no. They're two. They're the same three. Wheein, they're very feminine. Wheein Solar and Hwasa. So, there.

Researcher: So, do you believe all spectrums of gender can relate to MAMAMOO?

Yasmin: Music. In terms of music. This is just my perspective. I feel like they're very, for gay people. I mean, because, how will I justify this? Because those... Oh my God. For example, because they're vocal-centric. You noticed that there are cult-following here in our country. For example, Regine Velasquez. Because, or let's say, Mariah Carey. They have a lot of fans that are gay men. Or gay non-binary. Like that. Just gay in general or women. Because, maybe, drawn to talent. Like that. So, what's the question?

Researcher: Do you believe that all spectrums of gender can relate to mamamoo?

Yasmin: Ayun. I don't know. I feel like it's this... When you're alone, When you're alone, What do you want to belt out? Or what do you want to do in the shower? I feel like they have that quality. Maybe, I'm not really exposed with straight men. Because, I grew up in a family that mostly has women. I haven't encountered a man in my life yet. I guess. That sings, and suddenly belt out.

Like Mariah, or Whitney. That's like mamamoo's style. Beyonce-type of music, or... Whitney with Solar because.

Researcher: So, would you say something like fifty-fifty?

Yasmin: Yeah. She's not... I don't think... Mamamoo is for all genders. I think it's more for women. Eight to forty (in terms of age jokingly), that's just my perspective I don't have research or anything,

Researcher: It's fine there's no right or wrong answers don't worry. So how do Mamamoo's lyrics on various songs empower different genders such as yes I am if I were to describe myself I'm a confident woman again and again

Yasmin: Because the lyrics are very limiting, because confident woman, because not all who identify as a woman is born a woman right? or you, how do you feel that day. Since I identify as non-binary, I have feelings that this day I feel like I don't really feel like like on the spectrum I'm not the woman-woman, I'm not the woman-woman or man-man, I'm not the man so today I'm going to sing I feel like a confident woman

Researcher: So how do you say their lyrics empower you in any gender that you feel like?

Yasmin: Yeah I feel like in a way yes and maybe the highlight for me on yes I am is the chubby cheeks why does she want to change it? she doesn't want to change it he wants to change the parts of his body and I feel like that's what resonated with me in that song it's not necessarily a yes I am it could be any song, so like any song you get empowered from their lyrics like that, that specific song ah okay so what concept music videos and stage aesthetics mamamoo has presented are most important when empowering other gender ah I didn't think of that that specifically it has to feel empowering the vibe of their performance but what comes to mind is their performance of mama 2018 the one where they're red is that right?

Research: yeah, yeah

Yasmin: Yeah, I think that was their first time to be nominated as a vocal group, and then you know how to say it they could hype a crowd they know how to hype the crowd, and then you could visibly see the women idols cheering for them like wow that's amazing so their appeal in a way women or I feel like the closeted gay men in the audience. I think they're really they're feeling it mamamoo has that vibe they're really passionate and performing they're known not to lip sync so that's where the messiness of the performance that they're presenting on the stage it's transferring to the audience so I think in a sense if that's my definition of empowerment because it's transferring the energy

Researcher: Maybe music video?

Yasmin: music video?

Researcher: music video or their concept in an album something like that

Yasmin: more feminine empowering...

Researcher: it's okay if you don't have one in mind, I'm not pressuring you

Yasmin: Egotistic? because I don't tie it to specific style or aesthetic of music video. I just feel empowered looking at it like that like "yes girl!" like that's the feel

Researcher: okay so what issues of feminism have been highlighted by mamamoo have helped you see feminism in a different light what issues of feminism

Yasmin: Have helped me see, siguro hindi naman I see it differently but it's more of it adds something to you kasi parang they're known to have overcome the traditional standard of what it means to be an idol group. So, parang I'm not saying na sila lang yung gumawa nun kasi may mga group naman na vocal centric na hindi ganong na hindi um nag yung minold nila yung self nila to comply kung ano yung standards. I'm not saying that mamamoo didn't comply in a way kasi they did they keep losing weight mga ganon that's so typical of the industry pero I like what Hwasa said before she debuted with a group sabi niya kung hindi nagfifit yung image niya or yung standard eh hindi siya pasok, gagawa siya ng sarili niya standard. I really like that

kasi parang kasing um the way she challenges the industry as a woman kasi feel ko hindi nga lang yun as a woman eh she empowers that is empowering not just for women in kpop pero men in kpop kasi meron din equal pressure for men meron kaya feel ko when mamamoo did that tsaka ano parang yun yung feel ko na highlighted to me parang ganon yun.

Researcher: Do you see that over time mamamoo song lyrics and music video aesthetics have significantly helped you understand feminism better

Yasmin: Hindi eh hindi ako nanggaling parang meron akong perception of what feminism is parang I do not expect um...a group from South Korea to be feminist in its like in its core, kasi alam ko na they're coming from a culture na would have for them to be successful they have to kahit papano mold themselves to fit the expectation kasi they won't succeed kaya lang sila super duper siguro na nagsasucceed in some way kasi nga they started with talent. So, meron na silang bargaining chip sa boss nila na oh we can do this kasi nagwa-one na sila eh one na yung mga song sila kumikita na sila pero, before that they had to lose weight alam mo yun nagko-comply sila in some way pero in a way okay din si ceo kasi yung scripting nya is "you won't be known for the typical idol expectations like in terms of looks so bumawi kayo sa talent", or sa live kasi walang nagla live na noon eh sobrang lakas nung backtrack nung lumabas sila, mas malala ngayon so parang since ngayon meron na silang selling point na unique to them kaya sila freely nakaka parang, ano to, freely nakaka galaw kasi meron na silang fan base mas nagiging free yung mga groups to do what they really like hindi sila nakokontrol ng higher than them or nang minsan di na sila nakakontrol ganoon ng fans kasi yung fans more

of kahit anong ibigay mo we would take it parang ganoon so parang ganoon, nasagot ko ba?

Researcher: Eh ino lang sa pero sa tingin mo it help you understand or hindi naman?

Yasmin: Hindi talaga kasi nga ewan ko nung nung...ang thinking ko kasi walang truly feminist na performer in general na kailangan kumita para kasi siyang yun sa pride alam mo yung mga company na bigla nagbebenta ng rainbow theme pero ang question ko palagi saan napupunta yung kinikita niyo para kasing for me put your money where your mouth is pag di ko nakikita na ang advocacy ba niya anong ginagawa niya outside the performance or as an artist. So, if i keep putting that burden sa mga favorites ko mahirap kasi tao lang din yung it's a business for me. I see it as a business so hindi kayo for me, hindi kayo feminist kasi pag business eh anong business model inherently capitalistic inherently ano sino gumawa ng capitalism men so alam mo yung mga ganoon capitalism benefits from us feeling shit so parang ganoon yung point ko so parang oh sige hindi ko nababurden din sila pero i like that there's an attempt especially sa south korea empowering siya siguro sa kanila pero sa akin i just see it as pero, hindi for me talaga, na empower talaga ako ni Hwasa personally na parang ay wow oo nga no kung hindi ako nagfifit kung nasan ako applicable kasi yung sinabi niya sa lahat di nga lang siya sa feminism eh basta it empowers you in a way na if you don't fit the mold make a separate mold parang ganoon ay siguro as a non binary kung hindi ako nagfifit sa ganito eto yung gagawin ko ganoon.

Researcher: what specific lyric or aesthetic of mamamoo inspires you and why

Yasmin: Iba iba sa kadang ah gusto ko talaga yung ano eh yung mga kanta nilang mga 'just believe in love', mga ganoon ano nga sinabi niya it's mostly mental health eh when it touches mental health 'don't worry' yung mga ganoon lyrics tapos for me yun yung nakaka inspire sa akin kasi i feel like i need to calm down a lot of the time parang ganoon so mga ganoon, or halimbawa if i want to feel hype up mga gogobebe ganyan kasi hindi ko naman laging naiintindihan yung lyrics kasi korean sya, pero yung mga sinasabi nila na where i could understand it or pag ayun yun yung nakaka hype up sakin gogobebe...Hmm wanna be myself, just believe in love, ano pa ba, gleam, again it's an ad. Kaya nga ang ganda kasi talaga pakinggan ano pa ba yung mga title tracks talaga nila for me i kaya ang ganda ng aya, yung aesthetic rin ng aya maganda, ano din for me it's empowering kasi paano ba ang gusto ko yung mga music video nila na walang presence of men i'm so sorry parang it's just them parang hindi kailangan ng hindi kailangan ng men sa sa ano sa background or narrative dun nung music video gusto ko yung mga ganda ayun.

Researcher: so thank you for participating yun na yun thank you so much.

Interview B: Francine Bacud

Francine: Yes, I'm ready now.

Researcher: So I am Airlie Licca Depante, a 4th year Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia from the University of the Philippines Open University. As part of my course requirements for this special project, MMS 200, I am investigating the influence of MAMAMOO's lyrics and music video aesthetics on the fans' appreciation, and or application of feminist beliefs. Of course there are no right or wrong answers but you ever feel uncomfortable you can withdraw anytime. This interview is being recorded but will remain confidential. Let's start. Can you tell us your name, age, and gender identity?

Francine: Okay, I'm Francine Bacud, you can call me Francine. I'm 22 years old, and I am female.

Researcher: Okay, so your highest level of educational attainment, work status, and how long have you been a fan of Mamamoo?

Francine: My highest educational attainment is high school. Senior high school, and then job level, I'm a student and I've been a fan of Mamamoo since 20, like, I'm thinking, um, this time, I don't know the year, but it was when Queendom happened. It was during the hip era.

Researcher: 2019, tama ba?

Francine: Yes, yeah.

Researcher: Okay, so do you consider yourself a feminist, were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following Mamamoo?

Francine: Yes, I'm quite familiar with the term, seeing as I've studied it, well, it came across during some of my subjects in high school and yes, I would, I do consider myself as a feminist.

Researcher: Since you consider yourself a feminist, what is feminism for you?

Francine: It's basically just trying to make...The most simple explanation I can give is equity for all genders, and just trying to play it fair for all the genders out there, in terms of opportunities, in terms of, you know, the wages, the salaries, the treatment, you know.

Researcher: So, with your meaning of feminism in mind, what is... Which five Mamamoo songs? In your opinion, are about empowerment?

Francine: Okay, I would say... Hip was one of them. And then, I would say... They have a song...See, this is why I kind of hesitated, because I don't know the songs on top of my mind. But, oh my gosh. I know the music video, but not the song. It's really in my head.

Researcher: Can you describe it? I might help you guess.

Francine: They were wearing... Oh, because they were wearing suits back then. And then, you know...The song is really about being... Like, really, women empowerment. Suits. I remember Hwasa was wearing red back then. She was wearing black hair. Well, she's always wearing mostly black hair. HIP, Yes I Am...I feel like I'm being judged...Even if it's solo, is it okay if it's solo it has to be mamamoo?

Researcher: Yeah, it has to be mamamoo as a group sadly. I apologize. I didn't send Francelle the questions.

Francine: Maybe Girl crush? Girl crush in a way. You're the best okay One more yeah, one more

Researcher: If you're stumped we can skip it

Francine: Scanning through the songs because I'm trying to remember. Okay, maybe the last one would be, I don't know if you would consider this, it is a MAMAMOO song but, Wanna Be Myself. Okay, okay. Yeah, okay. So, should I reiterate the songs?

Researcher: It's basically just Hip, Yes I Am, Girl Crush, You're the Best, and, ah, there, last one again? Wanna Be Myself.

Francine: This is just the lyrics, based on the lyrics, right?

Researcher: Yeah, yeah. It could be based on the lyrics, it could be based on the beat, for you, it's okay.

Francine: If it's like based on the video, um oh ah yeh, it's also a very good one, yeah.

Researcher: Okay, okay. Thank you, thank you for that. So, as a MAMAMOO fan, what activities do you do to support MAMAMOO? Like, do you buy their merchandise, do you stream their music, do you watch their videos?

Francine: Actually, I, I'm not the type of person to buy, um, merch at all, because I don't really now, but MAMAMOO's the only one that I have an album, and I have photo cards, so, yeah, I think that says a lot. So, it's not just, like, as a person that doesn't really buy, yeah, um, yeah, and I, I'm not the very social media person, but I did create a stan account.

Researcher: Okay. Because of MAMAMOO.

Francine: Yeah. So, it kind of started there. But then now, it's, um, I was like, uh, there was a point where I was really kind of, like, not obsessed, but I, I watched a lot of their shows, I watched a lot of, you know, I followed them, but I think it's also part of my personality where I don't really focus on it too much, and, uh, this suddenly became, uh, parang nagsisolo-solo na sila. So, like, there was so much going on. I remember ang daming mga, like, hindi mo alam sinong papanoodan mo. So, naging

busy ako. So, parang, unti-unti na lang yung mga updates na, na, ano, ko, right now, hindi na ako masyado, like, um, like, active in retweeting, active in voting. Naalala ko ng first time kong nag, ano, like, for when the album is getting, like, selling sa theater, or nag-giveaway. Like, legit, pinasali ko din si Francelle sa giveaways.

Researcher: Ang cute naman.

Francine: Kasi hindi nga ako, ano, parang baka sus yung account ko kasi hindi naman ako masyado nag-interact first. Tapos gumawa ko ng stan account. Tapos eh, siya medyo may stan account na, like, legit na yung account niya. So, pinasali ko siya. So, eh.

Researcher: So, kumbag, parang, ano, mawaw mo really shape, kumbaga, yung, parang, like, in a way.

Francine: In a way, yes. Kasi hindi din ako super mahilig sa concert. Like, hindi ako mahilig umattend ng concert. I said in my lifetime na isa lang yung attendan ko na concert and that's Paramore. Because I'm a Paramore fan. Um, pero si Mamamoo talagang, ano, like, hindi ko pinag-isipan, sige, magg-g ako bumili. You know, parang, parang, Francelle, kasi that's my first time, like, um, doing, like, buying tickets, gano'n, kasi.

Researcher: Yes, I also talked to my friend about that, that you also bought tickets.

Francine: Yeah, although now, because I'm not active in the stan, it's hard to do a solo stan. Because one week, this is my stan, next week it's another. That's the vibe Mamamoo will give. Yes. You'll really confuse who you really like. My stan right now is Wheein, but I cannot go to her concert. So it's okay, I've already seen her.

Researcher: Don't worry, if I see Wheein at 13, I'll just send a bunch of pictures to Francelle.

Francine: Yeah, I'm just living through people's lives through Twitter. Actually, when we had a concert, I didn't want to spoil my experience, but I said, you know, and my favorite part was when they switched up. I watched all of them, but when they did the Asia tour, they did that in all the tours, right? I watched them one by one, the difference. There wasn't much difference, but yeah. Okay, okay. Sorry, we're already talking. No, sorry, not off topic.

Researcher: No, it's okay, I appreciate it. So, next question. Do you believe that Mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? If so, can you cite cases and examples?

Francine: Yes, so I think, on top of my head, Moonbyul really is one of a kind of an idol. Actually, one of the reasons Mamamoo drew me is, at the beginning, you wouldn't think that they're really an idol because they're not what they call fitting the beauty standards of Korean, right? Like, I saw them because I found them out through variety shows because I love variety shows. And then, I started watching the

Immortals. Immortals. The one where they joined Immortals. What do you call that?
Contest?

Researcher: Yeah, Immortals songs.

Francine: Immortals songs, yeah. And then, you wouldn't think that they're, like, they would be famous. That's what they said in the other challenge just then. But then, they proved them wrong by not fitting the standards, by staying true to themselves. And I think, really, Moonbyul, the way she dresses, it's not bad, but very, she's not really fitting as the female K-pop idol that people want to see. And then, Solar, I remember her stages with her experimental era. The one where she did a bald style. She did it well. So, it's like, oh. And then, their music videos as well. Especially the one with Uhm Oh Yeh. Like, I was like, like, when you watch the music video, I wouldn't say there's a lot of connection with the lyrics itself. Like, but they decided to just cross-dress. And, like, they could have gotten actors to play the role when they were playing it. But they chose to do stuff. And I think, like, sure, maybe for comedy, but at the same time, like, it's branching out to this idea. And then, there's also the one where Solar is dispatched. But, it's just, I don't know. And they're not bothered by it. They're not, like, bothered by it. And so, yeah, I think they really promote. And even if, what else? Um, I don't know. Sorry, the question is just promoting feminism, right?

Researcher: Uh, yeah. Parang empowering for various genders. Empowering for various genders.

Francine: Next is Hwasa. I would say, like, she's been controversial for the past few years. Kasi the way she dressed though, diba? Madaming, especially Korean netizens, nagagalit, gano'n. And then, she challenged. I remember yung issue niya doon sa college na medyo sinusok siya. Kasi she was doing provocative daw ng mga actions. Pero yung guy na nag-perform hindi naman daw. Si Jay Park yata yun. Basta may guy idol na nag-perform. Tapos, like, bakit yun hindi pinash gano'n? Eh, Hwasa. So, it's sad. It's really sad na gano'n yung ano. Pero, um, the way na si Hwasa na she doesn't really back down. And she just keeps on. You know, like, sometimes mocking in a way yung pagsuot niya. Like, nagalit yung mga tao. So, parang wala siya masyadong pake she's still to doing it. Like, staying to herself. So, it really pushes the idea na, like, there's something wrong with it. There's something wrong with this society and how we do it and stuff like that. So, parang it just shows kind of more empowering the females to, like, don't just confirm or conform. Don't, like, hold yourself back because of these criticisms na hindi naman masyadong reasonable. Gano'n. Na unfair talaga for the female. Females especially. For the cis-het females kasi blank yung guys. So, at the same time, it's also showing yung true colors ng society. Kung ano ba talaga gusto nila. So, parang may point of reflection yun for the rest of the people, I guess. And in some way, that kind of empowers females or empowers yung others na medyo ma-re-realize na, Oo, ano, bakit kaya ganto? Bakit ganito yung tinatrato yung mga females? Gano'n. So, yeah. Yeah. There are other things. But that's like the other, some of the examples that I think. I think I can give you. Pago pa akong mabato.

Researcher: Okay lang. Thank you. It's very informative. Thank you. So, you mentioned yung parang nakaka-empower siya for the, ano, most importantly sa mga

cis-het females, right? So, parang do you believe that, aside from that, all spectrums of gender can relate to mamamoo?

Francine: So, in terms of the songs, hindi masyado, unless you take it in a general way, na empower yourself. Like, I guess, like, example, yung Wanna Be Myself, it's just very general, gano'n, gano'n. Pero yung Yes I Am, it's more on really the females. Na parang, yes, I am, I'm a female, kaya ganito. Diba, yun yung song. That's what it's all about. So, yeah. But if you, if you listen to it, it's very, very important. And if you look into it, it's basically, it depends on, I think for me, it depends on the person. So, if they're gonna take it in a positive, encouragement way. So, but it's applicable to all genders. I think mamamoo presents itself to be accepting, accepting naman for all of the different genders out there. And yung community na they built. Yes. With their actions, with their ano. I think it's, of course, hindi mo maaalis yung mga iba na nahaluan na ng beliefs nila, ng culture of beliefs. Pero I think most of the members sa community are, are promoting a space na ma-accepted or understanding sa mga different kind of genders. So, yeah.

Researcher: Actually, nasagot mo na rin yung next question ko. But, okay, let's skip it. So, what concepts or stage aesthetics that mamamoo have presented that are most important when empowering other genders?

Francine: they mayroon silang, ah, hip, yes, hip. Diba? Meron silang mga drag. Yan, yan diba?

Researcher: Yeah, yeah, yeah, hip.

Francine: Yeah, hip. So yeah. That's just one of the things na, like, you wouldn't even imagine like some of the other girlgroups. I'm not being very comparing. Diba? Pero, kasi napapansin ko yung ibang girlgroups that are very managed by only company, just by my own experience. Not to name drop, but for example, Blackpink, they don't get as much of a creative say in their songs and music videos, unlike Mamamoo. So if you compare it, it's really different. Because when you interview Mamamoo, they share that they're part of the process of making music videos. So you can see their influence. I think it's really good. The songs that Mamamoo has written, I think it's really good. The fact that they include drag queens, it doesn't really connect to the song itself, but the way that they added them for inclusivity.

Researcher: You can mention the solo if you want.

Francine: No, not the solo. Sorry, repeat the question. I forgot it.

Researcher: It's okay. What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other gender?

Francine: Other gender? Not just, or like all genders?

Sorry. Other genders, like all.

Francine: Okay. So including females in it? Yes. The stage concepts that sometimes... Because girl groups, in my opinion, even the past girl groups have been more on the feminine side. Girls' Generation. Sino yun? Grupo nila SinB?

Researcher: Sino ulit? Sorry.

Francine: GFriend. Sorry, GFriend. They're very like feminine, poppy vibes, but Mamamoo, sometimes their songs have an edge to them. And then their presence on stage, there are others that are very... Like they're wearing suits and all that. And they didn't wear suits before, but now wearing suits is becoming popular. Wow. For me, the four of them. They're very like individual. They have their individual colors. Yes. And then it just shows that there are different types of... You can present yourself in different kinds of banner and different types of clothing. Like the way that they dress, and the way that their stylists dress them, really shows their character now. But then they're not afraid to switch it up, just like their stage presence. And then they're like, you know, at the concert. Like, Moonbyul mostly wears suits. But suddenly she wore something that Hwasa wears. Like, oh my god. It just shows that, you know, you can, I guess, present yourself in different ways. I guess in all... That can encourage all types of gender to not really conform yourself to the standards of society. That if you're a guy, you should dress like this. You can also dress in other certain ways, you know? And present yourself to the way that you want to be. So, that's it.

Researcher: Okay. Yeah, that's the... What was it? It's like you already answered this, but I want to know your insight. It's like... Because you mentioned that it shows different types of... Problems that are happening in society that Mamamoo has presented. So, what issues of feminism that Mamamoo highlighted helped you see feminism in a different light?

Francine: Helped me see feminism in a different light?

Researcher: Yes. It's like "she gave me a different definition of feminism". It's like...For example, there's an issue that Mamamoo faced. For example, they had a backlash. Then they addressed it you were like, Wow, yeah, this is a new take. I like it. It's inspiring.

Francine: Not so much inspired, but... It's more of an example of the rejection that you had of the backlash on her clothes. Hmm. I remember that...I think she was wearing a... Like in the airports. The ones that she wears. Ah, yes. I think there was one where the netizens were bashing because her underwear was showing or something like that. She included that in the lyrics of the hip. But she did not change. Then, like... In the next airport events... If they face a backlash like that, it will be a bit conservative. They will fix it so that there will be no backlash again. But Hwasa is Hwasa. She sometimes over-do it to show that in a way mocking. And I'm happy because...So, in a way, it didn't really change. My perspective is that I can still be like that. Because in my perspective, I know that I can be like that even before mamamoo. But then it's just more of an encouragement for me. What Hwasa is doing. Don't be afraid. Don't be afraid. Also like just make fun of them it's not logical at all like at the same time I realize that oh it's like super sad situation sometimes it makes me angry but at the same time you just have to like I know face the backlash by just being true to yourself and like I don't just encourage yourself to just present yourself as long as you don't have a person who is being harmed their beliefs, their beliefs but like because I showed a little skin like "oh my gosh like the world will be

ruined the world of people will be ruined”, and in the way of what Hwasa was going to do it shows that the wrong is the perspective of the person that why like because people people's main criticism is because it's like women's bodies are being sexualized it's like that like it leads to it's a cause and effect and it leads to sexual harassment that's why people are being harassed like that but like it's just so wrong in my opinion. Why is the thinking like that and so in a way what mamamoo is doing especially the Hip, that song it's just like there's a famous party she's spitting in their face. yeah so in a way it's like she's spitting on the face of the criticism of the of these perspectives that it makes me happy.

Researcher: So, in a way do you think their lyrics their music videos concepts have helped you understand feminism better.

Francine: Yes in a way.

Researcher: Yes okay so last question what specific lyric or aesthetic whether it be a music video or their stage performance of mamamoo inspires you and why?

Francine: inspires me so it doesn't have to be gender at all yeah

Researcher: Yeah.

Francine: This is the hard part. Because I like a lot of... I can't remember the song title but I do remember the concept. Sorry, the question is song lyrics, right? Specific lyrics or aesthetics? One of my favorite lyrics. Although the general song is about a

breakup and about getting over it. But I really love the line of Windflower, Get better day by day. Someday I want that to get the truth on me. I know the song, the context of it is about a breakup. And there's no breakup. The whole aesthetic of that video is of my favorites so yeah, it's just get better day by day. In terms of lyrics that's my favorite song but in terms of vibe and genre its Words Don't Come Easy, it's just the flow of music, one of my favorites. Also, their stage presence.

Researcher: But for empowerment?

Francine: It can be cliché, Yes I Am. The whole vibe, the whole performance, the whole lyrics, is just really empowering because of Oh this who I am, this what I am, parang sa lyrics nila one day I could wear heels, on another I can do this.

Researcher: Okay, so thank you so much for participating in this interview.

Interview C: Hanna, Aster, Aleah, Nash, Ren

RESEARCHER: Good afternoon- good evening. I am Airlie Licca Depante, a fourth-year Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies from the University of the Philippines Open University. So, as part of my thesis, or ano, MMS 200 Special Project, I am investigating the influence of MAMAMOO's lyrics and music video aesthetics on the fans' impression, appreciation, and/or application of feminist beliefs. So, before getting started, this interview is documented purely for data analysis purposes only. And the only people who can hear this interview is my research advisor and myself. So, you can hold the interview process anytime you choose to do so, and you can leave at any time. So, after the interview, you can also withdraw your answers if you don't want to participate in my research, but your answers will be remained purely confidentially. So, first things first, ano po pangalan niyo? Age niyo? At tsaka, ano gender identity niyo? ...Go, ate Hanna.

Hanna: Uh... name?

Researcher: Name, age, at tsaka gender identity.

HANNA: Name, Hanna, age 3- mali. 37.

Researcher: Tapos gender identity—Ah, tama, gender identity.

Hanna: Female.

Researcher: Okay. So, ano rin po yung highest level of educational attainment and work status? Ate Hanna?

Hanna: College grad, tapos, regular employee sa private organization.

Researcher: How many years kana as a MAMAMOO fan? Ate Hanna?

Hanna: Wait, nag-start ako nung 2020 na 'eh. Early 2020.

Researcher: Okay, sige. So, ikaw naman, Ate Aster, same questions. Name, age, gender identity...Ate Aster?

Hanna: Dumating daw yung kapatid niya, wait lang.

Researcher: Okay, Ate Ren first.

Ren: My name is Ren, and then I am 27. And then how many years has it been with MAMAMOO...? It started with 2021, so almost three years.

Researcher: What is your age?

Ren: Age is 27.

Researcher: And what is your gender identity?

Ren: I am a female.

Researcher: What is your work status at tsaka highest level of educational attainment?

Ren: My educational attainment is a college graduate, and then I am an employee in a private company.

Researcher: Okay. So, Engineer... uh, Aleah.

Aleah: Hello.

Researcher: Same questions.

ALEAH: So, name, Ali. Age... 24.

RESEARCHER: Okay.

Aleah: Gender identity, female. Tas work status, regular employee sa San Miguel. And then educational attainment, college graduate. And then, nagstart akong maging fan... a casual fan in 2016, pero last year lang talaga naging... nag start na maging super fan nila. So, ayun. Kung considered lang na kung kailan sila naging official fan, I think 1 year lang.

Researcher: Okay. Let's start with ate Nash.

Nash: Akala ko ba si Aster?

Researcher: Andyan na ba?

Nash: Hindi, sige.

Researcher: Okay.

NASH: So, I am Nash, age 33, female, naging fan ay... I wanna be myself era. So, 2020 or 2021? Basta, 'yun na yun. And then, work status, contractual in government, and then education... unit sa Masters.

Researcher: So, Aster, it's your turn.

Aster: Yes, hello, Aster, 28, female bi. 2017 ako naging fan so, seven years? Uh, College grad... course... communication. Work status, self-employed, and then, nag part-time.

Researcher: Okay, so let's start with the interview questions itself talaga. So, first of all, do you consider yourself a feminist? And were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following MAMAMOO? So, ate Hanna? ate Aster? ate Ren?

Ren: I know feminism, but do I consider myself as a feminist? I don't think so. But it depends on how I view feminism. But for me, I'm not—I don't consider myself really as a feminist.

Researcher: Okay. So, for you, ate Ren, what is feminism, though?

Ren: Feminism is fighting for equal rights for women. It says it's equal, but for me, it's more than equal. And equity is much more needed than equality. So, that's why I don't consider myself as a feminist.

Researcher: You don't consider yourself a feminist—parang hindi ka talaga para for equity or what, if I may ask?

REN: No. Feminism is for equality. But what I want is equity.

Researcher: Oh, okay. Gets, gets. Sige. So, were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following MAMAMOO?

Ren: Yes, yes. I'm already aware of the concept. Even before.

Researcher: And lastly, which five MAMAMOO songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?

Ren: Five... Of course, number one is HIP. And then next will be Wanna Be Myself. And then next is Yes, I Am. Uh, what more? Hm...

Researcher: Pwede kang tumingin sa Spotify mo, if you want.

Ren: Pwedeng tumingin sa Spotify, pero yung lyrics. Tignan natin kung maalala ko yung name nung lyrics....check natin.

Researcher: Okay. Go lang, just take your time.

Resercher: Only group songs, no solos. You're still there, ate Ren?

Ren: Naghahanap lang

Researcher: Okay.

REN: Isama na natin yung Egotistic

RESEARCHER: Okay.

Ren: And then last will be... Last one will be...

Ren: Required ba na lima?

Researcher: Okay lang na kung wala na. Okay

Ren: Okay. 'Yun lang, apat.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. Ate Hanna, it's your turn.

Hanna: Okay.

Researcher: First of all, do you consider yourself a feminist?

Hanna: Yes. Siguro since... mga around... I started working sa... yung... yung international company siya 'eh. So I used to work for... Nung, after I graduated, mga local. Pero nung nag-move ako—dahil I would say my third job... It's a newspaper. So, marami kaming resources noon. It was owned by... yung isang education... Yung sa US na... isang mainly an educational... It's like... mainly parang nagpa-publish siya ng textbooks and everything. So... I would say... My social consciousness... nag-open up at that time. So... I was around 24, I think. And um, So... I would say since then... I had a... Not a better understanding, I would say pero, I had... Um... Found a definition of feminism that to me... Resonated. So... Kasi... Katulad ng sinabi ni Ren kanina, it's about equality. But... Equality in a sense na... kasi... Ah... May mga... Sabihin nating may... in the media, syempre, laging may two sides 'yan. And then, alot of people... Ever since nagsimula yung movement ng feminism, A lot of people have been... Um... Say... Demo... Demonizing feminism when all it is, it's really just... Um... Looking for equal rights for women and everything. Wala siyang gustong tapakan, wala siyang gustong bawasan, wala siyang gustong tanggalin. It's just that... an all-around... You know... better treatment for women... without jeopardizing whatever it is that's the right of anybody—anybody else. So, 'yun yung

nag-reside na sakín na definition ng feminism. It's just that... You know... Equal rights. And it's... And um... ayun... yun yung ano—medyo mahaba sagot ko, no?

Researcher: Okay lang, okay lang.

Hanna: Pero 'yun nga, I think the popular definition is... And I think because yung pinaka-maingay na feminists are always the right ones. Um... So... The quieter ones... the ones who are just... really looking for equal rights, it's not... It's not... hindi siya nakaka-harm sa men. I think it will actually even help them. Kasi... Um... Like for example... Yung... The traditional way of a family, It's always been...housewife and then provider. When your partner is equal, you share equal load instead of the traditional na maiingay against feminism. You consign women to this role, the caretaker, housewife. There's nothing wrong with that. Even that is protected by feminism because it's not just equality, it's freedom of choice. If you want to be a tradwife, that's protected by feminism because that's your choice. If you want to be professional, again, it's just equality and freedom to choose for yourself. 'Yun lang.

Researcher: Okay, thank you, ate Hanna. Pero do you think that... As you mentioned before, parang, you were influenced in a work environment. Do you think MAMAMOO also has an influence on your perspective on feminism or wala?

Hanna: I would say, Oo. Kasi, we come from a country that's very... hindi siya famous for being liberal. They have certain ideas about very firm beliefs in the role of men and women in society. And that leads into their media, diba? So, it's always, you know, if you're a girl, if you're a woman, if you're a young woman specifically, they

have an idea na ito ka; you're dainty, you're pretty, you're quiet. And I think when they burst into the scene, they challenged yung traditional views. And I think, in a sense, nagka-impact sa akin n'un. Because I think they're very... I wouldn't say brave because I think that trivializes everything. It's just that they're very... Basta, they know who they are and they're firm on who they are. And again, they chose to be who they are.

And again, in a sense, like I said, feminism is also just about choosing for yourself. And I think they're very good examples of choosing for yourself. And I think isa din sila sa malaking factors because I think feminism is gaining ground in South Korea. They showed the public that it's not necessarily bad if you don't conform yung societal ideas if you don't conform to your societal ideas na women should just be this and then men should be this. And they can wear what they want, do what they want without hurting anyone. It's just that, you know, I don't know if they identify as feminist because radical feminism is very noisy. So I think that's the popular definition of feminism. And I don't want to impose my views on them. But I think if we are looking at a good example of feminism, it would be them. Because they're doing it without being performative. They're just doing it by being themselves. So that's it.

Researcher: Okay. So on the topic of Mamamoo, ate Hanna; which five MAMAMOO songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?

Hanna: Okay. So... Syempre, andun na yung "Yes I Am." Of course, they're following the Korean beauty standards. And then "Hip", It's basically a diss track for... yun nga. Yung sinusubakan silang i-box ng people. And... Especially, you know, Hwasa.

Um... But... ... This is me. And then... I would say... Decalcomanie. Again... Because... In a way, I think it celebrates their sexual agency. And... Because, syempre, we know that it's... We know it's... You know... It's a song filled with euphemisms. Or sexual... Sexual acts, probably. But that's it. Again, in their society na... Women are... expected to just be meek and virginal. So... They released that in what? 2014?

Researcher: 2016. 2016.

Hanna: And... Not a lot of groups are even... Making songs like that. So... yes. I would say it's about empowerment. And then AYA. I think their video... more than anything. And... What else? I think... Illela. Again, it's in the same vein of Decalcomanie. Okay. So, that's it.

Researcher: Okay, thank you, ate Hanna. Thank you for your wonderful answers. So... Ate Aster?

Aster: I'm here.

Researcher: So, first of all... Do you consider yourself a feminist?

Aster: A feminist at its core values, yes.

Researcher: Since you said yes, what is feminism for you?

Aster: For me, it's not just for equality. It's not just having equal rights and opportunities. It's also about... About... It's also about gender norms, self-expression, women's experiences, tsaka identities din.

Researcher: Okay, so... Were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following MAMAMOO?

Aster: Yes. And... Since high school, I think I'm familiar with it.

Researcher: Okay, okay. So, it's like way back before, really. With Mamamoo itself, right?

Aster: Mm-hmm.

Researcher: So, lastly, which five Mamamoo songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?

Aster: Well, number one is probably...HIP. Because even if you search for it, it will probably come out. And then... Yes I Am, I Wanna Be Myself. 4x4ever. Mm-hmm. It's like that. But if you just look at the intro, the lyrics, you'll hear it right away. And then, Decalcomanie.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. So, Engineer? Aleah?

Aleah: Hello.

Researcher: So, do you consider yourself a feminist?

Aleah: I think, yes

Researcher: Then, since you think yes, what is feminism for you?

Aleah: Because... For me, it's more on women empowerment. Especially for me, because... I work on a male-dominated field. So... I want to show that whatever they do, the hard work, the good work, I can do it too. Since pinag-aralan ko din 'yun, pinag-aralan din nila 'yun. I can also do what they do. So, that's it.

Researcher: Mm. So, were you familiar with feminism before listening to MAMAMOO?

Aleah: Uh, yes. Since I think it's been a while, I can hear it. But more on negative sides. Uh... It's like... That's it.

Researcher: Can you expound on that further?

Aleah: Uh, because... Uh, there are some I hear that it's like... Feminists are just entitled people. That's how it is. What happens happens before. But... I also researched further that it's not like that what feminists want to reach.

Researcher: Mm.

Aleah: So... That's it. That's why I also tried to study as a mechanical engineer so that I can try on myself if I can do it or not. So, kinaya ko naman.

Researcher: So, in a way, do you think that MAMAMOO has gave a positive impact on your perspective on feminism?

Aleah: Uh, yes. Because sila din naman ang naging reasons why I got positive like towards feminism. It is more on women empowerment and giving equal rights to women.

Researcher: Which five MAMAMOO songs in your opinion are about empowerment?

Aleah: So, for me, the first one is Wanna Be Myself, then Hip, and then maybe the AHH OOP, Yes I Am, and Gogobebe.

Researcher: AHH OOP? Okay. Okay. Okay. Their old song.

ALEAH: Yes, old song.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. So, ate Nash, Ikaw naman. Okay. So, first, do you consider yourself a feminist?

Nash: Yes.

Researcher: So, um, then what is feminism for you?

NASH: Well, aside from what they answered na syempre, it is, um, equality, equality? Oh, what's the term? Oh, equality. Equality. And women empowerment. Equality between genders. And then, as what Ali (Aleah) said, so in our field, which is dominated mostly by men, so I believe that what the guys can do, we can also do it. And then, sometimes we can do it even good, than them. Better? But there are certain, oh yeah, but there are certain things that uh, we know that we can do, but they can do. And then, other, in other ways, um, they can, uh, they can do, but we can do better.

Researcher: Okay. So, ano, were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following Mamamoo?

Nash: Yes.

Researcher: So, and lastly, which five Mamamoo songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?

Nash: Ah, so, just like them, hip, wanna be myself, yes I am, then I'll add is you don't know me, and then, yeah, and then I can't think another.

Researcher: Okay lang, okay lang, it's fine. Before going to the other respondents, ikaw na lang muna, Ate Nash, since masasagot mo ito kagad. What activities do you do to support mamamoo? Do you buy merchandise? Do you stream?

Nash: Of course! Of course! I buy merch, especially albums, and then concert MD (concert merchandise), and then going to their concert, stream their songs, watch MV, and then, yeah.

Researcher: Like, do you almost do it daily?

Nash: For the song right now, no, but before, yes.

Researcher: Okay, okay. Alright, thank you. Si Ate Hanna naman, same question lang naman, what activities do you do to support mamamoo?

Hanna: Ah, yun, same, um, yung merch, official merch, tapos stream ng videos, albums, uh, minsan pati yung variety shows nila, tinitignan ko kung saan sila lalabas. And then, ayun, kung nasa VIU, or sa, minsan meron sila sa Netflix, papanoorin ko, ganun.

Researcher: Ah, okay. So, parang very watcher, ah, avid watcher ka ng kanilang variety shows?

Hanna: Yeah Oo, kasi, diba, during pandemic, yun nga, wala ka naman ibang gagawin. Actually, doon ko sila na-discover, yung pandemic, kasi nga, unang-una ko

sila nakita sa, like, specifically, um, yung, yung Gopchang Mukbang ni Hwasa, tapos parang from there, nasundan ko na sila, yung channel nila, yung, yung, MMMTV (MAMAMOO TV on YouTube) pa, diba? Kaya nga, yun, sa, yun. So, from there, pinanood ko na. And, parang, before yung, actually, before yung music nila, yung sila mismo. Kaya, more on yung, pinapanood ko sila.

Researcher: Mm, okay. So, ah, next, si Aleah?

Aleah: Hello!

Researcher: So, ayun, same question. What activities do you do to support Mamamoo?

Aleah: Ah. Yung, unang-una, buy merch, official man or fan-made. Tapos, ah, everyday streaming ng songs sa Spotify and, ah, music videos, mga gano'n. Ayun. Tapos, minsan, kapag may time, nanonood din ako ng, um, variety shows or ng, sa videos ng, galing sa YouTube channels nila.

Researcher: So, parang, yung songs, ah, on the topic of songs, parang, everyday talaga pinapakinggan mo?

Aleah: Yes, everyday.

Researcher: Mm. Okay.

Aleah: Kasi, I cannot function nang wala akong music.

Researcher: Tapos, sila, syempre, ang choice of music mo?

Aleah: Yes. Sila yung nasa go-to na music ko. Okay. Kapag nagawa kong trabaho or naglilinis, gano'n.

Researcher: So, okay, let's proceed to Ate Aster.

Aster: Yes?

Researcher: So, same question lang naman. What activities do you do to support mamamoo?

Aster: Ah, hindi kasi ako ma-merch. So, pero, nakabili naman ako ng ibang merch nila. Pero, hindi nga lang lagi. Pero, nag-i-i-stream ako, gano'n. Tapos, every time they make a comeback, I make sure that, uh, I vote. For them.

Researcher: Ooh. So, masipag ka mag-vote sa mga apps nila, gano'n?

Aster: Oo. Masipag din akong manood, actually. Napapanood ko mga videos nila.

Researcher: Would you say, parang yung pagpanood mo ng videos, parang daily, gano'n? Or di naman?

Aster: Ah, daily? Oo, meron at meron akong napapanood na video nila.

Research: Mm. Okay. Okay. And lastly, si Ate Ren?

Ren: Hmm?

Researcher: Ah, what activities do you do to support Mamamoo?

Ren: Number one pagbili ng merch, every time may bagong release, and kaya bilhin, binibili, and also stream music. Everyday, with Spotify, kahit naka-shuffle pa yan, kahit iba-iba playlist pa yan, lagi merong Mamamoo songs. And then, ah, I'm not official, part, pero may mga times na, ah, kasi I have a group chat na kasama ng ibang admins or ibang officers ng Mamamoo PH. Kapag meron mga, ah, pagsasama, mga discussions doon or mga needed na, for example, ah, opinions or nang hihingi sila na mga suggestions, is sumusama din ako doon or, ah, nabibigay din ako ng mga insights or mga suggestions regarding, for example, mga activities, na pwede kong magbibigay. I don't know what to do in honor of them or kapag, for example, last time with MyCon (MAMAMOO Concert in 2023), ah, nag-volunteer ako during noong ticketing, as well as noong mismo araw ng concert, so yung mga ganun na activities.

Researcher: Hmmm. Ok. So, in...as a volunteer, Ate Ren, ano ang parang ginagawa mo pa rather than just ano, like, giving ideas, volunteer, ano pa yung parang nabibigay mo sa fan base?

Ren: Volunteering? Mostly assist lang. For example, sa ticketing, mga goal natin is maka-ensure lahat na makakuha ng ticket. So, dun sa line, sa first-come, first-served, talagang strict tayo with that. So, kailangan masunod yung mga instructions na binigay from mga officers. And then, nung mismo concert day, for example, yung mga banners, isa ko sa mga in-charge doon. So, kailangan lahat ng fans is may mabigyan ng banners. Also, sa pag-ensure na walang magiging gulo or lahat is ma-execute ng smooth that time. Ayan yung mga nagawa ko before as a volunteer.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. So, next question. I think, sigé, mauna na si Ate Hanna for this. Do you believe that mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? Can you cite cases and examples? Ate Aster muna lang, sigé.
Ate Aster?

Aster: Yes, yes, yes?

Researcher: Do you believe that mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? Can you cite cases and examples?

Aster: Ah, yes. Kasi usually, di ba, kapag tinutukoy natin female, lalo na sila isang female group, focus tayo sa feminine side. Naka-focus tayo sa femininity. Pero as mamamoo, as individuals din sa styles nila, yung outfits nila, in or outside the stage, in the stage, or as personal styles man, makikita mo na hindi sila naka-stuck lang sa isang aspect ng gender. For example, si Moonbyul, ayun, di ba? Minsan nasasabi

siya as androgynous. Kasi nga yung yung style niya. Tapos, hindi lang siya, kaya niya both feminine tsaka masculine styles.

Researcher: Mm-mm. Uh, any more additional, or yun lang muna sagot mo? Ah, yun lang muna. Okay, so Ate Hanna?

Hanna: Ah, um, yun, same. Same nung, ah, sagot din ni ni Aster, ano, yung personal style nila, pati sa videos nila, is I think, oh, appropriate siya. And, and, um, inspiring siya sa um, genders. And, um, naalala ko lang, syempre, yung kahit yung joke, pa-joke sila, yung, yung video nila ng nakalimutan ko talaga yung title, yung, yung, yung male si, nag-male costume si Hwasa, tsaka si Moonbyul.

Researcher: Uhm Oh Ah Yeh?

Hanna: Oo, Uhm Oh Ah Yeh., yeah. So, doon, um, tinakita nila na, ah, hindi sila, hindi sila takot na yung, yung aesthetics nila is sabihin na, ano ba yan, ganyan, na yung maridicule kasi, um, I think, yun nga, parang, yung personal styles nila is very, um, very appropriate for all genders. Tapos, yun din sa HIP, diba, like, doon sa part ni Solar na in-invite niya din mga drag queens doon sa video nung HIP. Um, ayun, I would say, ah, very inclusive din talaga sila yung aesthetics nila in style. Um, okay.

Researcher: Any more additional or yun lang naman so far?

Hanna: Yun lang.

Researcher: Okay. So, Ate Ren? So, same question. Do you believe that Mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? And can you cite cases and examples?

Ren: I think, yes, kung titignan, and also, kasi, lalo na, me as a fan, lagi ako tambay sa Twitter. So, makikita mo sa Twitter, yung mga pictures nila, whether any activities, or whether personal, or kapag sila isa sa public, yung mga style nila, or aesthetics nila is, iba-iba siyang, pag, kumbaga, parang iba-iba siyang style. So, may sarili silang, ah, kung paano nila may portray. Or, paano yung nakinepresent, usually nila, on different kinds of, ah, occasions, or different kinds of, ah, instances. And then, for the cases, um, number one would be, yung mga airport fashion. Airport fashion nila. Kasi, lalo na, lalo na, una-una, is dun unang nacrictize si Hwasa. Nanggaling doon. Pero, pinandigan niya yun. And then, next naman, will be, examples naman would be, for example, yung sa mga music videos. Example nun is, yung sa hip, yung regarding, yung sa band. Lalo na yung style doon ni Solar, na half, which is, sinabihan siya na wag, pero pinatuloy pa rin niya. And then, next naman would be, yung kasama nila yung mga drag queens doon. But, sa performance mismo, yung sa performance nila, sa decal ,and also, mismo, doon sa music video ng Hip, is talagang, doon makikita na, they are for all genders. Yeah. So, that's all.

Researcher: So, relating to that, Ate Ren, parang isabay na natin yung next question, since na- mention na may relation. Do you believe that all spectrums of gender can relate to mama mo din?

Ren: I think yes. Yes. Kasi, may makikita mo yun, kapag pumunta, on Twitter, also, kapag pumunta ka sa isang event or concert, ng mamamoo. Kasi, may kita mo, lahat pag may interact ka ng tao doon, is, they are of different gender. They're of different gender. And also, most recently, may kita mo, si, si, si Yong, si Solar, siya is mostly nag-interact with drag queens. And then, with Byul naman, and, uh, with Byul and Wheein, yung mga expression nila doon sa mga songs sila, it's not just for, uh, heteros. And also, with, uh, with Hwasa. Hwasa is very, very well beloved by the drag queens, with the gays, and any kinds of, any, uh, genders, because of how she portrays herself, and how she carries for herself. So, I say that, Mamamoo relates for all genders.

Researcher: Mm. Okay. Thank you. Thank you, Ate Ren. So, Ate Nash?

Nash: Uh, Yes? Ano?

Researcher: Uh, do you believe that Maomong's style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders?

Nash: Yes.

Researcher: Okay. So, Why? Uh, can you, can you cite cases and examples?

Nash: Uh, ano nga ba yun? Well, kagaya nung sinabi ni Ren, kasi, mostly, diba, um, yung styles nila, especially yung, uh, pananamit nila, is, hindi siya nakafocus sa isang gender. Yun nga, uh, they can wear what they want, as long as they feel

comfortable. And then, I think, ayan, uh, empowering siya kasi, uh, parang sinasabi nila na, um, yeah, it's your style, it's your body, so you can do whatever you want.

Researcher: Mm-hmm. Okay. So, yeah, last one si Aleah, engineer?

Aleah: Hello.

Researcher: Same question. Do you believe that Mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? Can you cite cases and examples?

Aleah: Yes. So, based on the way they portray themselves, sa pananamit nga nila, they have their specific styles na gusto nung i-portal. So, I think doon pa lang nakikita na very empowering sa kung anong gusto mong suotin, pwede mong suotin. Basta doon ka-comfortable, kaya mong dalhin, suotin mo. So, kahit na female group sila, Moonbyul is known for being androgynous nga. But I think other members can also pull off the androgynous looks. Based on the way they carry themselves.

Researcher: Okay. So, thank you. Nasagot na siya kanina ni Ate Ren, pero I want your insights, all of your insights. Si Ate Hanna muna, do you believe that all spectrums of gender can relate to Mamamoo?

Hanna: Yes. Yes. So, nakikita naman natin siya doon sa fans nila na umaattend ng concert. Basta yung online, mostly, part ng LGBTQ++ yung mga fans nila. And then, pag pumunta ka doon sa Mamamoo Philippines page, may mga nagpo-post doon. Like, may isang guy doon na madalas mag-post ng dance videos niya. And I don't

know how he identifies, pero... Yung, I think, yung fact na very comfortable siya na mag-post nung dance videos niya doon sa, like, I would say, it's probably semi-public kasi private group yun, di ba, yung Mamamoo Philippines. Yun, na-ipost yung dance videos niya. At, yun, i-out yung self niya as a fan. Um, so, nakita natin, hindi lang women, hindi lang men. All across genders is inspired nila and yun, nakaka, um, nagre-resonate sa kanila.

Researcher: Hmm. Okay, thank you. So, Ate Aster?

Aster: Yes?

Researcher: Uh, do you believe that all spectrums of genders can relate to Mamamoo? And how so?

Aster: Uh, yes. Ano, um, nahahatak nila, uh, various genders with their styles, uh, personalities, outfits. Uh, songs, choreography. Kasi hindi lang talaga siya, um, style ng iisang gender, eh. Pwede talaga siya pang lahatan.

Researcher: Hmm. Okay, so, thank you. Uh, Ate Nash?

Nash: Yes?

Researcher: Do you believe that all spectrums of genders can relate to Mamamoo?

Nash: Yes. Uh, actually, not only all genders but also different age group. Kasi minsan may nakikita ko there are families, may tatay, then may nanay, then may mga anak na fan ng Mamamoo. Yeah, so, yun.

Researcher: Hmm. Okay, thank you. So, next question. Uh, how do Mamamoo's lyrics on various songs empower different genders? So, Ate Hanna?

Hanna: Hmm... Sorry paulit ng tanong.

Researcher: Okay lang, uh, how do Mamamoo's lyrics on various songs, mga iba't ibang kanta nila, yung mga lyrics nila, paano sila nakaka-empower ng gender, different genders?

Hanna: I think diba? Kasi... Usually, yung kanta nila is very gender neutral yung lyrics, hindi gender yung pronouns. So, I think conscious decision nila yun kasi nga gusto nilang maging inclusive. So, ayun, parang the fact na hindi gendered yung lyrics nila. So, everyone can relate and probably use it kung kailan nilang gusto in any situation.

Researcher: Oh, okay. So, balikan natin si Engineer, si Aleah. So, sorry, hindi kita natanang sa previous question. Do you believe that all spectrums of genders can relate to mamamoo?

Aleah: Yes.

Researcher: How so?

Aleah: Kasi, wait lang. Kasi sa tingin ko hindi lang kasi, kasi based na sa na-oobserve ko sa other girl groups, more on male dominated yung mga, alam nila, yung mga fanbase nila. Pero, on mamamoo naman, ang nakikita ko is more on female ang mas madami. So, pero may mga, ilan-ilan din naman na ano, male. Pero sa tingin ko, kaya nilang or sakop nila kahit anong gender identity or kung ano, kung ano man na ina-identify mo sa sarili mo. Kasi, sa tingin ko, sa talent pa lang nila, sa galing pa lang nilang kumanta. So, natanda nila, mahuhupan na kagad sa kanila. And bukod pa yun sa mga sa visuals nila and sa iba pa nilang talents and sa personality nila.

Researcher: So, you mention na yun nga, sa talent nila. But do you think on their lyrics, nakaka-empower yung different genders?

Aleah: Yes. Since um, mayroong, may mga songs, may iba't iba silang songs na nakaka-empower. Katulad nga, nung... wanna be myself. So, based pa lang dun sa title ng song, so, gusto mo lang maging sarili mo. I- express mo yung sarili mo kung anong gusto mong gawin sa buhay mo.

Researcher: So, parang in a way na ano, nakaka-uplift siya for all genders sa lahat?

Aleah: Yes. Sa lahat. Sa lahat ng taong makakarinig ng kanta ngayon or makaka-encounter ng kanta na yun.

Researcher: Okay. so, thank you, Aleah. Ate Aster?

Aster: Yes?

Researcher: So, how do mong lyrics on various songs empower different genders?

Aster: Yung nasabi ni Ate Hanna kanina, kasi dahil wala nga siyang pronouns, pwedeng makarelate ang kahit na sino. Magagamit siya ng various genders.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. So, si Ate Nash?

Nash: Yes. Wala na ako yung idadagdag. Sinabi na nila eh. Okay. Okay lang naman. No problem.

Researcher: Ikaw naman, Ate Ren.

Ren: Ano yung question?

Researcher: How do Mamamoo's lyrics on various songs empower different genders?

Ren: Bigyan natin yung example yung sa may part ng chorus na wanna be my self. May part kasi doon ng chorus is you and I are not different. So, sabi nyo doon lahat ng, parang don't compare kasi lahat tayo is pare-parehas tao. So, whether you, any

kinds of gender, ano man yung expression mo, ano man yung tingin mo sa sarili mo, we are not different kasi pare-parehas tayong tao.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you, Ate Ren. So, Ate Hanna, next question. What concepts, music videos, stage aesthetics, on top of your head, of mamamoo, has presented that are most important when empowering other genders?

Hanna: Anong stage or anong performance?

Researcher: Ano yung naiisip mo kagad? Parang pinaka-importante when empowering other genders? Mga pa-stage performance, aesthetics, music videos, o kaya concept nila?

Hanna: Yun, naiisip ko pa rin yung kung makaya eh. Kasi nga, parang, at that time I think medyo controversial yung ginawa nila. Pero, yun nga, the fact na hindi sila, hindi sila takot. Na yung ano, yung to look a certain way. And I think that also empowers yung their fans, their followers na, oh, we, we, ginawa nila yun. And then, so ibig sabihin, hindi, kung parang hindi, as long as comfortable, yun. Kung parang magiging mababalik ka dun sa skin mo. Kung ano yung i-present mo physically, kung anong i-present mo sa public, is okay. That empowers it. Tapos, another thing is, nung pumunta sila sa stage as teletubbies. In a sense, parang, again, that's empowering. Kasi, ah, yun nga, parang, eh, nang-expect ng mga taong, oh, they're, they're big stars. Kailangan, eh, all the time, they look a certain way. Parang fashionable, yun nga. Pero, they, um, yun nga, they went with it and showing their

fans na basta comfortable ka and masaya ka, it's, it's okay. So, that in itself is very empowering.

Researcher: Okay, thank you. So, Ate Ren?

Ren: Yes?

Researcher: Same question. What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other gender?

Ren: Um, I think nasagot ka na rin siya kanina yung, ah, example ko is yung that one performance ng Mamamoo ng Decalcomanie with the drag queens, kasi that time noong pinerform nila its 2016 early 2017 so panahon na yun sabihin natin may ibang part na open naman na pero that time talaga compared to now, mas scrutinized. Yung, mas scrutinized yung ginawa nila. Pero, they did not, they did not back down. Talagang, ah, talagang, pinerform nila yun with that, ah, with that group of drag queens. Talagang, pinakita nila na they are different. And that they, ah, they, they, that they can fight or they can, ah, show na ito sila. And then, panindigan nila kung ano yung gusto nila, kanila eh. And then, kung ano man yung gusto nila iparating doon through their songs and through their performances. Through all of those stages.

Researcher: Okay. Sige. Thank you, Ate Ren. So, Engineer?

Aleah: Hello.

Researcher: Same question. What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other genders?

Aleah: For me, ang una kasing lumabas sa isip ko is yung music video nila na nakipag-coordinate talaga sila with drag queens and finiture sila on the music video itself. So, parang dun palang I think na empower na lahat ng pwede mong i-empower na makakita ng video.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. Ate Aster?

Aster: Yes?

Researcher: So, same question. What concepts, music videos, stage aesthetics on top of your head by Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other genders?

Aster: Ang unang pumapasok sa isip ko yung hip music video. Kasi ang dami talaga ng concepts na ginawa nila dun. For example na lang yung half and half concept ni Solar na may mga kasama siyang drag queens. Tapos, next siguro yung pagiging CEO ni Moonbyul dun na usually, diba, in a patriarchal society, positions of powers have always been given to men. Ayun.

Researcher: Okay. So, Ate Nash?

Nash: Yes.

Researcher: Ayun. Same question. What concepts, music videos na naiisip mo? Stage aesthetics even na nagawa na ng Mamamoo?

Nash: Actually, yung hip din kasi, sabi nga, nila din, is mostly yung performance nila even yung music videos and then yung, yung stage performances nila is, yun nga, nag-show yung iba't ibang types.

Researcher: Okay. Sige. Thank you. Next question, Ate Hanna. Last three questions na guys. Wag kayo magalala. Ate Hanna, what issues of feminism have been highlighted by Mamamoo that has helped you see feminism in a different light?

Hanna: Um, yun nga, yung, ah, yung, they, kahit, ah, ilan, ilan ng beses na yung Korean public and yung media has been against them, um, they stayed true to themselves. Hmm. Na, parang hindi sila nag-back down, um, and throughout yung career nila, makita mo naman, kahit nag-evolve yung personal styles nila, yung, yung core personality pa rin nila, yung core nila is, ah, makita mo na, it's still the same. And they're, they're still unapologetically themselves. So, ayun.

Researcher: Okay, thank you. Ah, Ate Ren muna. Ate Ren?

Ren: Issues, ah. Siguro, ah, i-relate ko na lang siya doon sa lyrics ng, ah, Yes I Am. Kasi sa Yes I Am, I keep, parang doon is, binibreak nila yung stereotype ng women. So, for example, yung, ah, also, yung sa standard ng, ah, physical appearances ng

women. For example, yung kay Yong with her cheeks. Hmm. And then, kay Byul is yung expression niya doon sa damit. So, kumbaga, yung parang stereotyping na, as mentioned din kanina, is yung stereotyping with women is through that song, is also lyrics din ng hip, or mostly is expression ng mga women. Yun yung mostly na, ah, nag-break nila na, okay lang, kahit, you can, you do you, you do you. Yun yung parang inaano nila is, kung ano, kung paano gusto mo i-express mo sa rin niyo mo, go, go for it. Or, ah, regardless kung ano man yung sabihin ng iba, kasi, ikaw yun.

Researcher: Okay. So, next, Ate Aster?

Aster: Yes. I'm here.

Researcher: Ah, what issues of feminism have been highlighted by Mamamoo that has helped you, feminism, to see in a different light?

Aster: Hmm. Sa akin, ah, showing and owning sensuality.

Researcher: Hmm. Can you expound on that further?

Aster: Ah, kasi kapag, ah, usually, ang, sa isang patriarchal society, ang tingin sa mga babae na ino-own yung sensuality nila, yung okay sila sa pananamit nila, yung hindi nakabase sa society, yung gusto nilang style, yung hindi nakakaayon sa norm, ganun. Actually, vini-vilify yan. Parang masama yung tingin, parang mababa yung tingin sa mga ganong klaseng babae.

Researcher: Bakit, bakit naman mababa ang tingin?

Aster: Ah, well, ah, ang tingin kasi ay, um, girls should be prim and proper. Okay. Yan. Yun ang nakafix na thoughts ng mga tao sa ganun na, kasi yun na yung nakasanayan ng society na tingin sa mga babae. So, once na, yun, pinakita mo yung sensuality mo, parang, ah, she doesn't match what is the norm.

Researcher: Hmm. Ah, thank you.

Aster: Next is, ah, ah, sige-

Researcher: Hindi, hindi, hindi, dagdag ka lang.

Aster: Mayroon pa isa.

Researcher: Okay, go. Dagdag ka lang. Sorry.

Aster: Ah, ano, motherhood. Motherhood. Hmm. Ah, yun. Being a single mother. Ah, kasi sa isang music video nila ba, diba, sa hip, si Hwasa, single mother siya dun. Ah. Tapos, ine-enjoy niya lang yun. Hmm. Ine-enjoy niya lang yun. It should not also be vilified din. Ah, ah. Diba, hindi dapat i-discriminate yung mga ganong situation. Either she chose to be a single mother or not. Dapat ang gawin na lang ng mga tao is to support, diba? Ayan. You know.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you, Ate Aster. Thank you. Ah, Engineer?

Aleah: Hello.

Researcher: What issues of feminism that have been highlighted by Mamamoo that have helped you see feminism in a different light?

Aleah: Ah, so, ano, ah, for me, ah, as nung nabanggit ko kanina, so, it's the part na before, ang dating na sa akin ng feminism is, ah, women being too entitled and just forcing kung ano yung gusto nila sa ibang tao. When in reality, women is just trying to have or to live in equal grounds as men, pursuing the life and career that, ah, ah, that they want for themselves. Ayun.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. Ate Nash. Ah, anong issues of feminism na na-highlight ng Mamamoo?

Nash: So, yun. Based din kasi dun sa ilan nilang MV, ah, especially din dun sa HIP, nagpapakita siya ng, ah, eh nga, katulad sinabi ni Aster kanina, yung CEO as si Moonbyul, and then si Solar, Rockstar, and then, ah, iba't-ibang types ng work na pwede rin pasukin as, ah, girl, or as a guy, diba? So, yun. I think dun siya pumapasok for me.

Researcher: Hmm. Okay. Thank you, Ate Nash. Ah. Alright. Next question. Ah, do you see that over time, Mamamoo's songs and lyrics, ay, songs, lyrics, and music videos have significantly helped you understand feminism better? Ate Hanna?

Hanna: Um, in, in a way, yes. Um, yung nga, yung they're owning their, their personal style, they're owning their, um, their, their sexual, sexual expression. Um, I would say na, parang, sa music videos, the way they present themselves, is, pinapakita nila na, ah, it's okay to be you. And, it's okay to, to choose. Ah, ah. Parang, if, to choose your, ah, to choose your own path. And, um, and again, yung nga, parang bumabalik tayo sa yung what feminism is to me is, other than equality, is, is the power of choice. na, um, pinapakita nila na, you're free to choose. To choose what, ah, whatever, yung nga, path or presentation or whatever. Choose to, to be who you are. Parang binibigyan nila ng, I wouldn't say permission, pero binibigyan nila ng, parang representation na parang, um, you don't have to conform. You don't have to bow to the society, societal pressures. Um. Ayun.

Researcher: So, you mentioned your, parang ano, you mentioned, Ate Hanna, na parang ano siya, ah, it's similar to your perspective on feminism. So, may I ask, what specific lyric or aesthetic, whether it be from a music video or stage performance, inspires you? And why?

Hanna: Um, yung ano, ah, I would say yung lyrics. Talagang nung, um, Yes, I am. Kasi, yun talaga yung sinasabi nila na parang, this is me. Ah, ito, kung ma parang, yung, yung nga, yung chubby cheeks ni Solar, yung shape ng mukha ni Moonbyul, yung, I think yung, yung demeanor ni Wheein was also, um, parang na, na criticized. And then, of course, everything about Hwasa, parang lagi nalang, every, every hour, may offensive silang nakikita about Hwasa. But, um, in the face of that, um, yung buong song na yun is, again, they're, they're, they're owning their identities. And

they're saying, ah, um, ito man, ito man yung traditional expectation, yung societal expectation. Pero, this is me, and I'm not going to apologize for it. And then, yun.

Researcher: Okay, thank you, Ate Hanna. Ah, Ate Aster?

Aster: Yes?

Researcher: So, do you see that over time, Mamamoo's songs and lyrics, aesthetics, ah, music video aesthetics have significantly helped you understand feminism better?

Aster: Um, yes.

Researcher: Ah, how?

Aster: For me, ah, their songs and music videos speak for themselves. Um, um, malalalim siya ka mabibigat na information ng feminism, nare-relay ng maayos in the simplest, in the simplest way possible through Mamamoo. Hindi siya information na paulit-ulit dinidikta kapag hirap kang intindihan. You can easily understand when you listen and watch them.

Researcher: So, parang, um, in a way, what specific lyric or aesthetic, whether it be from a music video or stage performance of Mamamoo inspires you and why?

Aster: Lyrics?

Researcher: Lyrics, music video, yung parang tumatak talaga sa'yo na nag-i-inspire sa'yo.

Aster: Um, hip tsaka 4x4ever. Hip music video, Uhm Oh Ah Yeh. Music video, lyrics na rin. Pero sa hip, more on lyrics saka music video. Uhm Oh Ah Yeh, music video. Tapos, uh, 4x4ever lyrics.

Researcher: Uh, can you explain why? Like, why?

Aster: Sa 4x4ever kasi hindi pa nila nababanggit, ah. Nakalagay dun sa lyrics, I live the way I want. Tapos, I love me because I'm more confident than anyone. Tapos, love myself, myself forever. Shall we enjoy this moment without regret?

Researcher: Ah, so parang it uplifts your, you. Ganun. It uplifts you, yourself, ganun. Okay. So, thank you. Ate Ren?

Ren: Yes?

Researcher: So, do you see that over time, Mamamoo's song lyrics and music video aesthetics have helped you understand feminism better?

Ren: Yes, of course. Uh, though, uh, sabi ko kanina is I don't really consider myself as a... as a feminist. But, uh, what I mean by that is hindi...uh, hindi... I don't want to be, uh, labeled kasi isang... I don't want to be under isang label kasi ako is... I want

to be impartial. So, uh... So, lahat is... parang gusto ko is lahat meron perspective. So... Pero hindi ko naman din dinidenay yung nagiging, uh, nagiging, uh, role ng, mamamoo. It comes with feminism. And I think that... Yes. Kasi yung may mga tao, sabi natin, minority, is hindi hirap sila to relay or, uh... For example, kasi yung sabi nga ngayon with Aster, yung mga complicated or yung mga mabibigat na issues is... hindi naman lahat kasi nakakaintindi. So, through their songs, through their, uh...through their, uh, works, through their... through their art, is na mapakita or narirelay ng mga mamamoo. Yung, uh... Ano nga ba yung feminism? Parehas lang tayo tao. Whether, uh, any genders may...Para may tindahan, ano nga ba yung feminism?

Researcher: Mm. So what specific lyric or aesthetic whether it be from a music video or stage performance of Mamamoo inspires you and why?

Ren: Ah that would be 2016 Melon Music awards. The performance with Pinky Cheeks. It is a strong message to perform with a gender fluid group on a stage with thousands of audience. They don't care if they will be judged. They want to relay what they are standing up for. That conviction to own up really inspires me to better understand and accept myself.

Researcher: Okay, thank you. Engineer?

Aleah: Hello.

Researcher: So, do you see that over time, Mamamoo's songs, lyrics, and music video aesthetics have significantly helped you understand feminism better?

Aleah: For me, yes. Mamamoo helped me see feminism, helped me see feminism that it is more than just women empowerment. It's also more on normalizing what society did as not stereotype for women. It's more on, ayan nga, so, normalizing kung ano yung hindi normally naikita ng mga tao na ginagawa ng mga babae. So, just live confident. And, wag magpa-affect ka sa mga discouragement na sinasabi ng mga ibang tao sa'yo.

Researcher: So, ano, you mentioned na parang it help you understand better. Is there a specific lyric or aesthetic of Mamamoo that inspires you?

Aleah: For me, yung sa ano, yung lyrics sa song ng Wannabe Myself, where merong ah, hindi ko lang sure kung ito yung sakto, pero may lyrics doon na if translated, ah, ang ibig sabihin is, wala akong pake kahit anong sabihin mo. Kung wala, kung hindi mo naman alam sa nasabi mo, huwag ka nalang mangelam. Parang gano'n. Basta, basta ito, gagawin ko to. Ito gusto kong gawin. Kung mo ang pakilaman, gano'n.

Researcher: So, parang nakaka-uplift sa sarili mo, in a way, yung lyric na yun.

Aleah: Yes.

Researcher: Okay. So, thank you. Ate Nash?

Nash: Yes?

Researcher: So, do you see that over time, Mamamoo's song, lyrics, and music videos, aesthetics, have significantly helped you understand feminism better?

Nash: Yes?

Researcher: Ah, how so?

Nash: Ah, ayun na naman tayo sa pag-iisip ng sagot. Okay. Well, kasi, yun nga, they show different ah, sides of the story. Kasi may iba-iba silang pinoportray, and then may iba-iba silang gustong iparating. Ah, so yun.

Researcher: So yun. So, last na, ah, what specific lyric or aesthetic na, by Mamamoo, na nakaka-inspire sa'yo, and bakit?

Nash: Mamamoo is, um, ano ba yun? Nakalimutan ko yung sasabihin ko. I think, get better day by day, yung lyrics. Yeah. Because, I think, actually, it's for the group, but, kasi, what I consider most, kasi yung solo, kasi, yeah.

Researcher: Okay lang, i-mention mo yung solo, parang special mention.

Nash: Ah, syempre, yung sa solo, tinutukoy ko pa nga, yung kay Hwasa na, to live is an act of courage. So, yeah. And then, i-correlate ko lang siya dun sa getting, ah, get better day by day. Yeah. So, as time, as time goes by, syempre, um, yun, yung

parang, personally, ah, based on experience, kasi nung pandemic, di ba, mostly, down tayo noon, and then, nag-struggle ang bawat isa, and then, so, those lyrics, I think, helped me to go forward. And then, ah, yun, stay to whatever I am right now. So, yun.

Researcher: Okay. So, thank you sa inyong lahat. Tapos na ang ating interview. Thank you so much for participating in, ah, for this research. Thank you.

Interview D: Anna, Merrick, Julia

Researcher: Good evening. I am Airlie Licca Depante. This is for formality's sake. I'm a fourth year Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies na student from UPOU or University of the Philippines Open University. Tapos, as part of my thesis or my MMS 200 special project, I am investigating the influence of Mamamoo's lyrics and music video aesthetics on the fans' impression, appreciation, and or application of feminist beliefs. So, this interview is purely voluntary. You can skip or leave out an answer to any of the questions if you feel uncomfortable. By the way, this is documented since this will be an interview research-based interview. Tapos, you may opt out at any time if you want to, and there are no consequences, so any answers is right. Tapos po, this documented interview will be only heard by me and my thesis advisor. So, ayun po. So, let's start na po. Can you all say your name and age? Tapos, yung gender identity nyo po. Sige, ikaw na lang po.

Merrick: Okay. So, my name is Merrick. I'm 30 years old. Gender identity, she or her.

Researcher: Okay po. Tapos, next po. Ay, ikaw na lang po at ate Arielle.

Anna: Okay. So, my name is Arielle, but you can call me Anna. And, 25 years old, and identified as she or he. She. Her.

Researcher: Okay po. Si ate Julia po.

Julia: Hello, I am Julia Cezanne. I'm 22 years old. I identify as she or her.

Researcher: Okay po. So, ano po yung highest level of educational attainment nyo, tapos work status nyo po? Ikaw na lang po ulit ate Merrick.

Merrick: Um, sigé. Um, bale, I graduated multimedia din sa Mapua. Okay po. Right now, I'm a product designer.

Researcher: Okay po. Tapos, ikaw po ate Arielle. Ah, ate Anna.

Anna: Ano, ah, graduate, college ako. College graduate. Tapos, ah, ah, currently reviewing for boards.

Researcher: Ah, sigé po. At ate Julia?

Julia: 4th year college ako ngayon. Graduating by July. For work. Um, nag-a-apply pa lang naman ako. Pero, I plan to teach. Kasi.

Researcher: Okay po. Thank you po. So, ito po. Ah, how long have you been a Mamamoo fan? In years? Kahit sino na po sa inyo mauna. Okay lang po. Ate Merrick, ikaw na lang po.

Merrick: Um, sigé. Ako, 2016 eh. Eight years.

Researcher: Eight years. Tapos, ate Anna po.

Anna: Ako, six years. Tama ba? Twenty eighteen eh.

Researcher: Ah, six years. Tapos, ate Julia po.

Julia: Tapos, halos sabay lang din kami lahat. Six years din. Okay po.

Researcher: So, ito po. Ah, do you consider yourself a feminist? Were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following Mamamoo? Ah, ate Merrick?

Merrick: Actually, I'm not that familiar before Mamamoo.

Researcher: Okay po. Pero right now, do you consider yourself a feminist or no?

Merrick: Depends. How do you define it?

Researcher: I mean, for you, what is feminism? Like, what is your definition to yourself? Like, do you see it as a form of feminism? Ganun po?

Merrick: I see it as a female empowerment. I'm not sure if that falls under feminism.

Researcher: I think that falls naman po. So, it's okay. If that's your belief, like, do you believe in feminism po? Like, for female empowerment?

Merrick: Yeah, of course. Yeah.

Researcher: Okay po. So, ate Anna, same question. Do you consider yourself a feminist? And were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following Mamamoo?

Anna: So, before Mamamoo, di rin siya very familiar for me. Like, I knew feminism from other perspectives. Like yung mga, more of the, ano, other, hindi siya more of K-pop. Parang ibang, ano, ibang approach, ganun. Pero, now, kasi I see feminism as more of equal rights. Hindi lang yung I'm, like, pro-female, ganun. Pero more of yung equality treatment regarding sa politics and yung mga sahod, ganun. Yun siya. Hindi siya yung, ano siya, more of a general term lang. Hanggang ngayon, ganun.

Researcher: Okay po. Ikaw po, ate Julia.

Julia: Yeah. Actually, familiar na ako with the term. Kasi growing up with PAPs (Psychological Association of the Philippines), ICOTS (International Conference of Teaching Statistics), sulat ni Bob Dylan, ganun naman. Si, I don't know. [Inaudible]. Yun. So, talagang namulat ako. Really aged out. Feminism, equality, tapos yung, yung sa LGBTQ rights. So, yun.

Researcher: Okay po. Ah. Pero, ano, right now, do you consider yourself a feminist or no?

Julia: Ah. Actually, hindi. Pero I'm more of a silent supporter. Kasi...

Researching: Ah, parang kumbaga behind the scenes lang po. Ganun.

Julia: Hindi po yung, parang outspoken, talaga. I would prefer to donate parang, instead na makapagtaban. Ganun.

Researcher: Gets po. So, eto po, um... Ate Merrick, ikaw muna po mag-start. Which five Mamamoo songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?

Merrick: Five Mamamoo songs, correct? Of course, Yes I Am.

Researcher: Pwede ka po mag-search sa Spotify niyo or kahit anong music app niyo right now para lang maalala niyo gano'n. Oo, sige. Ate Merrick, pwede ka po mag-play.

Anna: Ako, gusto mo kong mag-isip muna Ate, pwede ako mauna?

Merrick: Oo, go for it.

Anna: Ako muna. Okay lang po ba yan?

Researcher: Okay lang po, okay lang po.

Anna: Para at least habang nag-iisip sila, kasi ako nag-a-run ako nung question, in-answeran ko na siya noong maaga.

Researcher: Okay po.

Anna: So, yung five songs ng Mamamoo is, wait lang, can I ask if, his also applies din sa ano, yung solo music din? Like solo songs? Or as a group?

Researcher: As a group po talaga eh.

Anna: Okay, okay. Tama pala yung... So, for me, first, yung pinakauna talaga is Hip. Yan, Hip. Then, Egotistic, Rude Boy, Girl Crush, tsaka yung ad song nila, yung Wannabe Myself.

Researcher: Oo, okay po. Sige po.

Anna: Explain ko po ba?

Researcher: Pwede po, kung gusto nyo, okay lang po.

Anna: Sige. So, kasi po yung, sige, short na lang, i-generalize ko na lang silang lima. So, mostly kasi it's about thinking of yourself muna, like you have to treat, parang I

want to love myself. Kasi, yun yung nakita ko, kasi when it comes to, as a, syempre as a woman, parang you have to, ano din, like they have, you know, they have to accept you as you are, as a woman. Not, not as a person na, if ever you're in a relationship na toxic, ganun. Parang, you don't have to please that, the other person. Could be, ano, any gender. Pero, as a woman, you have to think of yourself. Your health din. So, in general, parang loving yourself, yung, ano, parang inano ko siya, in general, summarize ng limang songs na yun. Ayan yung sakin.

Researcher: Oh, okay po. Sige po. Thank you po, Ate Anna. Thank you. Okay po. Ate Julia, ikaw muna siguro po.

Julia: Ano kasi? So, for me, it's the Decalcomanie. Actually, more on aesthetically kasi ito, yun. Nagbabase ako sa music video.

Researcher: Ah, okay lang po.

Julia: Pero, exactly. Yeah. Decacomanie, hip. Tapos, sleep. Sleep in the car. Nakatatlo na ba ako? Tapos, Yes I Am, and yung, okay, isa. Yung Be Calm, para sa akin.

Researcher: Ah, Be Calm. Okay po. Okay, okay. Ah, ano po yung, ano niyo po?

Explanation Or general explanation for those five songs mo.

Julia: Oh my gosh. So, yung Be Calm kasi, for me, hindi kasi magaling magbasa talaga. Parang ang pagkaintindi ko sa kanya is embracing and understanding

yourself before loving someone. Tama nga ba? Yun ata yung message nun. Tapos, yung Yes I Am, parang positivity siya, in general. Oh my gosh. Mahawala natin yung status quo sa mga mga mu-address. Okay. Amali-mali ako na-interpret. Sorry. Tapos, yung Decalcomanie kasi, yung kasi yung una kong napakinggan na kanta. Parang, tapos watching the video, parang, ah wow, may nag-kaya pala nila magsuot ng suits. Samantalang, yung iba, girl group. Sino? Ang cute-cute na. Pero yung original meaning niya, medyo malayo.

Researcher: Okay lang naman po kung sa music video based.

Julia: Tapos, ano na yung sino? Okay. Yung Lisa din. Yung hip. Kasi may mga lyrics siya na, ano e, sabay ka tisyas doon sa issue ni Hwasa, yung punta siya ng, ano, ng airport na di naka bra. Tapos, in-issue ng kay netizens. Yun. So, parang, it's an empowering moment. Kasi kahit nga sa Pilipinas, di ba, pag kinamangon yun, pokpok ka daw.

Researcher: Yung Sleep In The Car po, bakit po yun ang napili niyo?

Julia: Ang Sleep In The Car, actually, funny kasi siya. First time kong nakarinig ng kanta, isang babae na nagre-reklamo na ang hirap-hirap mag-makeup. Kasi di ba, kadalasan sa advertisements, parang, putting on makeup has never been so good. Pero, ayun, sa kanta nila, sobrang nagre-reklamo sila. Natutulog na sila sa kotse, nakapick-up pa, ganun. Parang, as a woman, ay, parang, nagets yung struggles nila.

Researcher: Okay po. Gets. Thank you po. Ate Merrick, ikaw na po.

Merrick: Okay. Anong sinabi ko kanina? Yes, I am.

Researcher: Yes, I am po.

Merrick: So, I think, yeah, yung wanna be myself na. Because, it's talking about being comfortable. Or, parang, loving yourself. And then, yung hip and gogobebe, kinda similar na. Parang, wala akong pakisay ba. Yeah. opo. I just want to express myself and who I am. So, yun lang yung naisip ko. Okay lang ba? Apat lang siya.

Researcher: Okay lang naman po. Okay lang. Okay po. So, as part of mamamoo PH. Ano po yung mga ginagawa niyo sa Mamamoo PH? What activities do you do to support mamamoo? Like, ano po yung position nyo sa mamamoo PH? Ano po yung ginagawa nyo other than sa focusing on the admin group? Like, do you guys buy merchandise? Do you guys stream? Ano pa po? Ikaw muna po, Ate Anna.

Anna: So, ano po. So, yung ginagawa po namin. As a, ano po ba? As a fan? Or as a, ano, fanbase?

Researcher: Ah, kahit both po.

Anna: So, ako po as a fan, bumibili po ako ng merch nila. Pero not really whole. Like, hindi yung bulk buy. Like, kung may spark, ganun. So, ganun. Ah, yun lang. Tapos pagka, ano po, as a fanbase, nag-proproduce kami ng fanmade merch din. Then, kasama na yung, ano po, kasama na po yung, kasama na yung, ano dun, promotion

din ng mamamoo PH. As well yung, ano nga, streaming. Then, we attend events din na K-pop-wide. Then, ano dun, as a fanbase. So, parang, ano po, kayo po yung, parang, nags-spread pa ng information about mamamoo, ganun po? Oo, we share, ganun.

Researcher: Ano po yung position nyo sa mamamoo PH, if I may ask?

Anna: Ako po, ano, SNS head. Ah, okay po. Sige, ikaw na yung boss na. Then, nag-step down ako. Sige, sino na yung head ngayon? Si ate V.J na. Ah. Yeah. So, ano po, kaka, ako po yung, nung MyCon, until recently, ako po yung overall head. Then, nag-step down na ako.] So, nalipat yung isa po na a-attend nung interview nyo po yung overall head. Ah, okay po. Manigay ko na ako.

Researcher: So, ano na lang po, SNS head ka nalang po ngayon?

Anna: Ngayon, oo po. Ah, okay. Sige, thank you po.

Researcher: So, ate Julia, ikaw po?

Julia: Ay sorry.

Researcher: Okay lang po.

Julia: Yung position ko sa mga mga PH, no? Oo po. Well, secretary ako ngayon. Kasi graduating. Okay. So, ano pa? Ganon kasi kami yung segment na

Chismoosa, which is yung parang podcast namin. So, the whole, nagtutok lang kami of a kind of topic, basta related sa mamamoo.

Researcher: Ah, okay po. So, parang podcast nyo po na nagbibigay ng information more about mamamoo. Pero hindi lang siya, ano, sa mamamoo.

Julia: Ah, parang ano rin po, personal rin po, ganon. Parang, halimbawa, may release ang mamamoo, tapos meron kaming side topics na related sa, yun nga, sa feminism, etc. Tapos, ang isa pa naming project, yung talaga favorite kong project, is yung makikipag-partner kami with merchants or local people. Kasi meron kami, dati, nung uso yung community pantry. Yan. Yan yung isang talagang favorite ko na project natin. Although, wala na yun. Hindi man patay. Wala lang kaming contact na doon sa nag-head, si ate Rosalie. Awww. At kaya po ba yung, ano? Ate Rosalie, kasi yung naging...

Researcher: Ay, sorry po. Kaya po ba yung naging head, ay yung ano po, yung parang naging viral na momoland po daw, imbes na mamamoo?

Julia: Oo. Yung tao. Yan yata, yun.

Anna: Ano yun?

Julia: Magpasalamat sila tapos momoland yung pinasalamatan. Hindi mamamoo.

Researcher: So ano po... thank you po, ate Julia. Ikaw po, ate Merrick. Aliping sa giglang tingnan ko.

Merrick: Tumutulong ako sa graphic.

Anna: Subhead.

Merrick: Wala, hindi ako yung head. Subhead nga! Subhead! Subhead? May subhead palag? Subhead.

Anna: Hindi ka. Hindi ka head. Hindi po siya head. Hindi ko mismo yung ano. Siya yung mismo mamamoo itself. Char.

Merrick: Ako po si Moonbyul.

Researcher: Nice to meet you po, Moonbyul. Subhead daw, sabi ni Anna.

Anna: Correct. Siya ang aming vice. Sub.

Researcher: Hindi ko po natanong yung... Ay, sorry po. Ano po yung Subhead po?

Merrick: Subhead sa GFX po, sa graphics. Kasi nagdesign.

Researcher: Ah, okay po. Okay po. Okay po. Thank you for the clarification po. Okay, Ate Julia. So kahit sabay na po kayo ni Ate Merrick, ano po yung ginagawa

niyo as a fan? Like, do you guys stream? Do you guys buy merch? Ano pa po? Like, what do you guys do to support mamamoo itself as a fan?

Julia: Ako, I stream their music. Tapos nangaaway ako ng people sa Twitter. Hindi pala. Formerly Twitter. X na pala siya. Okay po. For them. Tapos ako yung isa sa mga taga-damage control. Pag may issues. Taga-damage control. Ayan.

Researcher: So kayo po yung mga nagre-report ganun?

Julia: Pwede na rin. Pero more on pag-related sa fandom lang. Tapos ako rin yung kumakausap sa ibang partners like PKCI and sa Globe dati.

Researcher: Okay po. Ate Merrick?

Merrick: Ummm... Bali ako... Ay... Binibili ko lahat ng official merch ng mamamoo. Sige, gusto ko. Gusto niyo ba makita?

Anna: Grabe! Nag-flex. Nag-flex. Katabi ko kasi siya.

Researcher: Ang dami ha po.

Merrick: May shrine ako dyan sa kwarto ko. Shrine talaga.

Julia: Grabe. I-flex. On cam! On cam!

Merrick: Pinag-handahan ko talaga to all my life for six years para i-flex to. Ummm... And then I go to concert din. Bali... Yung first concert ko talaga is sa Hong Kong. Yung SWFS pa. And then before... After that, yung MyCon. Tapos pupunta ako kay Wheein. Kung meron lang si Byul, pupunta ako eh. Pero wala na kasing ticket sa Taiwan.

Researcher: So... Pwede po ba paampon?

Merrick: Wala. May tatrabaho lang talaga ako.

Researcher: So... Okay po. Next question. Do you believe that mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? Can you cite cases and examples? Ikaw muna po, ate Anna. Okay. Naniniwala ba kayo na... Naniniwala po ba kayo na mamamoo in style and aesthetics nila nakaka-empower siya sa iba't ibang gender?

Anna: Ummm... Oo. Kasi yung... Ah, examples. Opo.

Researcher: Can you cite cases and examples na empower po?

Anna: Ummm... For me kasi yung more of yung... music videos nila kagaya nung sa Hip na... Parang they were yung mga, ano, different kinds of work na yung iba parang mostly dominant yung lalaki dun sa job na yun. Then, yung parang kay Solar, yung sa part ni Solar, may mga drag queens nakasama siya dun sa band niya. So yun, isa yun. Tapos yung isa yung sa, ano nila, ano ba yan, yung isang, yung isang

ano nila, sa Melon Music Awards nung 2016, meron silang kasama na genderfluid na nakaheels, yung mga lalaki nakaheels na kasama nilang sumayaw. Tapos nakasuit sila that time. So, very evident. Ayan, so, makikita yung versatility nila. Pati kahit outside work, yung pano sila banamit, hindi sila yung laging nakapalda or like nakadress, parang very comfortable sila sa ayan sinusuot nila. Nag-i-encourage dyan na hindi mukhang kailangan magtiis ganda, na sobrang to the point na hindi ka na comfortable to the bit. Para lang to show na ikaw yan. Ayan, for me.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you po Ate Anna. So, Ate Julia?

Julia: Sorry, ano ulit yung question. Sabog talaga ako.

Researcher: Okay lang po. Naniniwala po ba kayo na mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering sa iba't ibang gender?

Julia: Ah, yes, yes. Like yung example ko kanina is yung Decalcomanie. Like, yun yung first music video at saka yung ano, yung Yes I Am. Parang sa Yes I Am parang yung yung cross-dress. Si Moonbyul nga ata. Tama ba? Si Hwasa.

Anna: Yes I Am ba?

Julia: Yes I Am? Oo.

Anna: Or Uhm Oh Ah Yeh?

Julia: Ayun oo. Uhm Oh Ah Yeh. Sorry, sorry. Girl. Girl. I resigned. I resigned.
Dalawa.

Anna: Ay, ah, tatlo sila.

Julia: Dalawa kasi yun.

Anna: Tatlo sila. Si Wheein din.

Julia: Ay, oo nga. O, ayun. May balbas pa. Ay, sorry. Sorry, ha. Matanda na kasi ako.
Hindi ko natanda talagang.

Researcher: Okay lang po.

Julia: Tapos yung sa, ayun nga, sa Decalcomanie, naka male suit sila. Tapos si Solar, meron siyang performance na pinunit niya yung t-shirt niya. Live performance pa yun. Tapos, syempre, kapag idol na lalaki gumawa, wow, so hot. Pag babae, hala laswa. Ganun talaga. At saka yung isang mama performance ni Hwasa na, parang siya si Beyonce, naka red siya na body suit. Syempre, yung iba, ma-issue. Ayun. So, I think, hindi mo nalaga I think, talaga empowering talaga yung sa choices nila ng outfits. Ganun. Eh, kahit, ayun nga, like na-mention kanina, oh my Gosh. I don't
Dami ko sinasabi.

Researcher: Hindi, okay lang po.

Julia: Like na-mention nga kanina. Yung ano, yung outfits sila pag nakikita mo sila in person, parang hindi mo magpagkakama ng idol minsan. Parang mukha lang silang regular na tao. Dahil, yun nga. Dahil, iba nga, iba nga klase lang manamit for you. Ganun po. Yes. Parang kaya mong gayahin.

Researcher: Opo. Okay po. So, Ate Merrick?

Merrick: I think, yeah, kasi one thing, I mean, first thing that comes into my mind, kasi yung lyrics sila. Kasi si Moonbyul yung nagsusulat. Lagi siyang gender-neutral. So, I mean, if the Mamamoo girls is go with that, then of course, lahat sila ganun na parang no matter what their gender is, they want everyone or anyone can relate to their songs and their styles.

Researcher: So, parang do you believe that all of the spectrums of gender can relate to Mamamoo?

Merrick: Yeah. I think, yeah.

Researcher: Paano po siya nakaka-relate sa tingin niyo po?

Merrick: Ah, yun nga. Yung kay, ano, yung how Moonbyul writes her song or their song. Kasi siya siya mostly nagsusulat ng kanta nila eh. So, since it's gender-neutral, so anyone, and regardless of your gender, can relate to it.

Researcher: So, Ate Anna, yun actually yung next question eh. Do you believe that all of the spectrums of gender can relate to Mamamoo?

Anna: Yeah. I think, yeah. there is a uh, Oo, oo po.

Researcher: How so po?

Anna: Ayun nga, so yung... Wait lang, may sagot na ako dyan eh. Ayun, so para... Yun nga, parang kasi parang ano yung sinabi po nila kanina, nakaka-relate sila, yung gaya nung sinabi ni Ate Merrick po kanina, na yun nga, parang they write, si Moonbyul, nagsusulat sila ng lyrics, mostly gender neutral. So parang hindi siya, pag kinanta ng isang lalaki yung kanta nila, okay lang kasi hindi naman, parang wala siyang specific na gender na sinasabi, more of you, more of yung they, ganun. Hindi siya more of she, he, ganun. Tapos, ayun din, as you can see kasi yung mga damit din nila, lalo na ni Moonbyul siya, tsaka ni Wheein, branded siya pero mostly kasi parang lalaki yung nagsusuot. So parang nagugulat yung mga tao, uy, ayun pang babae palang ganyan na damit or like, uy, bagay pala sa babae. So parang naisip din na parang hindi lang siya limited na kahit ano yung ginagawa ng mama mo, parang nakaka-relate din yung mga, hindi lang lala, hindi lang mga babae pero pati yung ibang spectrums like kasi medyo ano din sila supportive din, nakikita din sa gawa nila yung support nila. For the, for the ano, LGBT. So, ganun din. Nakikita din kasi sa music video. Yun pala, yun yung gusto ko din sabihin. Yung music video nila, like yung ano, yung sa, yes, ah, ano yun, nakawa talaga ako. Uhm Oh Ah Yeh. Tapos yung ano ni Moonbyul, yung, ano yun? Yung kanta ni Moonbyul, oh my gosh, I'm a fake fan din. Bias ko na nga. Yung ano, Shut Down. So, ayun din. Tapos, ah,

ano pa, meron pang isa eh. Yung ano, hindi, mas makikita mo kasi dun sa Shut Down compared dun sa isa niya, yung Absence, saka yung Guchahe (Love & Hate). Mas alam ko ang Korean niya, kesa sa English. Pero mostly kasi ako makikita ko kay Moonbyul kasi, kasi bias ko kasi siya. So, ano, ganun. Ayun. Makikita sa music video as well yung pananamit. So, ano yung pananamit nila and how they write their lyrics and, ayun, yun yung summary nung sinabi kong lahat ng haba.

Researcher: Okay lang po. Thank you po. So, Ate Julia, ano naman po?

Julia: Um, yes. Yes.

Researcher: How so po?

Julia: Sabi na nila eh. Pero yes. Well, yun, paraphrase ko na lang. Ah, siges po. Ayun. So, sa performance kasi, dito naman natin. Iinvite siya or like may mga kasama siyang mag-perform na, yun nga, members of the LGBTQ plus community, tapos meron pa silang mga cultural aspects na dina-dive into, tapos yun, for everyone siya kasi yung name kasi nila, actually, medyo obvious naman na nakakatawa. So, syempre, may mga narinig kasi akong mga lalaki. So, syempre ka rin yung mga students ko, ano, ayun. Pag narinig kasi nila, ah, ma'am, nakikinig ka pala sa mama mo po, eh di nanay mo yung ang gagawin. Mag-joke silang, yun, tapos mamaya, seasearch nila, magugusto nila yung mga katatagal. So, at the same time, yun. So, yes.

Researcher: Okay lang po. Sige, next question po. Um, so, how do mamamoo's lyrics on various song empower different genders? So, ate Anna, ikaw muna po.

Anna: Hindi ata nasagot ni ate Merrick yung previous question mo. Ay, di ba? Or, okay. Ay, parang nasagot po siya.

Researcher: Nasagot po siya. Oo, nakonnect niya po sa isang question.

Anna: Okay, okay. So, ano yung next question? Yung lyrics? Oo. Various song. Ano? Ano? Yan. How, on various songs empower different genders? So, ah, ah, yung sa akin kasi, ah, like yung kanina na sinabi ko, yung empowerment nga, ah, yung sa lyrics nila. Ano nga ba? At, yun nga, yung kagaya nung sa hip na, yung part ni Hwasa na, yung, yung bridge niya. Ako. Yung kahit nakalabas yung panty. Okay, sorry. Pero ganun yung lyrics niya, yung very, ano, hindi nila sinisensor yung lyrics nila. Yung confidence nila na, ano, ah, yun nga, di ba, parang narilis yung hip kasabay nung airport fashion ni Hwasa yun, maka, ano nga, makabukas yung botones nung pants. Yeah. So, parang, yun nga eh, ganun siya. Parang, you don't have to, ano, like, let's...Let there be, like, let there be bashers, pero, ano, yung belief mo sa sarili mo, best as long as you're comfortable with what you're wearing, saka, or, ano, kung ano yung ka, ganun. Parang, ikaw yung may-ari ng sarili mo, so, wag mo siya, wag mo hayaan yung ibang tao yung mag-define sa'yo kung sino ka dapat, ganun.

Researcher: Okay, po. Ay. Okay, po.

Anna: Kailangan po ba ng specific lyrics?

Researcher: Okay. Kahit hindi na po baggatin, okay lang po. Kaya, sabihin niya lang po yung kanta, okay lang po. Thank you, po. Ate Julia, po.

Julia: Yung question. Ano, po? Sorry. Sorry. Ano yung ulit yung question? Sorry.

Researcher: Okay lang po. Okay lang po. How do Mamamoo's lyrics on various songs empower different genders? Ah. Ah, ayun.

Julia: Kasi, yung gender, ah, mali. Yung song lyrics kasi na, if mapapansin niyo, hindi sila kuma, ano na, halimbawa, like, tell me you love me, boy, walang ganun-ganun. Like, hindi sila specific. Like, kung kinakanta nila yung mga ganun-ganun lyrics, sabihin nila, tell me, ganun-ganun. Tell me love. Kumbaga, hindi sila nag-ano, nagsistick to one, ano, stick to one gender. So, ayun. I think nakaka-relate yung mga tao on that part. Kasi, isipin mo, di naman sa number one siya ako. My gosh, love kita, Hyolyn. Pero, oh, bad boy. Diba? Isipin mo, may isip mo, para siya sa bad boy. Oo nga po, lalaki lang. Aba, sabagi. Kung, halimbawa, ano lang yun. Or yung sa Red Velvet, yung really bad boy, para sa lalaki. Oo. So, para, at the same time, yung mga tao, ako kasi ganun, ako kasi ganun. Parang, nahihirapan akong makarelata sa kanta kung dedicated lang siya sa isang person or gender. Kumbaga, mas okay siya kung specific.

Researcher: Ah, okay. So, kung, pag hindi po siya parang specific, nakaka-empower rin po siya para sa'yo?

Julia: Ah, oo. Kasi, at the same time, may inclusivity na nangyayari. Kahit hindi sila aware. Diba?

Researcher: Opo.

Julia: Para, tapos may, ano nga. May mga parts doon sa lyrics kasi na nagpo-focus din na love yourself muna, unahin yung sarili, ganun. Or, simply as, ano, take time. Ano yung take things slow, time will, ano, be good to you. Yun. So, at the same time, parang nagbibigay na sila ng advice. Not just empowerment, pero ayun. Parang, parang pag nangyayari rinig mo kasi yung music nila, parang may yung mayangakas na yun. Ina-ano ka sa likod. Pinatapit ka. Sabihin kaya mo yan. Ika.

Researcher: Oo, okay po. So, parang nakaka-uplift po talaga siya, ganun.

Julia: Yes.

Researcher: Okay po. So, Ate Merrick, ikaw naman po.

Merrick: Luh. Nabanggit na nila eh. I think I have to agree with everyone na, ano, usually kasi wala talagang specific, specific gender yung kanta nila, unless, I mean, unless talagang specifically that song was, ano, was catered to a specific gender. So, parang, most of their songs, wala talagang a girl or boy or him or her. So, as far as I can remember, kaunti lang na may songs nila na merong gender-specific.

Researcher: Oo nga. Wala po. Uh, can you name a song na parang inisip ninyo pong gender-specific siya?

Merrick: Hmm. You're a girl. You're a girl. Oo, you're a girl. Girl crush. You're a girl.

Anna: Rude Boy ka ganun. Oo nga, girl crush. Oo nga, girl crush. Naisip ko lang, shut down. Pero she's not there. May she ba doon?

Researcher: May she po.

Merrick: Ay, oo nga pala, she said. Oo nga, no. Oh my gosh. Ano, yung, okay, never mind. Okay po.

Researcher: So, um, para sa inyo po, sa tingin nyo po, ano po yung concept po nila, music video, stage performance, stage aesthetics, na napakita nila na napaka-importante para ma-empower ang ibang genders. Ikaw po muna ate Anna

Anna: Actually nasabi na kanina ni Julia kasi naisip ko nung nabasa ko yung question yung kay Solar kasi yung reason niya kung ba't nilip yung t-shirt niya kasi is why boys do it always on their concerts or stages pero walang babaeng gumagawa yun nga ginawa niya yun nga, syempre na-criticize siya pero ang dami din nung pumuri sa kanya so ayun isa yun sa anon nila, yung isa yun, sa music video yun, yung para kanina, yung hip pa rin ganun din, ulit lang then yung concept is ka-concept din kasi yun sa ano ba yun din, sa ano, ang Uhm Oh Ah Yeh kasi kahit yung stages nila parang, kasi may isang stage nila naalala ko like music show

parang nagpapalit sila ng damit pero isang stage lang parang nakasutot tapos may nagpapalit sila ng dress nila na iba-ibang kulay ayan kaya yun sa akin.

Researcher: Thank you po ah ikaw po ate Julia.

Julia: Yung sa stage nila, ayun, yung na-mention ko nga kanina yung kay Solar po yung oo tapos ano, I would like to add din isa sa mga performances ni Solar yung pagpo-pole dancing kasi ano parang nagawa niya ata yun din live tsaka malam talaga siya wala kang makikita ang mga idols na I mean meron naman pero yung iper-perform nila ano? yun parang yung performance niya ng Cleopatra ata yun sa Mama ah po, n Mama nga ba yun?

Researcher: ah opo, tama yun parang siya po kasi daw nagsimula so parang she broke the barrier do you believe that po?

Julia: oo kasi diba ang pole dancing daw ay associated with sex work gano'n ah po yun, you get the point naman tapos yung isa, yung Kaiwasa yung na-mention ko yung nagmala Beyoncé siya ah po parang siya yung isa sa mga risky yung suot nun yung naka-body suit lang siya, wala siyang safety shorts unlike yung ibang mga idols kasi kapag, oo nagba-body suit sila pero alam mo yun, yun yung may patong talaga sa loob yung alam mo, naka-palda, may safety shorts, gano'n o kaya naka-shorts in general ah po yun, parang kaya nga no, compare siya with Beyoncé at that time Mama performance din yun.

Researcher: Okay po so, thank you po ah ikaw po ate Merrick?

Merrick: ano ulit yung tanong?

Researcher: Ah what concept, music videos, or stage, and or stage aesthetics mamamoo has presented na importante pag ine-empower ang iba't ibang gender

Merrick: Ah I think kaya yung katulad kay nga yun don sa Uhm Oh Ah Yeh na nagpapalit sila ng costume ah po and then, on the top of my head ang naalala ko lang si Solar yun, nag-suot siya ng suit tapos, I think, naka-bra lang siya sa loob ah, I think it's caters to all gender kasi it's both masculine and feminine then, I guess is more of mamamoo aren't afraid to wear suits or dress, whatever parang hindi naman sila specific to like only wearing dresses or just wearing suit

Researcher: so, parang androgynous po sila para sa iyo yun?

Merrick: Mhm, parang I think, I mean, what I can see is that they don't think the way they, they don't believe that clothes define your gender kumbaga.

Researcher: Thank you po, thank you po I would like to add din pala ay, okay ka po, go

Julia: kasi si Moonbyul may performance sila po As a whole naman, as a whole. Sa Queendom, parang meron silang solo parts. Tapos si Moonbyul, parang naka-leash, naka-dog collar yung mga ano niya. Yung backup dancers niya, sa part niya. So ayun, empowering siya. Kasi yung mga lalaki, di joke ka. So, first time mo rin talaga makikita ng gano'n.

Researcher: Okay po. Lalo na po pag K-pop idol, no?

Julia: Yes.

Anna: Tsaka babae pa.

Yes. Okay po. So, eto next question po. What issues of feminism have been highlighted by mamamoo that help you see feminism in a different light? Ano po mga issues ng feminism na na-highlight ng mamamoo na nakatulong sa'yo na makita ang feminism sa ibang perspective? So, ikaw po. Ate Anna muna.

Anna: Siguro for me, hindi siya technically na makikita as a feminist action. Pero feeling ko, as a person na, siguro like, someone na hindi confident. Kagaya ng ano, yung mga ad-libs nila nung decalcomanie era nila. Parang, diba parang, si Moonbyul kasi mostly yun eh. Yung tinatanong nila yung mga actors or like yung mga tao sa audience na mga lines dun sa ano, sa mga series. Alam niyo yun? Nalala niyo yun? Yung, gusto mo bang uminom? Gano'n. Like, alam niyo yun po.

Ayan. Kung naalala niyo yung mga gano'n. Ah, kasi mostly parang yinayaya. Do you wanna date me? Gano'n. Like, for me kasi. Parang, parang sa ano kasi natin. Parang, hindi siya normal na yung babae yung umaamin muna dun sa lalaki. Or like, if it's the same gender, gano'n. Parang ano siya, awkward, gano'n. Diba madalas kasi yung lalaki yung, ano, nanliligaw, gano'n. So, for me, malaking step yun na it's okay na yung babae yung unang. Nag-move ng, ano, ng interest. So, parang, ako kasi, kapag gano'n kasi ako. Parang, pag gusto ko yung tao, medyo

minsan shy ako. Pero, nagbibigyan ako ng parang motivation. Ay, motivation? Motive pala. Like, ano, nag-giving sign. Na may, maraming gusto ako sa kanya.

Researcher: Okay po. Thank you po. Ah, sige po. Ate Julia?

Julia: Um, ano po mo yung, ayun. So, medyo in general naman to. Hindi naman siya considered na feminist talaga. Pero more on body positivity. And yung sa way of clothing. Ayun, diba nga, like, mention kanina si Hwasa, nagpunta ng airport, walang bra, gano'n. O kaya, yung dun sa hip nga. Yung lyrics niya na, kahit kita yung panty niya, dead ma lang. Eh, ano. Tapos, dun sa music video din na, hip. Merong, ano, parang, placard. Meron doon part kasi si Wheein na, isa siyang protester. Basta yung overall message kasi nung kanta. Parang, women can be anything they want. Who they want, gano'n. Any shape, size, gano'n. As long as they know what they're doing. As long as masaya sila. Ayun.

Researcher: Okay. Any additional po, or yun lang naman po, so far?

Julia: Yun lang.

Researcher: Okay po. So, ikaw po, Ate Merrick?

Merrick: Ano ulit yung tanong? Sorry.

Researcher: Okay lang po. Ano po mga issues ng feminism na na-highlight ng mama mo, na nakita mo feminism in a different light?

Merrick: Sige. I guess, one thing is, I remember yung dun sa fan na nagsabi. Ay, nag-ask ng weight loss tips kay Hwasa. Hindi ko maalala yung exact reply, pero parang sabi lang niya na, parang, ano nga ba yung reply niya? Basta, dinisregard niya eh.

Researcher: Parang... Kumain ka lang po?

Merrick: Parang sabi niya gano'n. Parang gano'n ata. Hindi ko sure yung exact term eh. Pero parang gano'n. Kasi, syempre, as Hwasa, she doesn't care about her body weight. Or, kung ano, I mean, she's very confident with her body. And then, kay Moonbyul naman, I guess, the general of breaking the gender norms. Parang, she's not afraid. To wear, kunwari, yung traditional male clothes and such. So, parang, di ba controversial yan dun?

Researcher: Opo.

Merrick: And then, I guess, I can say yung kay Solar din. Yun dun sa pag-rip-off ng clothes, which I don't know. I guess, controversial din. Pero, parang, it's kinda unfair kasi na bakit nga naman kapag lalaki, pwede. At kapag babae, hindi. And then, kay Wheein? Um, I think I remember dun sa, um, MV, was it? Or, parang, prologue ng kanta niya, yung Goodbye.

Researcher: Ah, ano po. Oh, yes. MV.

Merrick: Yes. Oo. Parang, hindi ko maalala kung ano yung exactly na sinabi niya. Pero, pagkakalala ko, kasi sinabi na dun na, parang, it doesn't matter what gender is. So, parang, yan.

Researcher: Oh, parang, love is love ganun po.

Merrick: Mm-hmm. Same as Moonbyul, yan.

Researcher: Mm. Okay po. So. Ito po. Last two questions na po. Sorry po talaga sa tagal. Um, do you see that over time, Mamamoo's song, lyrics, and music videos have helped you understand feminism better? Ikaw po, ate Anna?

Anna: Mm. Oh, yeah.

Researcher: Uh, how so po?

Anna: Uh, I can't remember. Wait, ano question? Do you see that over time, Mamamoo's song, lyrics?

Researcher: Ayan po. Ayan po.

Anna: Second to the last, no?

Researcher: Ayan po.

Anna: Ah, ayan. Yes. Kasi, yun nga, like, what I mentioned. Parang, they give you confidence. Like, uh, example kasi, yun, hindi mo kailangan maging, makipagsabayan sa norm ng mga tao. Like, you can do, like, you have your own pace of exploring the world or your, you know. Kung saan ka comfortable. Hindi mo kailangan tumabay kung ano yung trendy. Like, you, ano, yun nga, parang, sabi ni Hwasa, I am the trend. Diba? Parang, kung ano yung, ano, ako to. Like, kung ano yung gusto ko sautin, ganun ako. And, ano, kung ano, kung saan ako comfortable, then, parang, that's what will, ano, kung ano yung po follow ko. Diba? Okay. So, for me, that's feminism. Like, everything is easy. So, ano po? Okay po. May follow up question mo?

Researcher: Hindi po. Baka may i-add pa po kayo kung ganun.

Anna: Okay na po ako dun.

Researcher: Okay po. So, Ate Julia, ikaw po.

Julia: So, actually, oo. I, it has helped me understand feminism. Pero siyempre hindi siya yung pinaka exact definition nga. Since the internet is full of information. Mabagang naging beacon. Naging beacon ang mamamoo for feminism. Mas naging accepting ngayon ng mga K-netizens compared sa iba. Simulan na lumabas yung mamamoo. Pero may pagka-OA pa din naman sila. Pero konti na lang.

Researcher: Parang you think na mamamoo has paved the way?

Julia: Oo.

Researcher: Okay po. So Ate Merrick?

Merrick: Ano yung tanong? Sorry.

Researcher: Do you see that over time mamamoo's song lyrics and music video aesthetics have helped you understand feminism better?

Merrick: Oh yeah, definitely. Kasi ano bang mga unang kanta na mamamoo? Mr. Ambiguous.

Researcher: Mr. Ambiguous.

Merrick: O diba? Nag-start sila ng hindi ano eh. Puro lalaki. Nag-start sila ng hindi female empowerment. And then I think nag-start lang siya sa, what was it? Yes I Am I guess? And then over time parang slowly nag-build up sila ng mga confidence song. And then parang typically kasi yung mga kanta nila or yung mga I guess ginagawa nila is based from an issue. So parang siyempre ako hindi naman ako masyadong updated. So parang some issues na I thought na parang since standard siya or norm siya na pwede pala yun.

For example, kay Solar nag-rip ng shirt. So parang naisip ko eh pwede pala yun. And then I guess na actually na-influence din ako ng mamamoo. Kasi before I wasn't really wearing parang mga crop tops and all. So parang slowly nung na-discover ko yung mama mo and then parang na-influence din ako. Based from

how they, um, paano sila manamit. Like some clothes na I thought na hindi pala or parang I guess hindi okay or hindi norm or parang maja-jujudge ko. Pero over time parang na-influence ako na to wear it. Parang okay wala akong paki. So parang yeah. That was the impact of it.

Researcher: So parang in a way po, parang nagkaroon ka rin ng self-feminism in a way?

Merrick: Like I gain confidence na about things na pwede pala or more of like I don't get restricted because of them.

Researcher: Okay po. So last question po. Um, what specific lyric or aesthetic, whether it be from a music video or their stage performance, of mamamoo nspires you and why? So ate Anna, ikaw po.

Anna: Um, naisip ko pa. Nagiisip ako.

Researcher: Okay lang po.

Anna: Uh, meron, siguro for me yung ano nila. Yung sa mama, yung kasama nila si JYP. 2019 po. Yan. Yan yung, kasi lahat sila doon naka-green na parang joker. Basta yung joker vibe sila. Mostly ganun. So parang kasi, ah, hindi naman sa med, yung ano, anong tawag dito, hindi naman sa na-inspire ako to do the same. Pero na-inspire ako to be more like, ah, colorful for me. Kasi black siya tsaka, pero may neon. Parang contrast. Parang bright kasi yung neon, yung green. Then black yung

damit nila. So, tapos tight pa. So parang ako kasi, mostly damit ko kasi is black or white lang. So parang ako, nung napanood ko yun, parang, parang nakita ko yung, pwede pala yung ganun na color combination na hindi lang kailangan, monotonous lang yung color mo. Pero you can mix colors with bright and dark colors.

So, ayun. So ngayon, parang mas naging confident na dinausap pa na damit ko as well as yung confidence ko to interact with people na, with a different gender. Like, kasi ako talaga, from the very start, it's like, one of the boys. Pero introverted ako ganun. Parang sa dun sa flow nila sa stage na yun, kasi yung camera nila dun iba't iba rin, parang pag di ka kasi fan at tinignan mo siya parang ang gulo. Parang nagpapan ang camera dito tapos si Moonbyul nasa chair bababa siya so bilang fan nasa iyo na yun kung pano interpret yung stage nila. So ayun nainspire ako to be more confident as a person na introvert dati. Medyo nag open na ako to step up to lead something, ako na nagiinitiate ng gawa, so naging initiate ng ako ng gawa kesa maghihintay ng gawa.

Researcher: So kaya po pala kayo naging boss sa MAMAMOO PH.

Anna: Wala po akong choice charot di na ako boss. So ganun din naging inspiration ko sa kanila. Sa MAMA 2019, yun kay JYP.

Researcher: Ate Julia, Ikaw po?

Julia: Pwede ba interview?

Researcher: Pwede naman po parang stage performance nila.

Julia: Ah okay, parang stage performance naman mila. Kasi nagkaroon sila ng interview sa K-CON MTV. Kumbaga din describe nila ni Hwasa as a concept ng group nila is "Woman". So dun palang parang may Feminist na sila, inexplain naman ni Solar parang lyrics nila nainspire sila sa mga babae na nagsasabi na ang lyrics daw nila parang naging source of strength tapos ayun, parang its literally Women empowering women, katulad sa hip at yes I am.

Specifically sa hip, parang sinasabi nila na women can literally want what they want tapos sa yes I am is self-acceptance and love tapos yung isang kanta ni wheein, yung goodbye niya although solo, napoportray siya na lesbian relationship yung mv niya, so very empowering. So ayun.

Researcher: Okay po, thank you po Ate Julia. Ate Merrick?

Merrick: Actually ako favorite ko talaga is wanna be myself, yung lyrics kasi talaga parang no standard, everyone is equal like wala parang whatever I do or whatever I wear its still me. So ayun.

Researcher: Okay, so thank you all for participating in this interview, this will be extremely helpful for me for my research po.

Interview E: V.J. (Vanya) and Jason (Frey)

Researcher: So, good day. I am A Ariel Depante, a 4th year Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies. I am from University of the Philippines Open University. This specific research is part of my course requirements in my special project or thesis. I am investigating the influence of Mamamoo's lyrics and music video aesthetics on the fans' suppression, appreciation, and other application of feminist beliefs. So, as always, you can opt out of this interview. This interview is purely voluntary and you can skip or leave out an answer if you don't feel confident or uncomfortable to do so. You are allowing me to record your answers for data analysis purposes and this data analysis will only be heard by me and my thesis advisor. So, first of all, I just want to ask for your demographics, your name, age, gender identity, level of educational attainment, and work status. How long have you been a Mamamoo fan? Anyone can start. It's okay.

Jason: Hello, I'm Jason. Is it okay just the first name?

Researcher: It's okay.

Jason: Jason, I'm 28 years old. gender identity...I'm a straight, cis-het male. Okay, po. And then, highest level of educational attainment is bachelor's degree. Currently, I'm an employee and I've been a fan of Mamamoo for four years.

Researcher: Four years, po. Okay, next po si Ate Vanya. Ate Vanya?

V.J.: Hi. You can call me VJ or Vanya. It's not a big thing, but... Tapos, I'm 25 years old. Di lang halata. Hindi ako nag-college, pero graduate ako ng senior high. Okay. Tapos, I'm currently working as a data analyst. And then, um, I've been a fan of Mamamoo since debut nila nila. So, ano na, magta-ten years na rin.

Researcher: Ooh, okay po. So, ano pa yung gender identity niyo, if I may ask?

V.J.: Oo, yun, nakalimutan ko po. Um, gender fluid.

Researcher: Ah, okay po. So, let's proceed to the interview itself na po talaga. So, first of all po, do you consider yourself a feminist? And were you familiar with feminism before leaving? Or listening to or following Mamamoo? At si Kuya Jason na lang po muna.

Jason: Ay, sorry. Yes, yes. Sorry, sorry. Nakamute pa pala. Yes. May isa. Ano po? Sorry po. Yes. Sorry, sorry. Do you consider yourself a feminist? Yes. Were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following Mamamoo? Yes. So, for you, what is feminism po? Yes. For me, feminism is a movement acknowledging that there are marginalized communities based on several socio-economic factors, one of them being gender. Feminism believes that through women empowerment and programs targeting marginalized sectors, it will be easier to achieve humanity's full potential in nation-building. So, in line with that, ano po yung...five Mamamoo songs in your opinion that are about empowerment. Yeah, yeah. For me, it's Wannabe Myself, Yung Hip, Wind Flower, Egotistic, tsaka Gogobebe.

Researcher: May I ask why specifically Wind Flower?

Jason: Yan ba yung wind flower? Hindi ako prepared. May part kasi sa lyrics nito. for me, yung get better day by day, medyo ano siya, parang ano siya, maganda siyang mantra. Actually, regardless naman, pero especially for women, siguro, na yeah, it has to be, parang you have to be better for yourself and not for other people.

Researcher: Okay po. Thank you po, ate V.J?

V.J.: Luh yung sagot niya, hindi ko alam paano ko susundan.

Researcher: Okay lang po, take your time po.

V.J.: Yes, I consider myself a feminist. Anong follow-up question mo dun?

Researcher:: Were you familiar with feminism before listening to or following Mamamoo?

V.J.: Yes, I am familiar before I became a fan. Tapos, kasi unang K-pop group ko talaga is Girls' Generation, so ayun.

Researcher: So, with that, for you, what is feminism po?

V.J.: Just to put it simply, equality, especially for women.

Researcher: Okay po. So, which five Mamamoo songs, in your opinion, are about empowerment?

V.J.: Almost the same din kay Frey (Jason). Tapos, parang pinaka-ina-associate ko na ka, with doon, is hip.

Researcher: Hip po talaga?

V.J.: Yes.

Researcher: Okay po. So, next question po. What activities do you do to support Mamamoo? Like, do you guys buy merch, stream, watch videos? Tapos, ano po yung position nyo in Mamamoo PH? Kuya Jason.

Jason: Okay. Yeah. Sa na yun. Oh, yeah. So, I buy merchandise. I stream. Tapos, I watch concerts din. Tsaka, mostly word of mouth. Convinced na mag-convert tayo ng mga hindi pa sila naririnig. Tapos, ang position mo ko sa ano ko, sa tech. At tsaka, more on tech ako, pero I do all around logistics stuff.

Researcher: Okay po. Next kay Ate VJ.

V.J.: Anong nga, ulit yung tanong?

Researcher: Okay lang po. What activities do you do to support Mamamoo? And what is your position in Mamamoo PH?

V.J.: Usually, nanonood ng contents nila. Ganyan, bumibili din ng album. Tapos, pupunta lang ng concert last year and nung, ano, concert ni Wheein. Tapos, ano din, nag-convert din ng mga non-fan. Hehe. Tapos, ang position ko sa Mamamoo Philippines is all around. But, ngayon, I'm acting as the head.

Researcher: Ooh, okay po. Parang yung word of mouth po, parang kulto po tayo. Next question po. Do you believe that Mamamoo in style and aesthetics is empowering for various genders? Can you cite cases and examples, if yes?

Jason: Yes, for me. Yung say, for example, they have different occupations. Some of them, supposedly, you know, in our society, supposedly, for men. Pero, they're they are women wearing, they are women representing, ano, different occupations. Tapos, yung Uhm Oh Ah Yeh, which is, parang may ang dami lang inirepresent na mga people. Alam mo yun, not necessarily glamorous. Not necessarily glamorous. Kasi, di ba, maraming maraming music videos, so, puro pacute lang yung ginagawa ng mga groups. Pero, sila, they're, they're open to throwing different types of people, kahit yung hindi, kahit yung supposedly embarrassing type ng mga tao. And then, yung for me, yung teletubbies, kahit it was a miscommunication, kumbaga they were confident enough of themselves, and they and they're supportive of each other. Bilang apat silang babae. It's really, it's really big na, you know, di nagiiwanan on that matter. So, yeah.

Researcher: Thank you po, Kuya Jason. Ate VJ?

V.J.: Um, empowering kasi yung mamamoo eh. So, yung confidence nila nakakahawa, gano'n. So, ako kasi, simula nung di pa fan ako, di ako gano'n kaka-confident sa sarili ko ganyan. Tapos, simula nung naging fan ako, parang nahawa ako sa kanila. Parang na-inspire ako na magtiwala sa sarili ko ganyan, mahalín yung sarili ko.

So, [...] they became my role model in life. Basically. So, especially si Hwasa, ano, she doesn't care, ano man sabihin ng ibang tao about her. Pero, she still show her true self, ganyan. She doesn't want to pretend as anybody. Also, si Solar din. Ang dami-daming ginagawa. Ang dami-daming alam na skills ni Solar, na usually, yung, um, mga stereotypical things, like, babae ka, so, ito lang yung pwedeng gawin, ito rin kaya man gawin. Pero, she always prove them wrong. So, ayun. So, kung baga po, parang yung iba't-ibang genres, iba't-ibang styles nila, parang nakaka-influence sa inyo po. Napaka-diverse kasi talaga nila.

Researcher: Next question, do you believe that all spectrums of gender can relate to mama mo, and how so?

V.J.: Yes.

Researcher: How so po?

V.J.: Ikaw ba muna, Frey?

Jason: Yes. For me kasi, as a group, they have been transparent about their challenge, ayun, they have been transparent about their challenges as individuals

and as a group. Tapos, yung music kasi nila, they're heavily involved. So, alam mo yung iba yung dating, for me as a fan, iba yung dating na they personally write their music. It's really something from them, hindi lang yung pinasulat lang from the producers. Tapos, yung ganung feeling kasi, regardless, sa spectrum mo, regardless kung ano, you will relate dun sa pinagdaanan nila, yung mga challenges, yung mga challenges, at saka yung base yung mga challenges nila as women and as supposedly non-conventionally attractive in terms of the Korean standard, diba? So, very relatable siya. Especially in the context of, well, in the context of Korea. Tapos, yun nga, in general, makaka-relate ka talaga at some point. Kung ano yung challenge.

Researcher: Do you think po, outside of Korea, nakaka-relate pa rin po sila?

Jason: Yes. Yes. Kasi may overlap naman.

Researcher: Ate V.J.?

V.J.: Yes din sagot ko. Kasi they inspire millions of people na nakakakita sa kanila. And just like, tinabi nila niya nun, based on each individual in the group, they represent a lot of people. Kahit anong gender mo pa, kahit anong klaseing tao ka pa. Kasi they came from the bottom and now look at them. So, they know the struggle and they use that in creating their own music. Using art as a form of telling a story. Telling their story to inspire millions of people. So, yes.

Researcher: Thank you po. Next question po. How do Mamamoo's lyrics on various songs empower different genders? So, Kuya Jason nalang po.

Jason: For me, it's pinakaano is representation. And for me, very important yung marami silang tinatry, marami silang tinatry na genre, marami silang tinatry na colors, marami silang tinatry na concepts. And that in itself, they're able to show that they can be just more than something that the society expects them to be. More than that pa sila. So, specifically parang yung lyrics po nila, parang it, ano rin po,

Researcher: It empowers different gender?

Jason: Yes.

Researcher: So, how do you believe so po?

Jason: Kasi, okay, so may mga, may mga, maraming ano siya eh, sorry, their songs promote someone who knows her worth and goes beyond societal expectations. So, yun, this is aside from the fact that mamamoo has been a role model for a lot of people. So, so yun palang yung, for me, very big deal na yung part na alam nila yung worth nila. And alam nila na they shouldn't just base themselves dun sa expectations na kanilang society. It's para, you know, they can be there more, para they're encouraging people to be more authentic and sincere on who they really are.

Researcher: Thank you po. Ah, ayun nga po, Ate VJ.

V.J.: Yes, I agree sa sagot ni Frey. Kasi ano eh, they promote uniqueness. Ganon. So, since napaka-diverse na ng lyrics nila, and it applies to all genders, kahit alien ka pa, it applies to you. Makarelate ka. Kaya naging role model ko sila kasi they aspire me to believe in myself. So...

Researcher: So, parang how does it inspire you in a way? Parang it helps you become more confident na e-empower ka through their lyrics po talaga?

V.J.: Yung self-esteem mo nabubooast while listening to their music. Kasi hindi lang, the way they write their song is not just for the sake na magkaroon ng meaning yung lyrics ng music nila, but they tell different stories eh. That they can use as inspiration to become the better version of you. So, yun yung nagustuhan ko sa kanila as an artist. Hindi lang nila ginagamit yun for themselves, but to inspire others din.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you po. So, What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other genders? Kuya Frey?

Jason: Sorry, paulit yung question.

Researcher: Ah, What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other genders?

Jason: Ito pala yung ano. Ito yung representation yung sagot. Yung representation, yung colors, different concepts, different genres, very important for me. Ayan. It's

just, ano eh. At some point, sa dami ng kanta nila, sa dami ng concept na triny nila, at some point, it's going to be really, really, it's going to hit different, depende sa person eh. Kasi iba yung relate level sa specific na song, for example.

Researcher: So, on your mind, on top of your mind po, ano pong naisip niya na present na po nila na parang, ah, nakaka-ano to, nakaka-empowered? As a male moomoo, ganun po.

Jason: For me talaga, it's, it's, yung nga, we go back to sa sagot ko kanina eh. Yung self-worth talaga. Very important nang nakakumunicate yun sa kanta. Kasi as we know, as we know yung ibang music kasi natin they tend to be more on parang consumerist. Parang you have to, you have to spend so much money to look good. You have to. You have to put on this much too much makeup to look good. Parang ganun, parang they're describing how you should be when in fact you can just do things because you want to. I think yun yung isa sa mga nakukuha ko dun sa music mo lang na they want to do this, they do this because they want to and then even if it's not expected of them.

Researcher: Okay po.

Jason: Nagets ba?

Researcher: Nagets po. Thank you po. Ate VJ?

V.J.: Paulit po ng tanong.

Researcher: What concepts, music videos, and stage aesthetics Mamamoo has presented that are most important when empowering other genders?

V.J.: Ayun, when it comes to stage aesthetics, ano eh, so sobrang dami concept tsaka ideas na ginagawa nila kasi super diverse talaga silang prasagot. So applicable siya sa lahat. Like yung Four Seasons Four Colors nung concert nila, they wear suits and they also wear dresses. Tapos there's one instance na sabi Solar, bakit ano, usually sa mga concerts, nagtutopless yung mga lalaki, di ba bakit hindi nila kayang gawin, hindi ba nila kayang gawin yan? So they, she proved to people that she can do that as well, ganon. To promote equality, ganon. To empower yourself, tapos embrace your wilderness and uniqueness. Hindi yung i-hide mo lang yung sarili mo kasi natatakot ka sa masasabi ng ibang tao. Sa'yo, you have to embrace yourself. And pakita mo sa mundo kung sino ka, ganon. So usually, they do that by presenting different ideas and aesthetics usually sa stage performances nila. Sobrang bongga nilang mag-prepare eh when it comes to performances. pinagiisipan talaga nila, hindi lang siya for the sake na may ma-precept, ganon.

Researcher: Aside from Four Seasons, Four Colors, ano po po naiisip yung performances na napapa, as you say po, na nakapaghahandaan nila, napapabigay nila, all-in nila, ganon po?

V.J.: Every time na sumasali sila sa contests or guesting ng shows, ganyan, lagi nilang binibigay yung 100% nila. So, ayun, nakaka-inspire siya kasi. They do that, hindi lang para sa sarili nila, ganon. They always think kung paano sila maka, paano

nila may-inspire yung mga nanonood sa kanila. Kahit na yung mga nanonood is hindi pa nila fan, ganon. Paglabas mo ng event or pagkatapos mo silang panoorin, magiging fan, ganon nila, ganon. Ganon sila ka-empowering nga eh. Parang superpowers nga nila eh.

Researcher: Mmm. Superpower how po?

V.J.: Kasi through their music, nababago nila yung katao mo. So, it's like their superpowers.

Parang positive impact po, ganon nila.

Researcher: Alright, thank you po. Next question. Do you see that over time, Mamamoo's song lyrics and music video aesthetics have significantly helped you understand feminism better? Kuya Frey?

Jason: Yes. Ah, yes.

Researcher: How so po?

Jason: How so? I think it's just ano, siyempre ako guy ako. I identify myself as one. And for me, it's very, it gives freedom, I guess. In terms of, di lang ano eh. Kasi if you remember yung definition ko ng feminism, it's parang they have to do whatever it takes to achieve yung equality nga, diba? And I think one of the most important things that the feminism movement has made success is yung reaching out sa mga, not necessarily the marginalized, pero yung mga lalaki din. For me, it's... Ano rin eh?

Siyempre ang guys kasi... Kasi may sarili din silang respective society struggles. And for me, it really helps. Very inspiring yung mamamoo in a sense na nakikita mo sila. They can be so much more. And kaya ako nakikita ko, I can be so much more. For example, I mean, I can be a guy. I can just... I can just enjoy my privilege. Pero it's one thing to use my privilege for those who don't have that privilege. Parang ganun, it's... Ano ba? It's the sense of community. I mean, more than the... Siyempre the song lyrics and the aesthetics kasi. It's how... It's how... The group has built a community of people who want to help each other. I mean, through the... Through yung nakarelatet tayong community, nakagalit tayong mga moomos dun sa struggles ng room. Parang we find ourselves na, you know, helping each other para yung struggles, yung mga makatulong tayo sa iba. Maka... Maka... In a way, we inspire each other. In a way, we... We help people better. We reach out. We reach out to those in need. Kasi yung mga idols natin, yun yung... Yun yung pinakanta nila. Yun yung ginagawa nila sa totoong buhay. Ayan.

Researcher: You mentioned po na parang it helped you build the community po. Tapos you... As a male moomoo, parang nakita mo yung parang pagka-privilege mo. Tapos you also want to reach out and help people in the community who are not privileged as you. So parang... What issues of feminism have been highlighted by Mamamoo na nakikita mo po in a different light?

Jason: It's, I don't know. Siyempre, representation. Meaning... Sa science, may representation pa ng babae in all levels. Kasi very important yung perspective. Yung different perspective. Yung hindi pa kulala ka lang. In our... In our... Powerful positions. Alam mo yun, yung makita mo si Hwasa na nakasaot ng pang President.

And then, makapaisip ka. Ha? Parang wala namang masyado. Yun pa lang eh. It raises the discussion na gano'n ba karaming presidente na babae. And gano'n karaming babae yung presidente yung actually advocating for, you know, are actual feminists, you know. Tapos, it's a lot of... For me, it's really choice din. Very important. Kasi, isa sa mga main na issues. Parang yan ang mga issue ng babae, whether it's reproductive rights, whether it's their body, whether it's abuse, whether it's... Whichever. Whether it... Everything about them, society is trying to decide. Men are trying to decide for them. And very important yung messaging na sa community natin. And ma-reach out. Yung ating mga potential moos na going through something. Possibly issues sa... Yung issues with how they see themselves, issue with... Issue with yung purpose niya sa buhay, issue with their body, issue with their choices. Does it have to be decided by the government? Does it have to be decided by the parents? Does it have to be decided by yung powerful male? Powerful males around them, gano'n. So, yung... Yung music nila, it tells you every time na your life is your choice. Yan. So, very powerful yun for me. Mm-hmm. And, alam mo yun? Parang in a way, I've realized na as a guy, I've abused my privilege at some point in my life. And, I've guilty of mansplaining, if you're familiar with mansplaining. Yes po. And, yung...Yung music talaga nila, it's very... It really makes you think. With a lot...Ang dami kasi, it's very subtle image, really. Very subtle yung mga images nila. Na... Na...Kaya, hirap din ako na if you ask me out right now, right away, right now, ano ba yung specific na parts ng mga music video? Nahihirapan ako kasi it's not really...They don't really throw it out there, eh. Parang it's... Parang di ba it's just... Yung mga pinapakinggan natin, it's just supposed to be bop.. Karamihan ng songs, it's just supposed to be bop lang. Parang... We...This... We maganda siya sa ears. Pero... Parang the more you listen to it, parang the more you...The more you listen to

it, the more you start to question kung yung ginagawa ko ba, tama ba yung ginagawa ko. Yes. Am I doing things for the right people? Am I helping the right people?

Researcher: Mm-hmm. Thank you for that insightful answer, po. Kuya Frey. Ikaw naman po, ate VJ.

V.J.: In the end, um, all strive in, ano naman eh, like, lahat naman gusto ng equality. And especially since pinag-usapan natin is feminism, it's dedicated to helping both women and men fight stereotypes. Kasi syempre, kami din mga female. Kasi yun yung biological ako. Um, there are privileges din applicable to females na, hindi nagagawa ng mga males. So, in the end, equality talaga. Like, respecting the experiences, identities, strengths, gano'n. Empower all women to realize their rights. So, by them representing females and showing them everything they can. To prove themselves, gano'n. Like, different perspectives and experiencing. And experience. And always, gano'n. Ginagamit nila yung music as a form of art to open our eyes. So, yun yung importance ng feminism for me sa kanila. Parang yun yung po yung main issue. It's equality. It's equality po, gano'n po. In the end, equality talaga. Um. So, you have to, ano, realize and be diverse when it comes to perspective. Um.

Researcher: Uh, question po, ate VJ. Do you see that over time, mamamoo song lyrics and music videos, have helped you understand feminism better?

V.J.: Yes.

Researcher: How so?

V.J.: Kaya, um, gaya nga nang sabi ko, yung, um, the way they do their lyrics is hindi lang basta may meaning. Nag-iisipan talaga nila. And, um, they're very careful and thoughtful. Like, each and every sentences, the lyrics na gano'n ginagawa nila, gano'n.

Researcher: Would you say the same for music video rin po?

V.J. Yes. Especially nga doon sa music video ng hip. Kasi sa music video na yun, they represent different kinds of people. Kasi mayroon doon, um, part na, yun sabi ni Jason, nakasuot ng presidential outfit si Hwasa. And then, there's one scene na nagpo-protest si Wheein. And then, there's one scene na may mga kasama si Solar na drag queens. So, they represent different people all over the world..

Researcher: So, thank you po. Uh, last question po. Uh, what specific lyric or aesthetic, uh, whether it be from a music video or their stage performance of Mamamoo inspires you and why? Kuya Frey?

Jason: Okay. So, yung, yung saking kinuha ko doon sa five, five songs. Uh-huh. Na I'm most aso, uh, are about empowerment. So, yung una, ay, wala. Yung una, yung kay, yung Wanna Be Myself. Yung, uh, I wanna be myself, there is no set standard in the world. Uh-huh. Like this and like that, don't compare. Yun, I'm original, not different. You and I are not different. Every day, I wanna be myself. Parang, alam mo yun, parang, eh, yun. It's about being yourself. Choosing things because you want

to. Uh, and iba-iba tayo ng standards. We should hold ourselves on a different standards based on our experience. Tapos, si Hip, uh, yun, attention wherever you go. Uh, reflection, you can shine. Uh-huh. There's only one you in the world. Uh, but what's wrong? Why spit on your own face? So, dun sa lyrics, sinasabi niya na, sinasabi niya na, why do you, why do you hate yourself so much when you are unique? Uh, when, parang you shouldn't compare yourself to others, again. And then, sa Wind Flower naman, yun nga, yung, are we the only ones hurting? Uh, but like flower petals that will bloom again, get better day by day. Get better day by day. Uh, as in, yun, alam mo yun, it's, it's, it's a life, it's a life mantra. Uh, if, if you're down, slowly get up and find a way to, ano, find a way to get better. Tapos, yun. Sa, yun. Sa egotistic naman, it's, sa egotistic yung, ano eh, yung, parang you only think about yourself and just be with yourself. Itong lyric na to, this reminds me of, this reminds me of people who will force themselves onto you. Uh, they will manipulate you, they will gaslight you, they will tell you whatever you want to hear. But they clearly don't care about you. So, if sa tingin mo, they don't care about you, then why bother with them?

Researcher: So, parang cut them off, ganun po?

Jason: Yes. Parang, ano, focus, focus ka lang, focus ka lang doon sa mga tao na may pakialap sa'yo. Yan. Uh, tapos yung sa Gogobebe, uh, put your phone away and display that charm. Throw away things that give you a headache. Uh, take this drink and wash away your scars. Stop playing nice. Uh, dito, for me ah, ang nakita ko kasi dito, it's, I think it's them, it's them being tied down by what they should be as females. Kasi, parang, you have to be, you have to be a modern day, I, no, you have

to be a traditional Maria Clara. Na, you have, you always have to smile, you always have to be sweet. Kahit galit ka, you have to, you have to suppress yourself. Because that's not really feminine of you, ganun. Tapos, so I, I guess it's just, you know, it's just telling you to, it, it's your life. Huwag kang, huwag kang magpapa, huwag kang, uh, don't, kumbaga don't suppress yourself just to please other people. Uh-huh. Kasi, di ba yun usually ang expectation sa babae? Parang, uh. Uh. Minsan sinasabi nila na, don't, uh, don't dress too flashy kasi, ano, kailangan humble ka lang, ganun. Parang, everything's being dictated sa'yo. And in the end, nawawala yung concept of our identity. And itong si Gogobebe, it's like, nah, just, just, just do what you want. If this is what you want, then go. Uh-huh. Huwag ka ano ka, then do what you want. Parang, as long as you're not...hurting yourself or other people. As long as you're happy. Yes.

Researcher: Yes, yes. Okay po. Thank you po, ate VJ. Ay, sorry. Ay, sigelang po. Go lang po.

Jason: You see na, parang, di ba, si Gogobebe, it's, it's, it's, it's supposedly a fun song, eh. Uh-huh. Agree ka ba sa'kin, VJ?

V.J.: Uh-huh.

Jason: Maybe it's supposedly a fun song, pero it's trying to discuss yung, it's trying to mention stuff like, alam mo yung parang, it's, it's trying to talk about things that hurt.

V.J.: Yeah.

Jason: Things that normally you don't, you don't talk about. Parang, kasi di ba, mayroon tayong... Parang ano, suppressed memories, ganun, or parang suppressed feelings. Oo, parang, ano kasi tayo, may ano kasi tayo sa Filipino culture natin na we're trying...Pag, minsan, when, when, when we're together, and we're "trying to have fun", it's, paano ba, it's, it's yung concept na good vibes, good vibes lang. Meaning, we try to suppress yung emotions natin. Pero, ito, parang, it's trying to be more, ano, ano yung, ano yung word? It's trying to tell you to be more open about it. Uh, it's, it's telling you that... Okay. To feel these things. You're allowed to, you know, let loose sometimes. You don't always have to be perfect. Tapos, yung, alam mo yung paggamit ng word na scars for me, not sure if ito yung talagang tamang translation. Pero, the way it was used, parang, parang, it's, it's acknowledging that, you know, we're imperfect talaga. And, we can't be, we can't always be happy. And, that's fine.

Researcher: Okay po. Thank you po. Yes. Ikaw na po, Ate.

V.J.: Couldn't agree more. Parang, sabi mo na ata lahat. Pero...So, my, uh, my lyrics sa, ano, sa egoistic na gusto ko talaga, ito yung translation niya, um, I'm just who I am, don't need to be perfect. I'm just who I am, don't need to be changed. I'm beautiful in my own way. So, it's pretty self-explanatory. But, um, important talaga na you, you embrace yourself. Like, don't pretend to be someone kasi yun yung gusto nilang makita sa'yo, ganun. Just be yourself. Basically. And, ano, meron pang isang lyrics sa hit na medyo related dito. Nakal-translation niya is, I'm not sorry I'm so fierce. I'm apologetic. I'm so chick. I'm not sorry I'm so fabulous. I'm a queen even if,

even when I'm standing alone. So, it's related in a sense na yun. Just embrace your own wilderness, uniqueness. Don't be afraid to be yourself. Ganyan. Kahit ano pang sabihin ng iba, eh, ano mong gagawa nila? Ikaw, ikaw yan eh. I'm me. You're you. We're different. So... We don't have to compare each other. But, um, use it like a way to understand each other. Ganun. So that, ano, magkaroon tayo ng diversity and equality. Ganun.

Researcher: Baka meron po yung additional na, ano, kuwari aesthetic na gusto nyo or kaya music video, ganun po. If wala, okay lang naman po.

V.J.: Mmm...Wala na akong maisip, eh. Okay lang pa. Nasabi na rin kasi lahat ni Jason.

Researcher: Very insightful nga mga kasagot nyo po, eh. So, that ends the interview itself po talaga. Thank you po!